

H2020 DAEMON Project
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Deliverable 5.3

Final evaluation results and proof-of-concept demonstrations

Abstract

This document, Deliverable 5.3 (D5.3), serves as the culmination of the effort of Work Package 5 (WP5) within the DAEMON project. Building upon Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2, D5.3 focuses on the comprehensive validation and performance evaluation of all Network Intelligence (NI) solutions designed in WP3 and WP4 and previously presented in Deliverables 3.3 and 4.3 of the project.

The core objective of this document is therefore to summarize the DAEMON activities in validating the research conducted within WP2, WP3 and WP4, by leveraging eight distinct evaluations designed to assess performance against nine target Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) within well-defined scenarios. Each evaluation utilizes a specific set of technical tools to execute 34 activities encompassing all eight NI services outlined in WP2.

Furthermore, D5.3 presents five additional demonstrations of NI functionalities, including a pilot (TRL 5) involving real customers, and 3 further Proofs-of-Concept (PoCs) and data-driven evaluations, all performed during Year 3 of the project. These evaluations, alongside a separate demonstration showcasing integrated NI solutions within the DAEMON NI Plane architecture, provide valuable insights into the technical readiness of the developed solutions.

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List of Acronyms

4G	– Fourth Generation
5G	– Fifth Generation
6G	– Sixth Generation
AI	– Artificial Intelligence
AQM	– Active Queue Management
B5G	– Beyond 5G
BS	– Base Station
BSR	– Buffer Status Report
DMARL	– Distributed Multi Agent RL
DQN	– Deep Q-Network
EC	– Energy Consumption
FFT	– Fast Fourier Transform
FL	– Federated Learning
IoT	– Internet of Things
KPI	– Key Performance Indicator
LDPC	– Low-Density Parity Check
MCS	– Multilevel Coordinate Search
MNO	– Mobile Network Operator
MSE	– Mean Squared Error
NFR	– Network Functional Requirement
NI	– Network Intelligence
NIF	– Network Intelligence Function
NIFD	– Network Intelligence Function Descriptor
NIS	– Network Intelligence Stratum
PCA	– Principal Components Analysis
PLT	– Page Load Time
PPO	– Proximal Policy Optimization
PRB	– Physical Resource Block
QA	– Quantum Annealer
RL	– Reinforcement Learning
RLC	– Radio Link Control
SLA	– Service Level Agreement
SFC	– Service Function Chain
SFC-E	– Service Function Chain Embedding
SNR	– Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SO	– Service Orchestration
TD	– Tail Drop
TRL	– Technical Readiness Level
UPF	– User Plane Function
vBS	– Virtualized Base Station
VNF	– Virtual Network Function
WP	– Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the updated evaluation results from DAEMON's Work Package 5 (WP5) for the Network Intelligent (NI) solutions designed in WP3 and WP4 in the context of WP2's NI Plane architecture. These solutions target eight specific services enhanced by NI capabilities.

WP5 validates the activities and designs from WP3 and WP4 by systematically collecting and analyzing key performance indicators (KPIs), defined in the Description of Action. Our evaluation methodology employs a comprehensive suite of tools, including experimental testbeds, simulators, emulators, and relevant measurement data, defined in D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [1] of the project. Also, WP5 integrates solutions from WP3 and WP4 into these evaluation environments. WP5 provided essential feedback to WP2, WP3, and WP4 to optimize the design and operational efficiency of the project's NI solutions.

This document details the latest results from WP5 activities. We report on the performance of NI functionalities developed in the project and outline the executed proof-of-concept demonstrations. Moreover, this document reports the validation of an implementation of DAEMON's NI Plane.

In summary, the document comprises six sections:

- Section 1 outlines the evolution of the DAEMON ecosystem architecture and the validation methodology for WP3 and WP4 activities and designs.
- Section 2 presents the evaluation of the DAEMON Network Intelligence (NI) Plane.
- Section 3 details KPI validation results and methodologies for each evaluation activity, including those conducted during the project's third year. Previous results are referenced for completeness. This section also addresses the satisfaction of network functional requirements (NFRs).
- Section 4 summarizes open-source datasets and software tools used in evaluations, with links to the relevant sections.
- Section 5 discusses proof-of-concept demonstrations for the evaluation of the NI functionalities developed in DAEMON, highlighting their performance and technical readiness level. New demonstrations from the third year are featured in this section.
- Section 6 provides conclusions and a final outlook.

1 Introduction

Overall, DAEMON has focused on the integration of 8 different Network Intelligent Services (NIS) into a common network architecture known as Network Intelligent Plane (NIP): Compute-aware radio scheduling, multi-timescale edge resource management, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces, in-backhaul support for service intelligence, energy-aware VNF orchestration, capacity forecasting, automated anomaly response, and self-learning management and orchestration.

To this end, DAEMON utilizes a methodology that integrates activities from Work Packages (WPs) 2, 3, 4, and 5, as outlined in Figure 1. Vertically, the DAEMON project addresses distinct services through Network Intelligent Functionalities (NIFs), each focusing on specific aspects of a service. Horizontally, these NIF design and evaluation activities traverse Work Packages (WPs) 2, 3/4, and 5 in a structured progression. WP2 established the foundation with functional and non-functional NIF requirements and guidelines for their embedded network intelligence. WP2's proposed NIP architecture further enables DAEMON's Network Intelligence Orchestrator (NIO) to manage these NIFs homogeneously. Guided by this foundation, WP3 and WP4 undertook NIF design. Along with detailed NIF designs, WP2 and WP3 deliverables specify NIP representations, interfaces outlined in WP2, and the relevant functional requirements.

Figure 1. Methodology of pursuing Objective 2 through activities.

Deliverable 5.3 (D5.3) reports the progress we have made within WP5 towards validating, testing and assessing the performance of these services and their composite functionalities (NIFs), in the context of WP2's NI Plane. In this way, WP5 has a two-fold role in DAEMON, as follows.

1. Validate the NI Plane itself, along with prototypes for managing NIO functionalities such as NIF-C/NIF/NIS deployment, NIF-C sharing, cooperative NIS behavior, and conflict resolution. Clearly defined placeholders and guidelines (N-MAKE-K) within the NI Plane enable the development of NI solutions.
2. Evaluate and validate each NI solution developed within WP3 and WP4. WP5 transformed these solutions into NIF-Cs/NIFs/NISs according to the N-MAKE-K approach, allowing for deployment and management by the DAEMON NI Plane. A first batch of evaluations was already presented in D5.2 [1]. These WP5 prototypes then underwent a second evaluation phase, presented in this deliverable.

Figure 2 below illustrates this vision with some examples of NIS/NIFs evaluated in Section 3. Specifically, Figure 2 illustrates the DAEMON ecosystem, demonstrating the integration of components developed across various work packages (WP2/WP3/WP4/WP5), such integration realized the DAEMON ecosystem. WP2 defined the DAEMON architecture, also called the NI Plane, and the foundational N-MAKE-K approach and taxonomy for building network intelligence (NI) solutions (blue boxes).

Each NI solution, deployed as an NIS (see the inset blue box), consists of multiple NIFs; each NIF further breaks down into modular building blocks (NIF-Cs). We refer the reader to D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [1] of the project for complete details about NIS and NIF definitions. The NI Plane then orchestrates the complete lifecycle of all elements through dedicated managers: the NIF-C Manager, NIF Manager, and NIO. While deployment functions rely on existing Service Management and Orchestration environments (e.g., OpenStack/Kubernetes), the NIO and its managers handle NI-specific tasks. Repositories store NIFs and NISs.

Figure 2. DAEMON ecosystem.

It is important to remark that the DAEMON NI Plane and its NI solutions integrate seamlessly with the established Kubernetes-based Service Management and Orchestration environment. More precisely, deployment manifests (NISDs) are Kubernetes manifests enhanced with annotations that describe N-MAKE-K details and planning targets for an NIS. Individual NIF-Cs map to Kubernetes Pods, with NIFs of a single NIS sharing a namespace. During operation, a publish/subscribe mechanism (e.g., Zenoh server) facilitates NIF-C/NIF sharing or cooperation. The NIO, preventing conflicts, orchestrates configuration actions across NIFs and NISs. Complete details will be provided in Section 2 next.

2 Evaluation of DAEMON Network Intelligence Plane

This section presents a reference implementation of the proposed NI Plane. We refer the reader to D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [1] for full details about the organization and operation of the DAEMON NI Plane. It is worth noting that the implementation described here does not pretend to be a comprehensive full-fledged realization of the NI Plane, rather it is a proof-of-concept intended to showcase the viability of this architectural innovation proposed by the project, as a complement to its design. Instead, complete implementations of the NI Plane, informed by the DAEMON design, are expected to be carried out beyond the end of project by other actions or organizations.

We next outline how two sample NIFs can be described and orchestrated to form a NIS. Then, we present a practical implementation of the target NIS. Finally, assuming that both NIFs are acting upon the same network element (i.e., reallocating and scaling the same network service), we show how selected orchestration functionalities of the NI Plane operate in practice.

2.1 Combining NIFs to build a NIS

One of the key features of the NI Plane is to allow the creation, management, and deployment of NISs. In this section, we showcase a key functionality of such Plane: combining two NIFs to create a NIS. We refer the reader to D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [1] of the project for a thorough presentation of the NIS and NIF concepts, and of how they fit the DAEMON vision for NI integration in mobile network architectures.

Figure 3. A federated learning-powered anomaly detection and service relocation NIS.

The first NIF employed in the representative example implements a federated learning (FL)-powered anomaly detection algorithm, enabling anomaly detection at the edge (NIF1 in Figure 3). This means that the AI model for detecting anomalies is trained locally on individual devices, while a central controller is responsible for retaining a global model and, therefore, enhancing the local AI model. This way, data privacy is preserved while the approach still benefits from a collaborative learning process.

The second NIF used in the example deploys a service relocation algorithm that collects real-time monitoring information from the edge, such as CPU load, memory load, used storage, and end-to-end latency measured at the client side. Leveraging a multi-criteria decision-making function, this algorithm dynamically relocates services based on real-time data (NIF2 in Figure 3), ensuring optimal resource utilization and service performance. It is important to note that by service relocation, we mean relocation of stateless services, a procedure that deploys the correct service instance on the selected edge and terminates all previous service instances running on the other edges to save the edge resources.

Following the proposed framework based on the N-MAPE-K to define NIS, we effectively combined the federated learning-powered anomaly detection with service relocation capabilities to achieve the NIS. Figure 3 shows the N-MAPE-K based diagram of the resulting NIS. We refer the reader to D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [1] of the project for a complete treatise of the N-MAPE-K representation that the DAEMON project introduced as a uniform model for NIS and NIF processed by the NI Plane.

In the context of this specific example, by integrating the federated learning approach, the NIS ensures that anomalies are detected securely and efficiently across the network's edge devices. The NIS also leverages the monitoring information collected from the edge to make informed decisions about service relocation, maximizing the network's overall performance and responsiveness.

Figure 4. NI procedures for the example NIS.

Before implementation, the NIS needs to be created, which is a procedure that includes validating the existence of constituting NIFs, and if one of them is not found, the proper models are created and trained, resulting in NIF images that are necessary for NIS composition and deployment. These NI procedures are visually illustrated in Figure 4, so as to clearly show how they drive interactions between the different components of the NI Plane presented in D5.2 [1] of the project.

2.2 Implementation of the target NIS

Communication among the NIS elements is implemented using the Eclipse Zenoh data communication framework, which provides a reliable and scalable solution for exchanging data between devices and components within the network. Additionally, the implementation utilizes Kubernetes to realize the NIF Manager and the NIF-C Manager, as shown in Figure 5. Kubernetes helps manage the deployment, scaling, and orchestration of the NIF-Cs, ensuring smooth operation and efficient service relocation.

Figure 5. Cloud-to-edge deployment of the proposed NIS and its different components.

The Smart Highway [2] located on top of the E313 highway in Belgium served as the edge environment for testing and validating the effectiveness of the proposed NIS, providing a real-world scenario to assess its performance and potential benefits for vehicular services. Figure 5 shows a high-level representation of the deployment and how the components were deployed at the cloud (centralized server) and edge (roadside units at the Smart Highway). As shown in Figure 5 Zenoh-based data managers are used for collecting metrics related to edge performance (CPU, memory, storage) and service performance (end-to-end latency). The edge performance metrics are used in the anomaly detection process (NIF1), while both edge metrics and service metrics are used in the service relocation process (NIF2). In the latter case, the service performance is measured as end-to-end latency collected from the client. The client is deployed on the test vehicle, which measures latency in communication with services deployed at the network edges in real-time. Once the final decision on the service relocation is made, i.e., when NIS decides to which network service the test vehicle should connect, the subscriber running in the vehicle receives all necessary information for connecting to the service.

The outcome of the deployment of this NIS is an edge-aware service relocation, which makes efficient decisions on when and where the service should be relocated to ensure minimum end-to-end latency at every moment, taking into account not only the edge performance but also its stability in terms of possible anomalies. Such intelligent services pave the way towards more reliable and high-performing deployments of vertical services in future 6G ecosystems. Nevertheless, the two NIFs presented in this section could produce conflicting decisions, which might severely affect the overall NIS performance. Thus, it is essential to ensure proper conflict resolution, as explained in Section 2.3.

2.3 Managing conflicts within a NIS

The conflict resolution procedure is one of the NI Plane procedures with paramount importance for the stability and smooth operation of the network. The architectural details of the procedure are described in detail in D4.3, [3] Section 5.1, while in this section, we develop and demonstrate how to enforce this procedure when conflicts emerge between two different NIFs algorithms acting on the same network functions but configuring different values for the target parameters.

During the prototyping, Kubernetes was used as the main deployment infrastructure, while the following phases of the conflict resolution process were addressed: (i) NIFD creation and annotation following

the N-MAPE-K taxonomy; (ii) initial assessment based on N-MAPE-K types; (iii) conflict identification; and, (iv) conflict resolution. The process is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Conflict resolution process.

To demonstrate the conflict resolution capabilities of the NI Plane, two NIFs were created and deployed. The first NIF includes a federated learning-powered anomaly detection algorithm (identical to the NIF1 presented in Section 2.1) extended with a basic service resource management capability (e.g., scale in/out on resource under/ overutilization). The second NIF remains identical to the NIF2, as explained in the previous section. The configuration actions of the above NIFs (scale in/out and service relocation) cause conflicts because they may act upon the same service, driving the network to unstable conditions if executed in a similar time window. Therefore, in the prototype, we showcase the identification of the conflict while appropriate policy rules are generated before deployment to avoid unstable conditions by orchestrating the configuration actions.

Initially, the NIFDs of both NIFs are created. Since each NIF-C is deployed as Pod in Kubernetes, we create the NIFDs directly from the Kubernetes manifest files. In this direction, the NIFDs are generated by extending such files in two ways: (i) labels are used to discriminate between different N-MAPE-K types (Sensor, Monitor, Analyse, Plan, Execute, Effector); (ii) annotations are used to specify the configuration capabilities of the NIF in a self-descriptive way. This process is illustrated in steps (1) and (2) in Figure 6.

```

template:
  metadata:
    annotations:
      kompose.cmd: kompose convert
      kompose.version: 1.28.0 (c4137012e)
      daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.memory: "true"
      daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.memory: "true"
      daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.cpu: "true"
      daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.cpu: "true"
    creationTimestamp: null
  labels:
    io.kompose.network/fl-dbscan-testing-default: "true"
    io.kompose.service: flcontroller
    daemon.nmapek.type.analyze: "true"
    daemon.nmapek.type.knowledge: "true"
  spec:
    containers:
      env:
        - name: host_ip
    
```

Figure 7. Descriptor of a NIF (NIFD) that can perform service scale out.

```

template:
  metadata:
    annotations:
      kompose.cmd: kompose convert
      kompose.version: 1.28.0 (c4137012e)
      daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector: "true"
    creationTimestamp: null
  labels:
    io.kompose.network/fl-dbscan-testing-default: "true"
    io.kompose.service: rsu_orch
    daemon.nmapek.type.plan: "true"
  spec:
    containers:
      env:
        - name: host_ip
    
```

Figure 8. Descriptor of a NIF (NIFD) that can perform service relocation.

The NIFDs of the two aforementioned NIFs are illustrated in Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively. The first NIFD, as shown in Figure 7, describes a NIF with two components (e.g., as in NIF1), one is of type "Analyze" since it analyzed the received input from different FL clients according to a global model, and "Knowledge" since adjusts the global model to offer federated learning-powered anomaly detection capabilities to the FL clients. As shown in Figure 4, the "Knowledge" component of NIF2 can be used to scale in/out services or provide enriched information to other NIFs (e.g., information to allow NIF2 to perform service relocation). In detail, the possible configuration targets follow the prefix "daemon.nmapek.analyze.target" followed by the resource they can configure (i.e., CPU and memory). This same structure is already used in the Kubernetes manifest files (for instance, in "spec.containers.resources.requests.memory"). In the same manner, Figure 8 illustrates the NIFD of a second NIF (e.g., as in NIF2). This NIF is of type "Plan" since it can perform service relocation. Unlike NIF1, NIF2 uses the "spec.containers.nodeSelector" annotation of a Kubernetes manifest file to specify the specific worker where the NIF should run. This may conflict with the CPU and memory annotations existing in the NIF2 manifest file.

Then, the CSOI module is responsible for parsing the provided NIFDs to identify the N-MAPE-K types included in the NIF and the possible configuration actions that the NIFs can generate (step 3 in Figure 6). In addition, an initial assessment is performed to quickly identify if a conflict process is required (step 4). The CSOI communicates with the PolicyIC module, which forwards only the relevant parameters to the Conflict Resolution module. The Conflict Resolution module executes a thorough analysis to identify any possible conflict (step 6). The analysis is based on a set of conflict resolution matrices and the list of already deployed NISs.

In this direction, a conflict may be identified between an existing NIS and a new NIS to be deployed. In case of conflicts, the conflict solver selector is triggered. This module selects the appropriate Conflict Solver from a set of available Conflict Solvers (step 7). The Conflict Solver is a software component that can resolve a conflict during the deployment and operation phases. This means that it may update the existing capabilities of a NIS or generate Policies as a set of rules (step 8) to handle conflicting situations during the operation of conflicting NIFs. An example of a rule is also illustrated in Figure 6, where NIF2 may wait 30 seconds before relocating the service if NIF1 already scaled it. In the case of new Policies, the Policy Manager is responsible for adding them to the Policies database and becoming responsible for keeping them updated during the whole lifecycle. After all checks are made and any Policies are generated and activated, the new NIS is deployed by the K8S Deployer (steps 10 and 11).

During operation, all the certified NIF coexist conflict-free in the same Kubernetes Cluster (step 11). In the case of a conflicting NIF, the candidate conflicting NIF communicates with the PolicyIC (and NIS Planning Orchestrator) before any conflicting action is realized (step 12). Then, the NIS Planning Orchestrator is responsible for retrieving the related Policies from the Policy Manager and applying their rules. After the related Policies are executed, the PolicyIC may or may not give the green light to the NIF to complete the requested configuration (step 14).

3 Evaluation of DAEMON Network Intelligence services

In the following, we summarize the evaluation results in terms of the activities carried out in the project on NI services during the third year of execution, and the key findings derived from such evaluations.

3.1 Summary of evaluation results

The ambitious vision and objectives of DAEMON call for a credible and solid validation and performance evaluation of the eight NI services introduced in WP3 and WP4 to improve B5G networks' performance, sustainability and reliability. In this respect, we developed full-scale NI services, which achieve the following objectives set out at the beginning of the action.

- **Increase network performance and efficiency (DAEMON Objective 2.1)** by supporting network functionalities that allow for extremely fast and adaptive control of (i) RIS in a new Beyond Edge domain, (ii) computational resources in the Edge domain, and (iii) support for service intelligence in the user plane of the Transport domain.
- **Enable the sustainable operation of B5G systems (DAEMON Objective 2.2)** by means of solutions for (iv) computation-aware radio scheduling, (v) energy-aware VNF orchestration and (vi) self-learning MANO.
- **Ensure an extreme reliability of zero-touch B5G (DAEMON Objective 2.3)** by exploiting (vii) capacity failure avoidance via anticipatory allocation and (viii) anomaly detection.
- **Ensuring that all KPIs (DAEMON Objective 4) are achieved**, by providing objective evidence of the advantage of proposed NI solutions in realistic settings targeting specific innovation aspects using a combination of evaluation methodologies that encompass:
 - simulation and evaluation-based evaluations
 - prototyping and experimental evaluations
 - large dataset-driven evaluations.

In order to assess the performance of the NI-assisted functionalities and demonstrate how they can achieve the KPI targets set out below, we have performed dedicated activities. Table 1 below groups all the activities throughout the whole duration of the project, identifying the references to the corresponding design and evaluations, and reporting the main findings in terms of performance.

Table 1. List of all activities and main findings per activity.

Activity	NI Function	Design reported in	Evaluation reported in	Main findings
A1	Reliable RAN virtualisation	D3.2, Sec. 2.1	D5.2, Sec. 4.1	29-50% energy savings per server
A2	AI-driven O-Cloud	D3.3, Sec. 3.3	D5.3, Sec. 3.2.2	3x higher energy-efficiency (joules per bit) in average, and 15x higher cost-efficiency (\$ per Mbps) in average
A3	Application aware radio scheduling	D3.3, Sec. 3.4	D5.3, Sec. 3.2.3	The accuracy of the best classification algorithms studied is close to 99%, yielding an optimality gap of less than 1%
A4	AI-aided energy-driven vRAN orchestration	D4.3, Sec. 3.3	D5.2, Sec. 4.2.1 D5.3, Sec. 3.3.1	Up to 12.5% of power savings without sacrificing RAN performance, and up to 12.5% of energy bill savings
A5	Energy-driven joint vRAN/edge orchestration	D4.3, Sec. 3.4	D5.3, Sec. 3.3.2	Overall energy saving of a vRAN orchestration system up to 10%, and up to 30% of power consumption savings in a GPU server
A6	Energy-aware deployment of VNFs for generic Edge computing	D3.3, Sec. 4.3	D5.3, Sec. 3.3.3	Energy consumption reduction up to 90%
A7	Combining VNFs at the edge	D4.2, Sec. 2.1	D5.3, Sec. 3.3.4	Energy consumption reduction between 54% and 59%
A8	AI-enhanced MANO	D4.3, Sec. 6.1	D5.3, Sec. 3.3.5	Response time of the AI algorithm of 280-330ms

A9	Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection	D4.3, Sec. 5.1	D5.3, Sec. 3.4.1	91% anomaly detection rate and 90% precision-recall AUC with at least 85% scoring in both precision and recall
A10	Compute-aware scheduling analytics	D3.3, Sec. 3.5	D5.3, Sec. 3.5.4	Up to 50% reduction of computational resources needed at the edge
A11	Multi-timescale network slice reservation	D3.1, Sec. 5.1 D3.2, Sec. 3.1 D3.3, Sec. 4.1	D5.1, Sec. 4.4.2	Reduction >50% of computational resources based on pro-active service relocation with guarantees of service response time
A12	WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management	D3.1, Sec. 5.2	D5.1, Sec. 4.3	Improved response time by 99%
A13	Data-driven resource orchestration	D3.1, Sec. 5.4 D3.2, Sec. 3.4	D5.2, Sec. 4.4.4	Mitigation of the stringent latency budgets of some applications via UPF function placement
A14	Multi-timescale network slice reservation	D3.3, Sec. 4.5	D5.3, Sec. 3.5.3	Near-optimal performance proven theoretically and shown experimentally
A15 A26	Energy-aware VNF orchestration	D5.1, Sec. 3.2.4 D4.1, Sec. 3.1.3	D5.1, Sec. 3.2.4 D5.2, Sec. 4.4.9	15.9% reduction in dynamic energy consumption and up to 66.2% in idle energy consumption
A16	Towards autonomous VNF scaling	D4.3, Sec. 6.2	D5.3, Sec. 3.5.5	Minimization of the number of SLA violations that generates OPEX savings compared to a traditional overprovisioning approach
A17	Auto-scaling Virtualized RAN caches	D4.1, Sec. 6.2.2	D5.2, Sec. 4.4.8	Up to 154% higher performance (gain of sum delay utilities) with respect to a static femtocaching model
A18	Random Forest in programmable switches	D3.3, Sec. 6.1	D5.3, Sec. 3.8.2	Inference fully performed in the user plane, at line rate and with latency in the order of tens of nanoseconds
A19	Anomaly detection for a roaming platform	D4.1, Sec. 5.2 D4.2, Sec. 4.2	D5.3, Sec. 3.5.2	Device-level anomaly detection for IoT that is agnostic to the vertical, using only signaling information from the roaming platform connecting the IoT devices globally
A20	Anticipatory capacity allocation	D4.1, Sec. 4.1 D4.2, Sec. 3.1	D5.1, Sec. 4.6.1 D5.2, Sec. 4.3.3 D5.2, Sec. 4.5.1	Complexity (mean training time) reduction by 50%, and traffic forecast error (mean square error) reduction by at least 30%, peaking at 50%
A21	Virtual Machine reservation	D4.1, Sec. 4.2 D4.2, Sec. 3.2	D5.1, Sec. 4.6.2 D5.2, Sec. 4.5.2	Reduction of the cost of anticipatory reservation of VMs by 40%, and reduction of SLA violations below 0.5% of the time, while also reducing the computational cost
A22	Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX	D4.1, Sec. 4.1 D4.2, Sec. 3.1	D5.1, Sec. 4.6.3 D5.2, Sec. 4.5.6	OPEX savings of around 30% with respect to state-of-the-art solutions and within 10% of the optimal, achieved without any prior knowledge of the expression characterizing the OPEX
A23	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	D3.3, Sec. 5	D5.3, Sec. 3.7	17-27 dBs gains over the noise floor, equivalent to more than 100% capacity increase in low-SNR scenarios

A25	Anomaly forecasting in mobile service traffic at base station level	D4.1, Sec. 4.1 D4.2, Sec. 4.3	D5.2, Sec. 4.3.3	Improved performance and stability under varied input ranges
A27	Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing	D4.3, Sec. 4.4	D5.3, Sec. 3.6.4	Near-optimal performance proven theoretically and shown experimentally
A28	Efficient backhaul circuit switching	D3.3, Sec. 6.2	D5.2, Sec. 4.7.2	34% throughput gains, 10-100 times faster than state-of-the-art.
A29	ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs	D3.3, Sec. 3.2	D5.3, Sec. 3.2.5	80% more traffic served on the computing capacity, while achieving 99.999% reliability in decoding for vRAN base station under any traffic congestion factor
A30	Placement and routing for network services	D4.1, Sec. 6.1 D4.2, Sec. 5.1 D4.3, Sec. 6.1	D5.2, Sec. 4.2.6 D5.3, Sec. 3.3.6	30% computational savings, 30% OPEX savings
A31	Anticipatory capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing with a priori system knowledge	D4.3, Sec. 4.1.1	D5.3, Sec. 3.6.5	Over 40% OPEX costs reduction, mainly obtained by limiting SLA violations
A32	Anticipatory meta-learned capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing without a priori knowledge	D2.3, Sec. 7.1.3	D5.3, Sec. 3.6.6	Up to 40% reduction of the cost of anticipatory admission control and resource allocation of network slices, while limiting the occurrence of SLA violations to less than 0.5% of time
A33	Energy-prudent vRAN management with loss meta-learning	D4.3, Sec. 3.3.1	D5.3, Sec. 3.3.7	Up to 30% reduction of the energy required for computation and instantiation of vRANs
A34	FEC decoding on Quantum Processing Unit	D5.3, Sec. 3.2.6	D5.3, Sec. 3.2.6	Implementation of a functional decoder in a Quantum Processing Unit, although reliability is not yet satisfactory for carrier-grade systems

The activities summarized in Table 1 jointly meet the 9 performance Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set out by the DAEMON consortium at the beginning of the project. We next report, for each individual KPI, a brief description of the indicator, the list of relevant activities, and how the evaluation of such activities demonstrates the achievement of the performance targets associated to the specific KPI.

3.1.1 KPI 1 (K1): VNF energy consumption reduction

Recent studies predict that energy consumption in softwarized mobile networks could rise by 25%, largely due to active cooling requirements. DAEMON addresses this challenge with NI designed with WP3 and WP4, aiming to reduce energy costs by up to 25% through strategic VNF placement. Additionally, NI-assisted VNFs can dynamically adjust their energy footprint based on location and operational context, potentially leading to another 25% in savings.

A summary of the activities targeting K1 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A1: Reliable RAN virtualization	Between 29% and 50% savings per Distributed Unit server.
A2: AI-driven O-Cloud	Up to 3x gains in energy efficiency (bits per joule), in average with respect to today's standard approach.
A6: Energy-aware deployment of VNFs for generic Edge computing	We can reduce the energy consumption of Generic Edge Computing system up to 90%
A15/A26: Energy-aware VNF orchestration	15.9% reduction in dynamic energy consumption and up to 66.2% in idle energy consumption.
A4: AI-aided energy-driven RAN orchestration	Up to 12.5% of power savings without sacrificing RAN performance
A5: AI-aided RAN/edge orchestration	Up to 30% of power consumption savings in a GPU server
A29: ML radio resource scheduling for virtualized RANs	Capability of serving up to 80% more traffic on the same using the same computing capacity
A7: Combining VNFs at the edge	Reduction between 54% and 59% compared to the other assignment policies.
A33: Energy-prudent vRAN management with loss meta-learning	Up to 30% of power consumption savings in a vRAN (total energy for CU and DUs)

3.1.2 KPI 2 (K2): Saving of computational resources at the edge

It has been shown before that intelligent radio and compute scheduling in O-RAN architectures can reduce computing resource requirements in virtualized base stations by up to 20%, with negligible performance loss. DAEMON's advanced NI design aims to build upon these techniques (Objectives 1-3) to achieve an ambitious 40% reduction target in relevant scenarios.

A summary of the activities targeting K2 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A1: Reliable RAN virtualization	Between 29% and 50% savings per Distributed Unit (DU) server
A2: AI-driven O-Cloud	$(N-1)*100\%$ savings, where N is the number of DUs
A7: Combining VNFs at the edge	Reduction between 54% and 59% compared to the other assignment policies
A10: Compute-aware scheduling analytics	Compute resource savings up to 50%
A11: AI-enhanced edge orchestration	Reduction >50% of computational resources with guarantees of service response time
A15 / A26: Energy-aware VNF orchestration	15.9% reduction in dynamic energy consumption, up to 66.2% in idle energy consumption for VNF/KNFs deployed in the edge
A20: Anticipatory capacity allocation	50% complexity (mean training time) reduction
A21: Virtual Machine reservation	40% reduction in the number of anticipatorily reserved of VMs
A30: Placement and routing for network services	30% of saving in terms of computational resources leading to 30% OPEX savings
A31: Anticipatory capacity allocation	Over 40% OPEX costs reduction

with overbooked admission control for network slicing with a priori system knowledge	
A32: Anticipatory meta-learned capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing without a priori knowledge	Up to 40% reduction of the cost of anticipatory admission control and resource allocation of network slices

3.1.3 KPI 3 (K3): Response time of AI-based NI algorithms

DAEMON harnesses the power of highly elastic AI models to create NI algorithms that balance accuracy with the strict delay and reliability demands of sensitive traffic. This approach aims to deliver a groundbreaking solution, i.e., AI-based NI with response time assurances.

A summary of the activities targeting K3 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A8: AI-enhanced MANO	10-ms inference via the AI, contributing to an overall Response time of the MANO algorithm of 280-330ms.
A9: Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection	200-250 ms response time of the algorithm based on Federated Learning (FL)
A15 / A26: Energy-aware VNF orchestration	Instantaneous answer for infrastructures of less than 20 nodes
A17: Auto-scaling Virtualized RAN caches	Up to 154% higher performance (gain of sum delay utilities) with respect to static femtocaching model
A18: Random Forest in programmable switches	User-plane inference latency in the order of tens of ns
A19: Anomaly detection for a roaming platform	0.7 ms inference for a single mobile device, with a total inference time below 20 minutes for 1,7M devices
A28: Efficient backhaul circuit switching	34% throughput gains, 10-100 times faster than state-of-the-art

3.1.4 KPI 4 (K4): OPEX savings

Previous studies showed that AI models trained with cost-aware loss functions can prevent SLA violations and reduce OPEX by up to 40%. These promising results focus on localized solutions. DAEMON's architecture, by enabling structured coordination of NI instances, aims to unlock even greater cost savings – potentially up to 60%.

A summary of the activities targeting K4 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A1: Reliable RAN virtualization	Between 29% and 50% of energy bill savings per DUt server
A2: AI driven O-Cloud	15x cost-efficiency (\$/Mbps) gains in average
A4: AI-aided energy-driven RAN orchestration	Up to 12.5% of energy bill savings
A15 / A26: Energy-aware VNF orchestration	15.9% reduction in dynamic energy consumption and up to 66.2% in idle energy consumption
A16: Towards autonomous VNF scaling	Minimization of the number of SLA violations, generating OPEX savings compared to a traditional overprovisioning approach
A17: Auto-scaling Virtualized RAN caches	Up to 154% higher performance (gain of sum delay utilities) with respect to static femtocaching model
A20: Anticipatory capacity allocation	Reduced Mean Square Error (MSE) of the traffic forecast by at least 30%, peaking at 50% for some services, which directly implies less OPEX per service

	supported
A22: Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX	OPEX savings of around 30% with respect to state-of-the-art solutions and within 10% of the optimal, achieved without any prior knowledge of the expression characterizing the OPEX
A29: ML radio resource scheduling for virtualized RANs	Up to 90% of increased traffic served with the same computing capacity used by the baseline solution
A30: Placement and routing for network services	30% of saving in terms of computational resources leading for the same performance (in terms of acceptance ratio)
A31: Anticipatory capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing with a priori system knowledge	More than 40% OPEX cost reduction
A32: Anticipatory meta-learned capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing without a priori knowledge	Reduction of SLA violations below 0.5% of the time, while also reducing the computational cost, thus cutting the OPEX of the operator by up to 30%
A33: Energy-prudent vRAN management with loss meta-learning	Increase of profit of above 36% thanks to the reduction of OPEX due to better prediction with imperfect knowledge and thanks to a better admission control decision

3.1.5 KPI 5 (K5): Reliability

It has been shown before SLAs can be met reliably with exceptional consistency (between 99.9% and 99.99% uptime). DAEMON's cooperative, multi-timescale orchestration can improve the data available to decision-making algorithms. This enhanced intelligence will drive even higher reliability, potentially meeting the extremely strict demands of Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) in specific scenarios.

A summary of the activities targeting K5 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A1: Reliable RAN virtualization	99.999% reliability in L1 vDU processing
A2: AI-driven O-Cloud	99.999% reliability in L1 vDU processing
A11: AI-enhanced edge orchestration	Service reliability >99.999% via ml-supported proactive reallocation.
A13: Data-driven resource orchestration	High reliability via UPF orchestration for users of a same vertical, as proven in Table 26 of D3.2 (Section 3.4)
A29: ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs	99.999% reliability in decoding for vRAN base station under any traffic congestion level
A34: FEC decoding on Quantum Annealers	Decoding reliability of QPU-based solutions is not carrier grade

3.1.6 KPI 6 (K6): Wireless Capacity (bps/m2) increase

DAEMON's NI-controlled Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) dramatically increase wireless network capacity in many realistic scenarios; hence we target a 100% capacity increase in the context of DAEMON.

A summary of the activities targeting K6 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A23: Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	Between 17 and 27 dBs over the noise floor (i.e., >100% capacity increase in low-SNR scenarios)

3.1.7 KPI 7 (K7): Anomaly detection recall and sensitivity

Current network anomaly detection methods achieve a precision-recall AUC between 0.66-0.88, highlighting the need for improvement in B5G systems. DAEMON leverages NI coordination and

advanced AI design tools to target a remarkable 0.9 precision-recall AUC. This should translate to at least 85% accuracy in both precision and recall within relevant scenarios, significantly advancing anomaly detection capabilities.

A summary of the activities targeting K7 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A9: Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection	Precision of 0.842, recall of 0.862, F1-Score of 0.852, accuracy of 0.816, and an AUC score of 0.913
A19: Anomaly detection for a roaming platform	Identification of anomalies that are currently missed by the alarm systems already in place in a production roaming platform for IoT managed connectivity, as validated with ground truth from the a-posteriori ticketing system
A25: Anomaly forecasting in mobile service traffic at base station level	Higher anomaly detection (in terms of F1 score, recall, false positive rate, and ROC curve) with respect to the state-of-the-art methods

3.1.8 KPI 8 (K8): Vertical service response time

DAEMON's backhaul-assisted computing and in-network support empowers third parties to reduce vertical service response times from minutes down to seconds. This revolutionary speed increase can be made possible by DAEMON's advanced NI functionalities.

A summary of the activities targeting K8 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A8: AI-enhanced MANO	10-14 s response time of the application, which is the delay for the whole request and response process, up to service recovery
A11: AI-enhanced edge orchestration	<15ms supported by ml-based proactive relocation.
A12: WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management	99% improvement of the response time of an interference management application, acting in the application plane of future SD-WLANs
A13: Data-driven resource orchestration	Improved vertical response time (e.g., PLT of web content below 10ms) as shown in Figure 7 of D5.2 for the A13 PoC

3.1.9 KPI 9 (K9): Optimality gap of network management decisions

DAEMON leverages long-term anticipatory networking to optimize network resource and function allocation on an hourly basis. This approach can achieve near-optimal performance (99% accuracy) in key scenarios, ensuring these strategic decisions provide robust guidance for faster, real-time NI operations.

A summary of the activities targeting K9 is presented next.

Activity	Summary
A3: Application-aware radio scheduling	98% classification accuracy using a Random Forest classifier, in case the RLC buffer is either governed by droptail or in case L4S AQM is used
A13: Data-driven resource orchestration	Reduced distance from the optimum achieved by the MNO depending on the demand from the different clusters
A21: Virtual Machine reservation	Reduction of SLA violations within 0.5% of the optimum
A22: Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX	OPEX savings within 10% of the oracle optimal solution
A27: Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing	Near-optimal performance proven theoretically and shown experimentally
A14: Multi-timescale network slice reservation	Near-optimal performance proven theoretically and shown experimentally

3.1.10 Evaluations and associated activities

The DAEMON project sets forth 7 evaluations that together allow demonstrating the performance reported in Table 1 and Sections 3.1.1-3.1.9 above. The details of the evaluations, including their context, objectives, employed testbeds and datasets can be found in D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [1] of the project; in particular, Section 1 of D5.2 [1] presents the latest version of the evaluations upon several modifications to the same that turned out to be necessary during the second year of execution of the project. Specifically, the DAEMON partners had agreed to integrate one additional evaluation (E8) that focused on NI solutions for in-backhaul learning, and to group the activities for two evaluations that were both related to anomaly detection (E3 and E5), reporting joint progress for those two activities.

During the last year of execution and the additional three-month extension of the action, the set of evaluations was finally frozen, and no further modifications were introduced.

Below, we simply list the different evaluations, and link them to the activities reported in Table 1. The four new evaluation activities that were initiated during year three of DAEMON are highlighted in bold.

Evaluation	Short description of the evaluation	Related activities
E1	NI for sustainable virtualized Radio Access Networks	A1, A2, A3, A29, A34
E2	NI for VNF placement and control	A4, A5, A6, A7, A8, A30, A33
E3+E5	NI for real-time anomaly detection	A9, A19, A25,
E4	NI for Edge orchestration	A10, A11, A12, A13, A14, A15, A16, A17, A26
E6	NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning	A20, A21, A22, A27, A31, A32
E7	NI to configure a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	A23
E8	NI for in-backhaul learning	A18, A28

In the following Sections 3.2-3.8, we present the individual evaluations, the Technology Readiness Levels they achieved, their association with the DAEMON KPIs, the experimental testbeds or datasets that they employ, their main findings. For each evaluation, we detail the associated activities, including any changes with respect to what reported in D5.2 [1] of the project.

3.2 Evaluation of NI for sustainable virtualised RANs

In this section, we discuss the conclusive evaluations concerning sustainable RAN solutions. Specifically, we discuss Evaluation E1, which discusses NI solutions designed for improving the NI for sustainable virtualized Radio Access Network (RAN). This evaluation encompasses 6 activities, as shown in Table 2, which summaries of the tools, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), Proof of Concept (PoC) execution, estimated progress, and primary innovative findings.

Table 2. Evaluation results for E1. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project. New activities are indicated as such.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	TRL	Testbed / Data	Main findings
A1	Reliable RAN virtualization	K1, K2, K4, K5	4	T1	Technology demonstrated in public events, as reported in D5.2
A2	AI-driven O-Cloud	K2, K4	4	T1	Technology demonstrated in public events, as reported in Section 5
A3	Application aware radio scheduling	K9	3	Data obtained via experiments on emulator S2	ML techniques (e.g., LSTM) can hardly improve over traditional ML techniques (e.g., random forest) that achieve accuracy levels above 95%
A29	ML radio resource scheduling for vRANs	K2, K4, K5	4	T1	Besides the optimization of the VNF, this solution contributes to validate the explainability of the system as integrated in the NIO
A34 (new)	FEC decoding on Quantum Annealers	K4	3	T17	The reliability of vRAN operation on Quantum computing systems cannot cope with the current carrier-grade requirements

3.2.1 Reliable DU virtualization (A1)

3.2.1.1 Evaluation

The complete empirical evaluation of this solution was presented in D5.2 [1], Section 4.1.1.

3.2.1.2 Summary KPIs

This activity was completed during Y2 and, correspondingly, the KPIs below have been validated in D5.2 [1].

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	29-50% savings per server	See D5.2, Section 4.1.1
K2	29-50% savings per server	See D5.2, Section 4.1.1
K4	29-50% savings per server	See D5.2, Section 4.1.1
K5	99.999% reliability achieved	See D5.2, Section 4.1.1

3.2.1.3 Requirements satisfaction

The empirical results presented in D5.2 [1], Section 4.1.1, allows us next to validate the following set of requirements described in D2.3 [4].

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-CAWRS-001	100%	The empirical results presented in D5.2 demonstrate a fully functional solution, whose E-HARQ predictive model meets the inference time requirement of 500 us
NFR-CAWRS-002	100%	This requirement has been achieved, as demonstrated in D5.2, Section 4.1.1.4
NFR-CAWRS-003	100%	This requirement has been achieved, as demonstrated in D5.2, Section 4.1.1.3

3.2.2 AI-driven O-Cloud (A2)

In the following, we provide an experimental prototype and a comprehensive empirical evaluation of CloudRIC, whose design was presented in D3.3, Section 3.3.[5].

3.2.2.1 Prototype implementation

Figure 9 illustrates our CloudRIC implementation in a multi-DU server, on top of the O-RAN AAL introduced in D5.2, Section 4.1.2.3 with heterogeneous GPU and SIMD-capable 16-core CPU processors. RUs and UEs are simulated following the bursty demand profiles presented in D5.2, Section 4.1.2.1, which generates realistic workload fluctuations that induce varied levels of stress on our O-Cloud platform. To this end, we encode, modulate, add noise and demodulate signals locally.

Figure 9. CloudRIC-powered O-Cloud prototype.

Figure 10. Overhead of RT-RIC & AAL-B models.

Figure 11. Prediction error of LPU models in AAL-B.

3.2.2.1.1 User Plane: AAL Broker

Our implementation of CloudRIC's AAL-B-UP (~2K lines of C++) follows the design in D3.3, Section 3.3 and builds on top of the O-RAN AAL we developed in D5.2, Section 4.1.2.3. We use the DPDK Environment Abstraction Layer (EAL) to abstract the complexity of thread and memory management via DPDK's efficient APIs. Our prototype runs over four threads. The 1st thread runs the AAL-B-UP, as well as its interfaces with the AAL-B-CP and the DUs using shared memory to reduce latency overhead. Upon each TB arrival, the AAL-B-UP routes its data into a pre-assigned LPU queue, based on decisions of the AAL-B-CP. The 2nd and 3rd threads handle the CPU and GPU LPUs, respectively: they (i) gather bursts of TBs from the associated LPU queue; (ii) enqueue bursts in the LPU; (iii) execute the corresponding driver or library; and (iv) enqueue the decoded bits into an output queue. The last thread handles performance metrics.

Validation. To validate our implementation, we use all the profiles presented in D5.2, Section 4.1.2.1 with a random LPU allocation, and measure the latency overhead introduced by our AAL-B-UP operations. Figure 10 (blue line) shows the distribution of the overheads, with a median latency of 2 μ s and a 99th percentile of 46 μ s, which is negligible compared to the 1-3 ms time budget available for the LPU processing of each TB.

3.2.2.1.2 Control Plane: AAL-B-CP and RT-RIC

The AAL-B-CP and the RT-RIC are implemented in C++ (~1.5K lines) using DPDK for efficient inter-process communication, and ONNX Runtime (ORT) for neural network acceleration. The AAL-B-CP uses four threads implementing, respectively, the main pipeline of CloudRIC, shown in D3.3, Section 3.3, the management of queue state updates received from the AAL, the queue time estimator logic, and the LPU models. The RT-RIC uses a single thread to implement the radio policy agent.

For every TB i , the radio policy selects an action $r^{(i)} \in \{0,0.1, \dots, 0.9,1.0\}$. Both actor and critic are neural networks with (5x140, 140x140, 140x11) and (16x140, 140x140, 140x11) layers, respectively, that are jointly trained using eq. as reward, parameterized with $\delta = 10\%$ of the deadline D and $\beta = 10$, which proved to work well in all experimental scenarios considered in the study. For the target soft Q-function of the critic, we set a discount factor equal to 0.99.

The LPU models' neural networks are composed of three dense layers (3x128, 128x128, 128x1). The WCET loss in eq. is parametrized with $\lambda = 10$. To illustrate the advantage of training the latency model v_n with our WCET approach, we used the dataset presented in D5.2, Section 3.3.1.3 to show the distribution of the model's relative errors $\epsilon_n^{(i)}$ with solid lines in Figure 11. As a benchmark, we also plot with dashed lines the relative error of an identical neural network trained to minimize the standard mean absolute error (MAE). What is relevant to CloudRIC operations is the fraction of overly optimistic estimates ($\epsilon_n^{(i)} < 0$) that lead to overrating the O-Cloud capacity and to queuing TBs that will later violate their deadline. Only 1.5% of the errors are optimistic for our method in contrast to the 53% of a MAE loss. Note that percent errors are higher for GPU than CPU, because the GPU latencies $d_n^{(i)}$ are considerably smaller, hence harder to estimate: the absolute error in μ s is however comparable for the two processors.

Validation. The overhead of the RT-RIC, which runs the the radio policy agent, and the AAL-B-CP, which runs the LPU models, have latency constraints of around 200us, as explained in D3.3, Section 3.3. To assess that timing requirements are fulfilled by our implementation, we run CloudRIC for all the UE demand profiles again and measure the overhead introduced by both modules. The distribution of the resulting latencies is depicted in Figure 10. The RT-RIC's radio agent (green line) has a median and a 99th percentile latency of 5 μ s and 9 μ s, respectively. The LPU model neural networks incur instead into a median and a 99th percentile latency of 42 μ s and 62 μ s, respectively (red line). Both meet their budgets and validate CloudRIC's real-time operation.

3.2.2.2 Evaluation

We evaluated our prototype of CloudRIC with a thorough experimental campaign. First, we quantify the training overhead of CloudRIC. Next, we validate that CloudRIC meets the design goals in terms of reliability, throughput, and energy savings. Lastly, we juxtapose CloudRIC against several benchmarks, scrutinizing aspects of reliability, energy- and cost-efficiency.

3.2.2.2.1 Training time

CloudRIC hinges on data-driven approaches to realize the LPU models and radio policy agent. The LPU models are stateless and can be pre-trained, e.g., using the dataset introduced in D5.2, Section 3.3, in our case. Instead, the radio agent is trained online upon deployment in the target system, and the training time it requires to learn effective radio policing decisions is an important metric.

Figure 12. CloudRIC’s mean (line) and max-min range (shaded area) reward for different training sets.

To analyze its training cost, we initialize RT-RIC’s radio agent with random weights and study the evolution of its performance as it learns to schedule the traffic of 150 UEs distributed among thirty 100-MHz DUs. Figure 12 presents the mean normalized reward achieved by CloudRIC after it has observed an increasing number of TBs across three processing deadlines $D=\{1,2,3\}$ ms commonly used in the literature. We present results for UEs with the “x4”, “x32”, and “Max” profiles introduced in D5.2, Section 3.3 as “5G”, “5Gx8” and “5Gx64”, respectively, to assess low, medium, and high workloads.

CloudRIC reaches maximum reward almost instantaneously for small workloads (“x4”): the radio agent readily learns that it does not need to constrain the allocation of radio resources to guarantee deadlines in this case. With more demanding “x32” and “Max” users, CloudRIC takes up to 50K TBs to converge, and achieves 90% of that reward with 10 times less TBs. It shall be noted that 50K TBs correspond to less than 4 s in real-time with “x32” users, which demonstrates that the radio agent can learn good policies with minimal service degradation upon deployment.

3.2.2.2.2 CloudRIC validation

CloudRIC has three goals, prioritized as: (i) achieving 5-nines reliability, (ii) maximizing throughput, and (iii) minimizing energy use, which we evaluate next.

Reliability and throughput. The compliance with the processing deadline during the inference phase directly controls the reliability of CloudRIC. We now better substantiate the dependability of our solution for real-time operation after the (very quick, as shown above) online training phase.

Figure 13. Processing latency distribution for different deadlines $D=\{1, 2, 3\}$ ms (shaded area).

Figure 13 shows the empirical distribution of the processing latency for all scenarios considered in the previous subsection. The shaded areas highlight deadline violations: by bounding all distributions to the left of those regions, CloudRIC meets the reliability target in all cases.

To achieve this, with growing loads and (to a minor extent) with more stringent deadlines, CloudRIC increases the average use of both CPU and HA as shown Figure 14 (top). However, when LPUs are under pressure, CloudRIC must bound the allocation of radio resources as depicted in Figure 14 (middle). That is, in response to workloads that increasingly exceed the O-Cloud’s capacity, the radio policy agent throttles down a progressively higher fraction of radio resources that otherwise would be

wasted. Despite this, CloudRIC attains on average 98.7% of the achievable network throughput (i.e., that of an offline exhaustive search with perfect knowledge of the future), which validates the second design goal.

It is worth noting that the results in Figure 14 above are averages, while the UE traffic at the ms timescale is inherently bursty. Therefore, CloudRIC must manage sudden upswings of requests (which saturate the LPUs and force radio grant limiting) alternating to low-demand periods (where all grants can be accommodated but resource utilization remains low). This explains why LPU usage inflation is fairly linear in the face of exponentially surging demands of “x1” through “Max” Ues, and why 100% radio allocations are not feasible even when the LPUs are not fully used, with “x8” through “x128” Ues.

Figure 14. Mean resource utilization (top), radio allocation (middle), and workload allocation (bottom) for different deadlines $D=\{1,2,3\}$ ms and demand profiles.

Energy Savings. Having assessed CloudRIC’s reliability and throughput, we focus on the last design goal, i.e., exploiting computing heterogeneity to improve energy efficiency. To that end, CloudRIC’s LPU allocation function, informed by HA-specific LPU models, prioritizes energy-prudent processors as long as they allow meeting processing deadlines. This yields a flexible load balancing, as shown in Figure 14 (bottom): for instance, 100% of the workload is assigned to the CPU pool to save energy in the case of “x1” UEs, but around 40% is allotted to the HA to protect reliability in higher-loaded scenarios with “x32” through “Max” UEs.

Figure 15. Energy savings of CloudRIC when using a CPU pool relative to only using the HA.

The ability of CloudRIC to exploit CPUs opportunistically provides substantial gains in energy consumption. Figure 15 shows the energy cost savings achieved by CloudRIC with respect to the cost of exclusively relying upon the HA, i.e., the industry-standard approach. The results refer to CPU pools of varied size, under all UE profiles and for $D = 3$, and validate the last design goal of CloudRIC. Remarkably, CloudRIC provides over 50% energy cost savings with just a single CPU core in presence of low-load “x1” UEs. Increasing the CPU pool size provides more savings, but with diminishing returns as many cores remain unused. For higher workloads, the energy cost savings are understandably lower as the LPU allocation function prioritizes network throughput and reliability over energy consumption. For instance, a single-core CPU pool provides practically no gain for the case of “Max” users, but a 16-core pool attains 37% savings for the same Scenario.

3.2.2.3 Comparison with other approaches

CloudRIC improves reliability and sustainability of vRANs over both best practices that the operators currently adopt in their deployments, as well as advanced benchmarks that only partially implement our design guidelines. We demonstrate this by juxtaposing CloudRIC to the following baselines.

"Industry-std" uses a dedicated *in-line* HA co-located with every DU, which is *the conventional approach in the industry today*. To test this approach fairly, we simulate as many in-line HAs as DUs, each with the same performance of our NVIDIA V100 GPU, using the dataset presented in D5.2, Section 3.3, and ignoring the look-aside overhead shown in Figure 10 (blue line).

The other benchmarks are the policies introduced in D5.2, Section 3.3, "O-Greedy", "O-MWT", "C-MWT", and "C-DA", which we implement in our AAL platform, like CloudRIC, sharing the HA and the CPU pool. In D5.2, several of these approaches relied on future knowledge, which is not feasible for real-time operation. To enable real-time operation, we use LPU models trained with a MAE loss to predict the information they require. Note that CloudRIC implements the "C-R-DA" policy in D5.2.

Figure 16. Reliability (top), energy-efficiency (middle), and cost-efficiency (bottom) for different policies on different scenarios with "x4" (left) and "Max" (right) users.

We run comparative experiments with a varying number of 100-MHz DUs aggregating 50 to 350 UEs in a single server. Figure 16 depicts reliability (top, expressed as the percentage of TBs processed within D), energy efficiency (middle, calculated as the amount of data bits processed successfully per unit of energy), and cost efficiency (bottom, measured as the mean network throughput achieved per unit of capital investment¹). Results are for $D = \{1,2,3\}$ ms and a variable number of "x4" (left) and "Max" (right) UEs, hence DUs. The first key remark is that only CloudRIC and "Industry-std" provide high reliability across all scenarios. The "Industry-std" is the only benchmark to achieve the same 5-nine reliability of CloudRIC.

However, "Industry-std" matches the dependability of CloudRIC by largely over-dimensioning the computing capacity, which yields the worst cost-efficiency performance. Figure 16 demonstrates how CloudRIC makes the best use of a much smaller, shared, and heterogeneous O-Cloud to achieve 15x higher cost efficiency and 3x higher energy efficiency, on average, than the legacy industry practice.

The capital cost of all the other benchmarks is the same as CloudRIC's so its cost-efficiency gains are solely due to network throughput gains. Because "C-DA" uses CloudRIC's AAL-B, it achieves similar performance to CloudRIC for small workloads; however, the absence of the RT-RIC causes "C-DA" to waste radio and computing resources on TBs that miss their deadlines during heavier workloads, which results in 34% and 31% lower energy efficiency and network throughput, respectively. "O-Greedy", "O-MWT", and "C-MWT" all confirm the poor reliability of these approaches on a real-world platform, with throughput dropping to 0% for "Max" UEs.

¹ To calculate cost efficiency, we used market values, i.e., \$110 per CPU core, and \$3,000 per HA.

3.2.2.3 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allows to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	3x energy-efficiency gains in average	As shown in Section 3.2.2.2.3, CloudRIC attains 3x energy-efficiency gains in average, across a vast number of scenarios, with respect to the industry-standard approach
K2	$(N-1)*100\%$ savings, where N is the number of DUs	The solution provided here allows, for the first time, share computing servers among multiple DUs, which allows using 1 server every N DUs, instead of N servers every N DUs
K4	15x cost efficiency gains in average	As shown in Section 3.2.2.2.3, CloudRIC attains 15x cost-efficiency gains in average, across a vast number of scenarios, with respect to the industry-standard approach
K5	99.999% reliability achieved	As shown in Section 3.2.2.2.2, CloudRIC attains 99.999% reliability regardless the Scenario evaluated.

3.2.2.4 Requirements satisfaction

The empirical results presented above moreover allow us next to validate the following set of requirements described in D2.3. [4].

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-CAWRS-001	100%	The empirical results presented in Section 3.2.2.2.2 demonstrate a fully functional CloudRIC solution, whose machine learning models meets the inference time requirement well below 200 us
NFR-CAWRS-002	100%	The empirical results presented in Section 3.2.2.2.2 demonstrate that our solution maximizes throughput while respecting the reliability target, given any computing capacity constraint

3.2.3 Application aware radio scheduling (A3)

3.2.3.1 Evaluation

In Section 4.3 of deliverable D3.1 [6] we discussed three methods to classify traffic based on the evolution of the RLC (radio link control) buffer: a threshold-based method (TB), a method based on K-nearest neighbors (KNN) and a method based on a feed-forward neural network (FFNN). We reported more detailed results in Section 4.1.3 of D5.1 [7]. In Section 2.3 of deliverable D3.2 [8] we introduced a method based on long short-term memory (LSTM), also capturing the trends in the RLC buffer evolution. In Section 4.1.3 of deliverable D5.2 [1] we provided how all methods compared for a RLC buffer governed by TD (tail drop). In Section 3.4 of deliverable D3.3 [5] we considered a new data set in which the RLC buffer was governed by an AQM (active queue management). As explained in that deliverable using AQM could have an impact on the performance of the classifier as the AQM tries to keep the buffer occupancy small. In the present deliverable we summarize all results.

For each of the configurations considered below, we performed 20 runs: in each run, the split between the training set and the test set was randomly changed. This allows us to report the confidence interval for each of the metrics: i.e., performance is always expressed as the "average of the metric \pm the standard deviation of the metric" in the tables below).

In this final deliverable we also compare the results of the KNN, FFNN and LSTM with more traditional methods, i.e., RF (random forest classification) and SVC (state vector machine-based classification) Table 3. We first consider such classifiers with on the original raw signal as input. Since this possibly yields a large training and inference time we also calculate salient features on the raw samples and use these features as input to the classifier. We selected the best feature set based on how well the features correlate with the class labels.

We performed all experiments on a Linux machine with 24 Xeon CPUs @ 2.30GHz using the python library TensorFlow for FFNN and LSTM; and the python library sklearn for KNN, RF and SVC. We exploited parallel computation as much as possible.

Table 3 and Table 4 presents the results on the TD and AQM data set respectively when the raw traces are presented as input to the classifiers.

Table 3. Classification results on the TD data set with as input the raw traces.

Method	Optimal configuration	Probability correct classification	Training time [s]	Inference time [ms]
KNN	2 neighbors	0.806 ± 0.004	15 ± 3	13 ± 3
RF	200 estimators	0.941 ± 0.002	19.9 ± 0.4	0.138 ± 0.0003
SVC	radial basis function kernel	0.732 ± 0.002	1081 ± 4	39.1 ± 0.1
FFNN	5 hidden layers, 100 cells per layer	0.920 ± 0.005	229 ± 32	0.121 ± 0.009
LSTM	100 input features, 125 output features	0.953 ± 0.004	1732 ± 220	0.34 ± 0.05

Table 4. Classification results on the AQM data set with as input the raw traces.

Method	Optimal configuration	Probability correct classification	Training time [s]	Inference time [ms]
KNN	1 neighbor	0.085 ± 0.002	16.2 ± 0.5	4.7 ± 0.2
RF	200 estimators	0.945 ± 0.001	49 ± 2	0.0175 ± 0.001
SVC	radial basis function kernel	0.726 ± 0.001	7565 ± 1779	153 ± 20
FFNN	3 hidden layers, 100 cells per layer	0.905 ± 0.005	342 ± 57	0.182 ± 0.07
LSTM	100 input features, 125 output features	0.978 ± 0.004	2650 ± 727	0.35 ± 0.05

Figure 17. Mutual information between various feature sets and the class for the TD data set. (a) statistics-based features, (b) FFT based features, (c) PCA based features and (d) auto-encoder features. The red dashed line is the entropy in the class and represents the maximum value that the mutual information can have.

It is common practice to reduce the dimensionality of the input by calculating a set of representing features. Various kinds of features can be used. We considered statistics-based features (average, standard deviation, span, autocorrelation coefficients), FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) based features, PCA (Principal Component Analysis) based features and an auto-encoder. For each type of feature set we assess the mutual information between the features and the class (calculated with the sklearn subroutine).

Figure 17 shows that the statistics-based features have the largest mutual information. The same conclusion applies for the AQM data set. Below we use the statistics-based features. It takes (0.234 ± 0.01) s to calculate those features for one raw sample with 2000 entries.

Table 5 and Table 6 presents the results on the TD and AQM data set respectively when the statistics features are presented as input to the classifiers. Remark that the LSTM classifier does not work on features, because it relies on the time evolution in the trace. All classifiers have much shorter training and inference times than when the raw traces are used as input. Surprisingly the classifiers experience an increase in probability of correct classification as well.

Table 5: Classification results on the TD data set with as input a selected set of features.

Method	Optimal configuration	Probability correct classification	Training time	Inference time
KNN	3 neighbors	0.978 ± 0.001	0.0385 ± 0.0008	0.0057 ± 0.0001
RF	150 estimators	0.987 ± 0.001	0.72 ± 0.02	0.00181 ± 0.00004
SVC	radial basis function kernel	0.909 ± 0.002	7.2 ± 0.2	0.220 ± 0.003
FFNN	2 hidden layers, 80 cells per layer	0.938 ± 0.006	123 ± 27	0.041 ± 0.003

Table 6: Classification results on the AQM data set with as input a selected set of features.

Method	Optimal configuration	Probability correct classification	Training time [s]	Inference time [ms]
KNN	1 neighbor	0.987 ± 0.001	0.067 ± 0.002	0.004 ± 0.001
RF	150 estimators	0.992 ± 0.001	1.06 ± 0.03	0.00146 ± 0.00002
SVC	radial basis function kernel	0.923 ± 0.002	35.7 ± 0.6	0.5556 ± 0.004
FFNN	4 hidden layers, 80 cells per layer	0.959 ± 0.004	163 ± 37	0.042 ± 0.002

The conclusion is that classification of traffic based on its RLC buffer fingerprint can be done with an accuracy of 98% to 99%. The LSTM classifier operating on the raw trace achieves this performs, as well as a RF classifier operating on statistical features.

3.2.3.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following KPI.

KPI	Result	Justification
K9	<2%	The accuracy of the best classification algorithms studied in DAEMON is close to 99%, yielding an optimality gap of less than 1%. (see Section 3.2.3 of the present deliverable)

3.2.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

The results presented above moreover allow us next to validate the following requirement described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-CAWSR-001	100%	The inference associated to best traffic classification was shown to be way below 1ms, which leaves ample headroom to reconfigure the resource block allocation and schedulers

3.2.4 ML radio resource scheduling for virtualized RANs (A29)

3.2.4.1 Evaluation

This section completes the empirical evaluation of this solution which was presented in D5.2 [1], Section 4.1.4, where the solution is compared against a Baseline implementation of srsRAN. We ran our experiments using TTI of 1 ms and 10 MHz of bandwidth, which gives 50 PRBs in the uplink out of which the $N = 45$ are only available for uplink data transmission. We have also disabled HARQ retransmissions in order to compare the success of our solution during the first transmission of the frame, i.e., using a single redundancy version. We adjust the channel gain G of the UE so that the perceived SNR per PRB at the gNB side varies between 5 dB and 30 dB.

Figure 18. Throughput served by a gNB running ATHENA, ATHENA-MCS and Baseline algorithm, for different congestions β and SNR between [5, 30] dB.

In Figure 18, we plot in solid lines the average throughput (in Mbps) achieved by ATHENA, ATHENA-MCS and Baseline at each SNR level. A TB is considered successfully decoded when T_{dec} is below 3 ms and has a successful CRC check. When $\beta = 0$, where either controller suffers losses from deadline violations, Baseline substantially underperforms both ATHENA and ATHENA-MCS, in terms of average throughput. ATHENA records an improvement of 3.94 Mbps with a maximum improvement of 7.45 Mbps at 13 dB. This originates from the conservative nature of traditional controllers where they stick to simulation-based min-MCS approaches to pre-serve the decodability of the frames, while the data-driven approaches can discover optimal control policies (e.g., at high SNR ATHENA picks MCS 24, while Baseline goes up to 23). We observe similar behavior in higher $\beta = .5$, where the congestion factor has an important impact on the decoding time. Baseline's throughput drops due to low reliability, as we depict in Figure 19, where it counts the percentage of the frames where either CRC = 0 or $T_{dec} \geq 3$. The maximum achievable throughput for both versions of ATHENA drops to 11.5 Mbps with very high-reliability levels.

Figure 19. Reliability by a gNB running ATHENA, ATHENA-MCS and Baseline algorithm, for different congestions β and SNR between [5, 30] dB.

When $\beta = 1$, Baseline's reliability essentially drops to 0, along with the average throughput. For ATHENA, the SNR has minimum impact, because the high congestion forces the agent to apply a single control policy for all the channel conditions. In Figure 20, we compare the T_{dec} yielded by the two approaches. While in $\beta = 0$, all T_{dec} are below 3 ms, we observe that variability is much higher in ATHENA, which is explained by higher MCS selection. Again, with higher β , a non-negligible part of the frames misses the deadline. ATHENA, instead, lowers down either the MCS or the PRB to always meet it. As a result, it obtains a flatter T_{dec} distribution, which is a direct consequence of the selected actions, as we discuss next.

Figure 20. The T_{dec} distribution and the selected MCS, for ATHENA and Baseline algorithm, with different congestion β .

We now compare the two alternate versions of ATHENA and ATHENA-MCS. In Figure 21, we plot the PRB, and MCS decisions of the two versions for different SNR levels and three congestion factors. While ATHENA-MCS always transmits at full bandwidth, ATHENA explores different alternatives in the 2D action space. As we observe in Figure 18, both versions manage to achieve optimal levels of reliability and equal performance, with ATHENA slightly overseeding by 500 Kbps in medium congestion factors,

transmitting at lower PRBs and increasing the MCS. The major advantage by ATHENA over ATHENA-MCS is the up to 44% spectral efficiency improvement (in terms of PRB utilization) since it can achieve the equal or slightly better performance using less bandwidth leaving available space for other users to be scheduled. We plan to incorporate multi-user scheduling at the same TTI in a future flavor of ATHENA, that jointly selects users and decides MCS and PRB, so that we take advantage of the unused PRBs to increase the total throughput of the system, respecting the time budget as well as technology requirements and user characteristics. We note that both the original ATHENA algorithm and ATHENA-MCS are both based on the same original architecture and should be considered variants and not alternative solutions.

Figure 21. MCS and PRB decisions of the two versions ATHENA and ATHENA-MCS.

We resort to DT in order to evaluate the performance of our solution in a multi-user setting. We consider 3 users within the UL with increasing mean SNR and standard deviation of 3 dB. In each TTI, a user is selected in a round-robin fashion. Given the user’s channel conditions and congestion factor, the pretrained ATHENA agent provides the control decision. Subsequently, the DT is inferred outputting the expected decoding time and the decoding success probability. The UL frame is considered decoded if the predicted decoding time is less than the deadline and the sampled success probability process is 1.

To capture the capability of ATHENA to adapt to different UL traffic shapes, we modify the load as we depict in the first row of Figure 22 in a period of 1300 seconds. This load reflects the demanded bits to be transferred at the UE’s MAC level and is conveyed in the BSR message to the base station. Accordingly, in the following three rows, we show how the throughput is modified for each user. We see that the throughput, achieved by ATHENA, follows the pattern of the traffic load which incurs due to MCS degradations, as we described in Sec. V-B5, and are shown in the shaded gray area.

Figure 22. Throughput for different congestion factor β and user load.

In Figure 23, we repeat the same experiment but for full traffic load (100%). We depict with bars the mean throughput and with error lines the jitter of each user for variable β values. We observe that in low β and high SNR scenarios, ATHENA yields high jitter (due to the SNR fluctuations), which gets lower either when the SNR drops or the congestion goes up. For $\beta \geq .6$, the SNR is almost taken no account since the congestion impact overrules. In the same plot, we depict the cell utilization, defined as the total

throughput of the users divided by the throughput at $\beta = 0$, which denotes the maximum achievable throughput for these channel conditions. We observe a gradual drop of cell utilization in low congestion factors, reaching 60% in medium β , before falling to below 40% in high β , showcasing its impact in the model's predictions.

Figure 23. Throughput for different congestion factor β and cell utilization.

3.2.4.2 Summary KPIs

This activity was completed at the beginning of Y· and, correspondingly, the KPIs below have been validated in D5.2 [1] and in this document.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	From 10 to 90% saving depending on the capacity and the congestion level	Explained above, as in Figure 18 and Figure 19
K2	From 10 to 90% saving depending on the capacity and the congestion level	Explained above, as in Figure 18 and Figure 19
K4	From 10 to 90% saving depending on the capacity and the congestion level	Explained above, as in Figure 18 and Figure 19
K5	99.999% reliability achieved	Explained above, Figure 19

3.2.4.3 Requirements satisfaction

The empirical results presented in D5.2, Section 4.1.4, and in this document are used to meet the requirements discussed in D2.3. [4].

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-CAWRS-001	100%	The solution has been evaluated in the testbed T1, providing empirical results presented and hence it is fully functional. The ML based scheduling decisions allow the operation of a state-of-the-art vRAN implementation based on srsRAN
NFR-CAWRS-002	100%	By achieving very high reliability, this solution optimizes the spectral efficiency according to the available computing capacity

3.2.5 FEC decoding on Quantum Annealers (A34)

In the following, we describe a new activated initiated during Y3, where DAEMON explores the opportunities of quantum computing to solve DAEMON-related problems.

3.2.5.1 Evaluation

As discussed in the WP3 deliverable series for the activities A1, A2, and A29, large savings in terms of resource utilization could be achieved by properly designed NI algorithms, as we demonstrated above. While for the aforementioned activities the used computing platform is a traditional x86 system, in this activity we studied the capabilities of novel computing platforms such as quantum computers in a virtual RAN setting.

The motivation is shared with A1, A2, and A29. FEC decoding represents a significant share of the computational effort for a vRAN system, thus a disruptive technology could be built using quantum computing. In particular, in this activity we focus on Quantum Annealers (QA). QAs, which are now commercially available, are specialized analog computers designed to tackle NP-complete and NP-hard optimization problems. They operate differently from traditional computers by using qubits that can represent a continuum of values, allowing for potential speedups over conventional computing

methods. Users can input constraints and preferences for qubit behavior, which the QA uses to solve optimization problems, typically represented as quadratic polynomials of binary variables. Each run of the machine involves multiple quantum annealing trials, each potentially yielding a different solution based on the user-defined constraints.

A seminal work that analyzes the issue is the one in [9], where the authors leverage DWave's Quantum Annealer (specifically, a D-Wave 2000-qubit (DW2Q) quantum adiabatic optimizer machine), to implement an Low-Density Parity Check (LDPC) Forward Error Correction (FEC) Decoder, which is a fundamental part of a quantum-enabled vRAN base station. However, their work focused in rather simple LDPC codes (2-3 regular codes) which are far from the ones used in real 5G base station. Thus, their work motivates our in pursuing this path, as they proved its initial feasibility, but introduces a number of challenges that we need to solve in order to obtain a viable solution to the problem.

For the sake of space, we refer the reader to [9] or a primer on LDPC FEC decoding and its implementation in Quantum annealers. In a nutshell, LDPC decoding is an iterative process that fulfills these steps:

1. The decoder receives log-likelihood ratio (LLR) vectors from the demodulator, representing the likelihood of each bit in a transmission (or codeword) being 1 or 0.
2. The decoder Improves the beliefs inherent into the LLRs using a belief propagation algorithm that performs operations involving check or parity bits.
3. Upon a stopping criteria, the decoder computes the data bits according to the resulting LLR values.

The process is repeated from step 2 until all the parity constraints are met or when a maximum number of iterations is reached.

When applied to the quantum setting, in particular to a QA from D-Wave, the formulation involves the class of Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) problems, whose generalized form is:

$$E = \sum_i h_i q_i + \sum_{i < j} J_{ij} q_i q_j \text{ where variables } q_i \in \{0,1\}$$

where h_i and J_{ij} are the linear and quadratic coefficients of the problem, and q_i are the variables. To solve an optimization problem using the QA, the first step is to formulate it in linear and quadratic terms, define objective and constraints, build a Binary Quadratic model (BQM), send the optimization model to the D-Wave solver, and finally post-process and interpret the result.

BQM model building. Following the work in [9], we built the BQM corresponding to an LDPC decoder by splitting the QUBO into two main parts:

1. The *LDPC satisfier function* is designed to ensure that all the *valid* LDPC codewords correspond to zero-energy states in the quantum system, effectively differentiating valid codewords from invalid ones. This function leverages the energy minimization nature of quantum annealing to identify valid codewords.
2. The *Distance function* identifies the correct codeword among all valid ones. It assigns lower energy to the codeword closer to the received noisy message, thus enabling the quantum annealer to favor the correct codeword as the system's energy minimizes. This function uses the Hamming distance, adapted for the quantum context, to evaluate the closeness of potential codewords to the received message.

The above yields the following QUBO formulation:

$$\min_{q_i} \{W_1 \sum_{c_i \in V} L_{sat}(c_i) + W_2 \sum_{j=1}^N \Delta_j\}$$

where q_i represents each decoded bit, W_1 and W_2 are weighting parameters, V is the set of parity check constraints, $L_{sat}(c_i) := \text{XOR}(c_{ij} w_j)$, with w_j being the j^{th} received bit, Δ_j is the Euclidean distance between bit q_j and the probability of bit j being 1 given w_j .

This formulation is then submitted to the Solver, which performs the real quantum annealing process. The solver, using the anneal process, finds a set of candidate solutions that solve the problem among the ones that minimize the used energy. To test the performance of the QUBO formulation using 5G New Radio LDPC codes, we used a commercial quantum annealer from D-Wave, which we classify as Testbed T17 in DAEMON. Specifically, we used the D-Wave Advantage computer, with more than 5000 qubits and more than 35000 couplers, based on the Pegasus architecture as shown below.

Figure 24. The Pegasus Architecture (qubits and couplers) used by the Advantage Computer.

Pegasus addresses the limitations of the previous Chimera topology (used by the work in [9]) by improving qubit connectivity, which is fundamental for solving complex optimization problems more effectively. The new Pegasus design allows for a denser and more complex network, which enables embedding larger and more complex problem graphs directly onto the quantum processor. The improved connectivity facilitates the reduction of qubit chains (as discussed below), which in turn lowers errors yielding more accurate results.

Embedding creation. To solve the QUBO problem, there is an additional step to be performed: the original set of bits represented in the QUBO formulation has to be mapped onto the sets of physical qubits available in the quantum computer. This is needed because, while in the QUBO formulation all the used bits can be leveraged in an arbitrary number of constraints, this is limited when applied to the Quantum setting to the available number of connections in the quantum architecture. Thus, if two bits are part of the same constraint, they should have a connection between them. If a bit is used in n different constraints, it should have connections with all the bits available in the n constraints. If a direct connection is not possible, chains of qubits may be used.

Thus, the embedding process is a function that maps one bit in the original formulation to a set of physical qubits in the physical computer. The computer used in T17 performs this operation using a heuristic algorithm, MinorMiner [10], that solves the embedding task with the goal of minimizing the amount of qubits used.

Performance evaluation. We start the evaluation with a 3,7 regular code (a code that adds 4 parity bits every each 3 bits of data), generated with the PyLDPC library [11] We generate random codeblocks and measure the Block Error ratio in Figure 25.

Figure 25. BLER for a 3,7 LDPC code.

Figure 26. BLER for different 5G Codes.

We compare the traditional Belief Propagation (BP) method against the QA solution for a number of input codeblocks and different noise ratios. In Figure 25, we show that the performance of the quantum annealer is comparable with the traditional BP showing thus the potential of this approach for performing the decoding operation in a virtualized RAN system.

However, the code tested in Figure 25 is far from being a usable code in commercial and carrier grade system, due to its very low channel efficiency (more than 50% overhead). In the following, we compare the performance of the QA process with the BP using traditional computing approach for a number of 5G codes.

Figure 26 shows the block error ratio for different 5G-NR codes using two different modulations: BPSK and QPSK. From Figure 26, we can see that the performance obtained by the QA solution is far from ideal, and it suffers a consistent gap with respect to the performance achieved with the traditional BP solution. In particular, for the same code, we can observe that there is a gap of up to two orders of magnitude. Only when the signal-to-noise ratio is very high, the QA solution can perform on par with the traditional BP one.

We investigated the reason behind this effect, and we noticed that a key issue is the embedding process introduced above. That is, the heuristic embedding algorithm employed by the T17 QA by default yields solutions that have overly long chains of qubits. This is because the complexity of the 5G-NR codes we tested cause that the same bits in the source graph are part of several constraints, which hence need to be mapped to the same qubit. Given the limited number of connections available in our quantum computer, this leads to very long chains, which compromise performance.

This becomes evident by comparing the embedding shown in Figure 27, which corresponds to the simpler (2,3) code proposed in [9], and that of Figure 28, which corresponds to the embedding of a 5G new radio code we used before. It can be observed that the embedding yielded by the [9] code was way simpler. In [9], the embedding process has been performed manually in order to avoid the usage of very long chain length which was not possible to obtain with the heuristic we used.

Figure 27. Embedding of a 2,3 regular code. **Figure 28.** Embedding resulting from the code in [9].

We investigated this issue by testing different heuristic algorithms besides MinorMiner (MM), the default one used by D-Wave QAs. In particular, we used three different state-of-the-art heuristics available in the literature that build on top of MM. MM has as a pre-processing stage that finds an initial mapping for each logical qubit, allowing overlapping a vertex in target to map more than one in source. Then, it iteratively refines the solution by removing a vertex mapping and looking for a better solution for this vertex using a cost function that takes into account the qubit utilization. The embedding process is complete when no overlapping happens and when no improvements have been provided after a fixed number of tries.

Variants of this approach change the preprocessing step. Layout-Aware MM (LAMM) [12] is a variant that considers that the source graph has a repetitive layout pattern (e.g. clique, big clique, star, cubic, 2-3 D) and maps each source node to its closest target node in the 2D space. Then it performs diffusion and concentration strategies to find the final initial embedding solution. Clique-based MM (CLMM) [13] computes a k-clique embedding of the source graph and feeds these initial embeddings to MM. Spring-based MM (SPMM) [13] draws both source and target graphs to a 2D plane. The target graph is easily drawn on the 2D plane since it naturally has a structure. Source graph is drawn using a force directed graph drawing algorithm with spring layout. Finally, it maps each source node to the closest target in the node plane and feeds these initial mappings to MM.

Figure 29 showcases the performance of these algorithms under different LDPC codes sizes and a 5G-NR code.

Figure 29. Chain lengths for different codes and different heuristics.

Figure 30. BLER performance of different codes.

While for simpler codes LAMM can obtain in general shorter chain lengths, that changes when 5G NR codes are used. Due to their irregular pattern, the LAMM approach cannot outperform anymore the MinorMiner approach used by the D-Wave quantum computer. From the same figure, we can see that the MinorMiner objective of minimizing the usage of qubits is fulfilled in any case.

In the next Figure 30, we finally compare the Block Error ratio for the different codes we tested. In each case we compute 4 metrics: the average BLER, for all the solutions found by the Quantum Annealer, the Minimum BLER, which finds for each experiment the best (in term of BLER) solution coming from the annealer. Also, we pick the solution that yields the lowest energy among all the anneals.

Still, the performance for these families of codes is still far from being carrier grade. Even for the more complex 2-3 codes we tested above, the average block error ratio is almost always 100% for any signal to noise ratio levels, as shown in Figure 30. Only when we take the best possible solutions (Min BLER in Figure 30) the performance is comparable with the one obtained with a traditional BP approach. However, this solution is not directly applicable to a real system as the Min BLER benchmark relies on the perfect knowledge (i.e., the decoder knows the original data bits that must be decoded) something that is not applicable in a real system. This means that there is still a large avenue for improvement needed to be taken before reaching a usable system for the decoding of wireless frames using quantum computing approaches.

3.2.5.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allows to validate the following KPI.

KPI	Result	Justification
K5	Performance below the achieved by traditional computers	The BLER achieved by a QA under realistic scenario is higher than a traditional BP solution. Further analysis shall be performed in order to provide a carrier grade solution

3.2.5.3 Requirements satisfaction

The results presented above moreover allow us next to validate the following non-functional requirements described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-CAWRS-002	50%	Performance is bounded, but the bound is large and not carrier grade

3.3 Evaluation of NI for VNF placement and control

In this section, we discuss the final evaluations concerning NI for placement and routing of new network services. Specifically, we discuss Evaluation E2, which considers VNF placement under constrains of energy and computation power, and transport capacity. This activity encompasses A5-A8 and A30. Summaries of the KPIs, TRLs, used testbeds and dataset, and primary innovative findings from these activities are provided in Table 7 and expanded in the following subsections.

Table 7. Evaluation results for E2. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project. New activities are indicated as such.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	Reached TRL	Testbed / Dataset	Main findings
A4	AI-aided energy-driven RAN orchestration	K1, K4	3	T5	Up to 12.5% energy savings
A5	AI-aided RAN/edge orchestration	K1, K2	3	T5	30% of savings in GPU resources
A6	Energy-aware deployment of VNFs for generic Edge computing	K1	3	D10	Energy consumption reduction of GEC up to 90%
A7	Combining VNFs at the edge	K1, K2	3	T8	Energy consumption reduction between 54% and 59%.

A8	AI-Enhanced MANO	K3, K8	2	Randomly generated data	Response time of the AI algorithm of about 280 – 330ms in total (10 ms the AI part)
A30	Placement and routing for network services	K2, K4	3	Simulations via python code	30% computational saving 30% POEX saving
A33 (new)	Energy-prudent vRAN management with loss meta-learning	K1, K4	3	T5	30% reduction of energy required to power the required compute resources

3.3.1 AI-aided energy-driven RAN orchestration (A4)

A preliminary version of this NIF was empirically evaluated in D5.2, Section 4.2.1.

In this section, we present the results of the evaluation of an updated NIF designed, which integrates the BSvBS algorithm described in Section 3.3 of deliverable D4.3 [3]. We use real-world traffic traces and testbed measurements to demonstrate the efficacy of our online learning scheme, as well as to highlight the weaknesses of prior works.

3.3.1.1 Evaluation

Our evaluation of the BSvBS algorithm is conducted across multiple scenarios with our recent dataset, which includes measurements of the power consumption and performance of vBS policies. This setup is subject to random fluctuations due to changes in UL and DL demand $\{d_t^u, d_t^d\}$, and variations in Channel Quality Indicators (CQIs), $\{c_t^u, c_t^d\}$. The dataset contains $|X| = 1080$ configurations (policies), but we use a subset of them because calculating the best configuration in hindsight is computationally challenging when $|X|$ is large. For the power cost function, we set $P_t(x_t) = V_t$, where V_t is the total power consumed by the vBS, and $\delta = 1$ to emphasize reducing power usage.

We assume that the traffic loads discerned in our system are sampled, either from $d_t^d \sim U(29,32)$, $d_t^u \sim U(20,23)$ (high DL and UL demands, respectively, where U is the uniform distribution), or from $d_t^u, d_t^d \sim U(0.01,1)$ (low DL and UL demands, respectively). Similarly, the channel qualities are drawn, either from $c_t^u, c_t^d \sim U(13,15)$ (good channel qualities in DL and UL, respectively), or from $c_t^u, c_t^d \sim U(1,3)$ (poor channel qualities in DL and UL, respectively). Thus, we have the following two scenarios: (i) Scenario A, where the demands and CQIs are consistently drawn uniformly at random from the high distribution (stationary) and aligns with the experiments in recent studies, and (ii) Scenario B, where the demands and CQIs are drawn randomly from the high distribution in odd slots and from the low distribution in even slots; this ping-pong strategy corresponds to the most challenging-to-learn adversarial scenario in regret analysis.

In Figure 31 (a) we run the algorithm for 20 independent runs and present the expected regret in the stationary and adversarial cases for $T = 50k$ slots. During the first 12k slots, the regret for Scenario A is higher than Scenario B by 7.5% in slot 1k; however, as time evolves and confidence in the performance of configurations is built, it is reasonable to observe the regret of the stationary case (Scenario A) to be lower than the more volatile system of Scenario B. In this way, for slot 50k, the regret for the adversarial case is 12.7% greater than the stationary's Scenario for the same slot. Figure 31 (b), we showcase the experienced regret and its upper bound. More precisely, we notice that the regret of BSvBS is 80.9% and 78.1% lower w.r.t the upper bound, for Scenario A and B, respectively.

Figure 31. BSvBS regret in Scenarios A and B for $|X| = 256$.

Figure 32. BSvBS power consumption in Scenario B for $|X| = 256$.

Figure 32 depicts the effect of δ in the consumed power. We define a hyper-slot of 200-slots-length to facilitate the presentation of results and consider the (i) total power consumption and ii) the BBU/CPU power consumption. By running the experiments for 100k slots, we observe that as δ increases, priority is given to the minimization of the power instead of the maximization of the utility. Thus, for the hyper-slot 500, we manage to save 6.8 % and 9.4 % in the total and CPU power consumption, respectively, by using $\delta = 100$ instead of a small δ .

3.3.1.2 Summary of KPIs

The following table shows the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results presented above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	100%	As shown in the experiments above, BSvBS can achieve around 10% energy savings by tuning the parameter δ accordingly, as explained in Section 3.3.1.1. Additional results have been provided in D5.2, Section 4.2.1
K4	100%	From Section 3.3.1.1, the proposed solution is able to reduce the energy spent by the operator, which leads to reduced OPEX. Additional results have been provided in D5.2, Section 4.2.1

3.3.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

The following table shows the set of requirements we have successfully validated with the results above.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-EAWVNF-004	100%	The BSvBS algorithm aims at balancing network throughput and energy consumption in vRANs
NFR-EAWVNF-004	100%	A data-driven approach based on Bayesian Learning was designed to control different configuration parameters of virtualized base stations to balance throughput and power consumption, as per D5.2, Section 4.2.1
NFR-EAWVNF-005	100%	A data-driven approach based on Bayesian Learning was designed to control different configuration parameters of virtualized base stations to maximize network throughput given hard power consumption constraints. Details in D5.2, Section 4.2.1

3.3.2 AI-aided RAN/edge orchestration (A5)

3.3.2.1 Evaluation

The motivation for this activity was presented in Section 4.1.5 of D5.1, and the solution design in D4.3, Section 3.4.

To evaluate such solution, named EdgeBOL, we developed an experimental system prototype, as shown in Figure 33 . Our prototype consists of a vBS, a user equipment (UE)², a digital power meter, and an edge server, Figure 33. The vBS and UE include an NI USRP B210 as radio unit (RU) and a general-purpose computer (Intel NUCs with CPU i7-8559U@2.70GHz) deploying the near-RT RIC (for the vBS) and the baseband unit (BBU), implemented with the srsRAN suite. The vBS and UE are connected through

² The UE emulates the requests of multiple users using the service at the edge server.

SMA cables with 20 dB attenuators, and we adjust the transmission gain of the RU's RF chains to attain different uplink SNR values. Without loss of generality, we set 20 MHz bandwidth for the LTE interface.

Figure 33. EdgeBOL experimental testbed.

Our edge server is equipped with a CPU Intel i7-8700K @ 3.70GHz and a GPU Nvidia GeForce RTX 2080 Ti. The vBS and server are connected using a switch with Gigabit Ethernet technology. To measure the power consumption at the BBU and the server, we use the digital power meter GW-Instek GPM-8213 with the GW-Instek Measuring adapter GPM-001. The evaluated AI service is implemented using Detectron2, developed by Facebook, which performs object recognition. Specifically, Detectron2 is configured with a region-based convolutional neural network (Faster R-CNN) comprising a ResNet backbone with conv4 layers and a conv5 head with a total of 101 layers. The UE sends to server images from the COCO data set we used in D4.3, Section 3.4, through the LTE uplink. The images are resized at the user side using the OpenCV library in Python. The bounding boxes and object classes are computed by Detectron2 and sent back to the UE (LTE downlink).

We introduced two key rsrNB modifications. First, we modified the radio MAC scheduler to implement the two radio policies designed in D4.3, Section 3.4. Secondly, we integrated the O-RAN E2 interface to enforce the radio control policies (MCS and airtime) on-the-fly. We configure the GPU speed by using the Nvidia driver that allows us to set the maximum power management limit, ranging between 100 and 280W. This runtime configuration does not affect the GPU operation. Note that the actual GPU consumed power depends on its duty cycle.

We consider $|\mathcal{H}| = |\mathcal{A}| = |\mathcal{I}| = |\mathcal{M}| = 11$; hence there is a large number of $|\mathcal{X}| = 11^4 \approx 14.6 \cdot 10^3$ control policies, which, in combination with the effect of the possible contexts, highlights the need for a data-efficient learning mechanism. In line with previous works, we select $\beta^{1/2} = 2.5$ to parametrize the Bayesian model designed in D4.3, Section 3.4, which shows good performance in our evaluations. Finally, unless otherwise stated, we will plot our results with lines and shadowed areas representing, respectively, the median value and the 10th and 90th percentiles, across 10 independent repetitions.

3.3.2.1.1 Convergence

To evaluate the convergence of EdgeBOL, we consider a single context and a certain constraint set with ρ^{min} (minimum mAP performance) and d^{max} (maximum service delay). Dynamic context changes and different constraints are evaluated later. Namely, we set the mean SNR to 35 dB (good wireless conditions), $\delta_1 = 1$ mu/W, $\rho^{min} = 0.5$, and $d^{max} = 0.4$ s. Figure 34 plots the evolution over time of the cost (u_t), mAP performance (ρ_t), delay (d_t), and server and BS power consumption (p_t^s and p_t^b) as a function of δ_2 .

The first observation is that the cost u_t (top plot) converges within roughly 25 time periods across all $\delta_2 = \{1, 2, 4, 8, 32\}$. Higher δ_2 values induce higher cost as the price associated to each watt consumed by the BS grows. Remarkably, both the mAP performance and delay fall within the selected system constraints upon convergence with high probability. In fact, we have observed consistent results (converge speed, satisfaction of system constraints) irrespectively of the context and system constraints.

Figure 34. Convergence evaluation. A scenario with steady channel conditions (no context changes), $\delta_1 = 1 \text{ mu/W}$, $\rho^{\min} = 0.5$, and $d^{\max} = 0.4 \text{ s}$.

The system power consumption presents interesting trade-offs with δ_2 . Small δ_2 (e.g., $\delta_2 = 1$) induce high power consumption at the BS but low at the server. This is because the maximum net power consumption of our virtualized BS (around 7.25 W) is much smaller to that of the server (between 85 to 180 W). Therefore, if the associated cost (mu/W) is similar for both BS and server, EdgeBOL will minimize the power consumption of the server at the expense of a small energy toll for the BS. However, when δ_2 is relatively high (e.g., $\delta_2 = 64$), the actual cost associated with the energy footprint of the BS becomes comparable, or higher, than that of the server. Hence, EdgeBOL drives the system to configurations that minimize BS power consumption at the expense of the server energy. This latter case is relevant for situations when a small cell has stringent power budget (e.g., solar-powered) or has cooling restrictions. Indeed, different types of BS have different energy footprint, which motivates the need for approaches that learn the relationship between power consumption patterns, performance metrics and configuration policies.

3.3.2.1.2 Static scenarios

Let us now take a closer look at the power consumption and the respective EdgeBOL's policies for different constraints and values of δ_2 . Figure 35 shows the power consumption and normalized cost once EdgeBOL has converged for $\delta_1 = 1$ and $\delta_2 = \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64\}$ mu/W. We compute the normalized cost independently for each δ_2 so we can compare across different δ_2 values. We now test different constraint settings: (i) $d^{\max} = 0.5 \text{ s}$, $\rho^{\min} = 0.4$ (lax constraints), (ii) $d^{\max} = 0.4 \text{ s}$, $\rho^{\min} = 0.5$ (medium constraints), and (iii) $d^{\max} = 0.3 \text{ s}$, $\rho^{\min} = 0.6$ (stringent constraints), represented in red, green, and blue in the figure. In addition, we represent with dashed lines the cost attainable by an offline oracle, which we obtained using a time-consuming exhaustive search procedure over the whole control space. Though this approach is unfeasible in practice, it is a good benchmark to empirically assess the optimality of EdgeBOL.

Ignoring, for now, the differences across different constraints settings (different colors in the plots), we can make two observations. First, we can confirm our earlier observation that higher values of δ_2 (compared to δ_1) steer EdgeBOL to shift power consumption from the server to the BS (and vice versa). Second, EdgeBOL is able to drive the system to near-optimal points of operation, when comparing the cost of EdgeBOL with that obtained by our oracle.

In more detail, the figure renders very different behavior across different constraint settings (colors in the plot). In the case of $d^{\max} = 0.5 \text{ s}$, $\rho^{\min} = 0.4$ (lax constraints, in red in the plot), there is a drastic change in the selected policies and resulting power consumption as we increase δ_2 . Because these settings are rather lax, EdgeBOL has more leeway to explore (and then select a policy from) a larger space of feasible policies. This is made evident when we compare its normalized cost with that of the most stringent settings ($d^{\max} = 0.3 \text{ s}$, $\rho^{\min} = 0.6$, blue line in the figure): for $\delta_2 = 1$, the minimum cost attained by EdgeBOL is 25% larger for the latter, and 10% for $\delta_2 = 64$. Moreover, the normalized cost consistently grows, though with a shrinking gap in cost across constraint settings, as we increase δ_2 . This occurs because, in our testbed, the range of power values that the BS can consume (across all policies) goes between 4 and 8 W, which is substantially smaller to that of the server (between 50 and 200 W). As a result, when we increase δ_2 , i.e., when we increase the importance given to reducing BS power, the cost variance across policies reduces. Note that this may vary with diverse BS such as macro cells.

Figure 35. Power consumption and normalized cost for a single context as a function of δ_2 , with $\delta_1 = 1$ μ /W. Dashed lines represent our exhaustive search benchmark.

Figure 36. Policies for a single context as a function of δ_2 , with $\delta_1 = 1$ μ /W.

Finally, Figure 36 shows the corresponding control policies for the same scenarios shown in Figure 35. Let us first consider the lax settings ($d^{max} = 0.5$ s, $\rho^{min} = 0.4$, depicted with red lines in the figure). When δ_2 is small, EdgeBOL imposes low-consuming server-side policies, i.e., low GPU speed policies. This certainly helps to reduce the server consumption, and the overall cost as a consequence. However, to meet the performance constraints, EdgeBOL has to compensate low GPU speed policies with higher image resolutions and higher radio policies that ease the job of the service while minimizing delay, which comes at the expense of higher BS power consumption. Conversely, when δ_2 increases, EdgeBOL selects low-consuming radio policies and, to compensate, lower image resolutions and higher GPU speed policies that help reduce service delay. On the other side, for the scenario with most stringent constraints ($d^{max} = 0.3$ s, $\rho^{min} = 0.6$, blue lines), EdgeBOL is forced to deal with a smaller space of feasible policies. Therefore, all policies are roughly consistent across different δ_2 values (with mild differences for the highest settings).

3.3.2.1.3 Dynamic scenarios

We now test the performance of EdgeBOL in the presence of fast context dynamics and sudden constraint changes. Let us start with the former. To this end, we deploy an untrained EdgeBOL in an environment where the wireless conditions quickly vary between 5 and 38 dB, as depicted by the first plot in Figure 37, and set $\delta_1 = 1$ and $\delta_2 = 8$. The top right plot depicts the size of the safe control set over time. As expected, the safe set quickly reduces within roughly 25 time periods and then adapts to the eventual contextual changes, with fluctuations matching the context changes. Remarkably, EdgeBOL converges upon only 3 cycles over all contexts under evaluation. This is possible because the knowledge acquired by EdgeBOL for one context is *actually transferred across similar contexts*. That is, EdgeBOL is able to select judicious policies, shown in the remaining plots of the figure, even for unseen contexts. Specifically, for this choice of δ parameters, the GPU speed policy and the MCS policy highly vary upon context dynamics, whereas the image resolution and the airtime policy remain consistently high. It is worth mentioning that this policy dynamics is substantially different for diverse values of δ (not shown here to avoid clutter).

Figure 37. Evolution of policies for dynamic contexts ($\delta = 8$).

The above illustrates one of the major advantages of our approach, which makes appropriate decisions—even for contexts unseen before—by inferring correlations between the cost function and the context-control space. Conventional neural network-based approaches are substantially less efficient in doing so, which renders EdgeBOL a particularly *data-efficient* solution.

To assess this, we implement a customized version of the deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG). Since the DDPG is designed to address the full-RL problem, we need to adapt it to address a contextual bandit problem, according to our formulation. The DDPG algorithm uses an actor-critic neural network architecture, but the critic, instead of approximating the Q function (full-RL problem), it learns a new cost function referred to as *DDPG cost*. The *DDPG cost* takes the value of when all the constraints in are satisfied, and the maximum cost value otherwise. Note that the DDPG does not handle constraints naturally and by using the *DDPG cost* function we allow the algorithm to do it. The DDPG algorithm is particularly appealing for this type of problem because it operates with continued-valued control spaces. Conversely, value-based approaches (such as Deep Q-Networks) are impractical for large control spaces, such as ours.

Figure 38. Evolution of delay and mAP upon changes on the constraint settings for EdgeBOL and DDPG approach implemented with neural networks ($\delta = 8$).

We then test EdgeBOL and DDPG in a dynamic scenario where the constraint settings change over time: (i) $d^{max} = 0.5$ s, $\rho^{min} = 0.4$ from $t = 0$ through $t = 1000$; (ii) $d^{max} = 0.4$ s, $\rho^{min} = 0.6$ from $t = 1000$ through $t = 2000$; and (iii) $d^{max} = 0.5$ s, $\rho^{min} = 0.5$ from $t = 2000$ on. Figure 38 depicts the evolution over time of the service delay and the mAP performance for both approaches. Not surprisingly, EdgeBOL rapidly converges to policies that respect the performance constraints, even when they suddenly change. The non-parametric nature of our approach and the fact that we can compute safe control sets for any constrained setting based on prior data, allows EdgeBOL to drive the system to the new

optimal points of operations almost instantaneously. In marked contrast, our neural network-based benchmark takes a substantially higher number of time periods to find the new optimal—it is actually unable to converge prior to the constraint changes—and fails to adapt graciously upon constraint changes because neural networks are parametric models that need to re-learn upon such changes.

3.3.2.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	30% of energy savings in GPU server	As shown in Section 3.3.2.1.2, EdgeBOL can achieve 30% of power consumption savings in a GPU by appropriately tuning parameter δ
K2	30% of savings in GPU resources	The energy savings presented above are determined by a reduction in GPU resources by appropriately tuning parameter δ

3.3.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

The empirical results presented above moreover allow us next to validate the following set of requirements described in D2.3 [4].

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-EAWVNF-006	100%	The solution described in this section is specifically designed to meet service-specific KPIs such as image classification performance while minimizing energy consumption

3.3.3 Energy-aware deployment of VNFs for generic Edge computing (A6)

This section describes experiments to evaluate the SAVRUS approach presented in Section 4.3 of Deliverable 3.3 [5].

3.3.3.1 Prototype Implementation

The core of the SAVRUS approach is the algorithm presented in the mentioned deliverable, which can be found at <https://hadas.caosd.lcc.uma.es/savrus.php>. The front-end is a web application, whereas the backend is developed in PHP 8, and a MariaDB 10 SQL database stores the Quality Attributes (QAs) measurements. In this prototype, the Variability Model (VM) supports Boolean and numerical features (i.e., numerical VMs). The prototype runs on an Intel Core i7-4790 CPU@3.60 GHz processor with 16 GB of memory RAM and an SSD running an up-to-date Ubuntu server 20.04 LTS X86 64 with the latest supported versions of NGINX web server.

We evaluate SAVRUS with a proof of concept that analyses extensive IoT/Edge/Cloud systems. Specifically, we aim to detect features' influence on the energy consumption rate of the IoT/Edge/Cloud system using a Generic Edge Computing (GEC) case study, a VM with an ample configuration space that we have designed to represent regular IoT/Edge/Cloud systems [14]. The VM of GEC is depicted in Figure 39, comprising six main branches: Device, Architecture, Operating System (OS), Programming Language, Edge Technology and Edge Context.

Figure 39. Variability Model of the Generic Edge Computing large case study.

Following the planning process for the energy-efficient software [15], we measured the GEC energy consumption rate QA in Watts, triple-checking with three professional tools: Watts Up Pro Portable Power Meter, Multimeter Eversame C, and Eversame PowerMeter 2n1. The devices were always highly cooled in a quiet, isolated room to avoid external factors affecting the readings. We will analyze GEC in four different scenarios, chasing four sets of results. In the first one, we run the Clafer choco-solver for the GEC VM to generate the entire solution space, checking that it is a correct VM. The second scenario is the perspective of a random GEC systems developer interested in improving its products' energy consumption by knowing which are the most efficient component alternatives (i.e., features). In this scenario, the developer acts as a SAVRUS user who interacts with its graphical web interface by running a sequence of SAVRUS instances with different analysis requirements. We execute two sets of SAVRUS instances for the third scenario for a few VMs, including GEC. We focus on the average accuracy, coverage, and runtime of each combination. In the last scenario, we evaluate the scalability of SAVRUS for colossal QA spaces like GEC's.

Evaluating fresh versus established instances of SAVRUS will not differ in detecting the noteworthy features and interactions. On the contrary, it could affect the resulting ranking of those features. We initially set the Transfer Learning (TL) scoring weights to 0 (i.e., not affecting). To prevent this and reflect actual usage of SAVRUS, we performed an initial set of 1000 SAVRUS runs with random user parameters generated by the PHP8 openssl random pseudo bytes(), like the strategy to use, the number of samples, and feature constraints. After that, we conducted 100 runs of the SAVRUS prototype and averaged the results for a confidence level of 95% with a 10% margin of error [16]. In this second set of instances, the k parameter was left by default (k = 2). For this setting, the GEC average ranked list of the most to the least influential top 10 noteworthy features and interactions affecting the energy consumption rate was: 1. Runs, 2. Phoronix Test Suite, 3. Windows, 4. (HP Elite X2) G1, 5. Bluetooth + Send, 6. Wireless + Send, 7. Architecture, 8. (Intel) NUC8i3BEH, 9. StartUp, and 10. Shutdown. We represent graphically this result in Figure 40, indicating changes in the order of effect. Noteworthy features, colored in bold red, are meant to be avoided to improve the QA values – i.e., to decrease the energy consumption rate in our study. Hence, the developer is implicitly advised to replace those with alternatives, which, just for simplicity, are marked as dotted green features in Figure 40.

Figure 40. Improving GEC energy consumption rate by switching the noteworthy red to alternative green features.

Figure 41. The interactive graphical interface of the SAVRUS web prototype.

Nevertheless, SAVRUS is an interactive approach that developers will normally execute several times while taking decisions based on previous executions. Thus, we now present a SAVRUS usage scenario running a GEC analysis of a developer that needs to understand which features affect the energy consumption rate of the system under development. First, the developer loads in her favorite web browser SAVRUS, which welcomes her with the graphical interface of Figure 41. Then, she clicks the Analyze button without selecting features or declaring numerical values (i.e., cross-tree constraints). This results in receiving a similar graphical list to Figure 40 – an overview of GEC features and energy interactions. While so much data can be overwhelming by itself, a quick look at the red indicators tells her that the Edge Context seems to be playing a significant role in the energy consumption of GEC, no matter the case.

With the information provided by SAVRUS, the developer understands that we should avoid constantly restarting a device, as Shutdown and Startup are energy consumer features and Sending data. Additionally, the developer noticed that the measuring operation was not considered noteworthy (i.e., did not negatively affect GEC energy requirements), which was essential to discard the observer's paradox. After that, as she is interested in sending and Receiving data with GEC, she constrains those operations in the second run of SAVRUS. The new results are visible in Figure 42, where she sees a reduction in the number of noteworthy features detected, simplifying the application of the obtained insights. Based on that second run and the green-marked features, some actions that she can pursue to reduce the system energy requirement are: Switch the Device to a RaspberryPi and the OS to Linux/BSD; Use External Storage instead of a constant Wireless connection; Not worrying about most of the peripherals. By switching the Device and OS to the green alternatives, she saves between 5 and 27 watts, based on our measurements. That means a 16-90% decrease in the system's energy requirements of the system to perform the same task.

Based on the noteworthy red features, she should avoid using Bluetooth wirelessly to send data; she should use WiFi instead. She saved up to 1 watt in every possible scenario by changing the GEC wireless interface to WiFi. Furthermore, she could keep performing newer runs of SAVRUS, hence obtaining deeper insights. As a final note, current mandatory features as architecture could be identified as noteworthy red features, yet irreplaceable in every scenario of the current model. In conclusion, the main features and interactions increasing the energy consumption rate in GEC, and aimed to change by an alternative, are Windows OS, larger devices such as HP and Intel, and last, Sending Wireless data. Considering that we performed the analyses with just 3% samples of the 0.25% measurements of the total space, and we can reduce the energy consumption of GEC up to 90%, we conclude that SAVRUS is a functional approach that matches our objectives.

Figure 42. SAVRUS results for GEC considering the features Send and Receive user requirements as variability model constraints.

3.3.3.2 Evaluation

In this section, we empirically demonstrate that SAVRUS generates meaningful results sufficiently fast by analyzing two aspects of our prototype: its validity and scalability. We require VMs to be wholly measured for a QA to empirically demonstrate that SAVRUS results are correct. As stated, it takes much time and resources to predict energy consumption – note that energy is always estimated, never measured. According to [17], large systems and VMs thoroughly measured for any energy footprint are currently nonexistent and unlikely to happen. GEC is an example of this issue; thus, we cannot use it to derive SAVRUS' accuracy.

As an alternative, we search for the most similar QA in which measuring is independent of complex expertise and tooling. According to Weber et al. [18], while the performance QAs runtime and energy do not necessarily correlate in every situation, they exhibit similar trends. Additionally, runtime performance is a well-known QA commonly used in the variability reasoning community and measured per configuration. Accordingly, we selected the four real-world VMs provided by authors of [19]: Dune, HSMGP, HiPAcc and Trimesh [20]. Table 8 shows them ordered by the configuration space size in ascending order. We sequentially execute the SAVRUS prototype 20 times. We repeat this process five times for VM, degrading the measured space differently five times, reaching 100 analyses per VM.

Table 8. Detailed real-world variability models ordered by their search space size, of which GEC QA is incompletely measured.

NVM	Description	Booleans	Numericals	Space	QA	Measurements
Dune	Multi-grid Solver	11	3	2304	Equation solving time	2304
HSMGP	Stencil-grid solver	14	3	3456	Equation solving time	3456
HiPAcc	Image analysis framework	33	2	13485	Equation solving time	13485
Trimesh	Triangle Mesh library	13	4	239360	Equation solving time	293360
GEC	Generic Edge Computing	552	2	~5.3*10 ⁸	Energy Consumption	132.500

3.3.3.2.1 SAVRUS approach validity

For each analysis, we calculated and averaged the following metrics:

- **Time:** It is the averaged runtime in minutes (m) performed with our implementation of SAVRUS of N analyses of a variability model VM_x : $SAVRUS\ Time(VM_x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N Runtime_i}{N}$
- **Coverage:** It is the averaged percentage of covered features f_s and pairs of features p_f regarding the total number of them when running SAVRUS for N analyses of a variability model VM_x : $SAVRUS\ Accuracy(VM_x) = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \#f_i + \#p_f_i}{\#f_x + \#p_f_x} \right) * 100$
- **Accuracy:** After initially computing the correctly ordered list by a brute-force pairwise, we calculate the accuracy of SAVRUS for N analyses of a variability model VM_x and averaged the percentage of correctly identified and ranked noteworthy features rnf_s up to pairwise interactions. In other words, the accuracy is the probability of SAVRUS detecting and perfectly ordering the most meaningful feature-quality interactions. We compute this using the equation $SAVRUS\ Accuracy(VM_x) = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \#rnf_i}{\#rnf_x} \right) * 100$.

For results fairness and to keep runtime below 10 minutes in all cases, we fixed the number of samples per analysis to 3% of their respective search space. Nevertheless, a user could increase the number of samples to obtain better results at the cost of SAVRUS runtime. However, this is most noticeable for initial space explorations; if similar analyses have been previously executed, a heavy increment of the number of samples produces a large server overhead without proportionally improving its accuracy. Finally, to prevent SAVRUS server blocking, its current time-out is set to 30 minutes.

The averaged results of the 20 * 5 executions per VM are presented in Table 9. We can see that SAVRUS runtime increases linearly and proportionally to the space size, reaching ~ 7 minutes for Trimesh. The opposite occurs with coverage and accuracy, as they slightly decrease, although they keep around [65.2, 76.9]% and [83, 82.8]%, respectively. Hence, SAVRUS returned a correct ranking of noteworthy features and interactions affecting a QA above 80% of the runs; in other words, SAVRUS returned a partially mistaken ordered list less than 20% of the time.

Table 9. SAVRUS time, coverage and accuracy for SRS/DDbS querying 3% samples of the incompletely measured space of four real-world systems.

Model Sampling	SRS			DDbS		
	Time	Coverage	Accuracy	Time	Coverage	Accuracy
Dune	1.5m	73.2%	86.7%	1.3m	76.9%	83.9%
HSMGP	1.9m	72.4%	85.4%	1.4m	75.7%	83.3%
HiPAcc	3.7m	70.5%	84.1%	2.8m	73%	83.3%
Trimesh	7.3m	65.2%	83%	6.6m	68.7%	82.8%
Mean	3.6m	70.3%	84.8%	3m	73.6%	83.4%

Regarding sampling, their means suggest that DDbS is slightly faster (i.e., -0.6 minutes) and has a higher coverage (i.e., +3.3%) than SRS, although SRS is more accurate (i.e., +1.4%) on average. It is interesting to highlight that while SRS has lower coverage than DDbS, it is more accurate; hence, the covered SRS samples seem more meaningful than the ones covered by DDbS but at the cost of a higher runtime. That is also visible by looking at each model metric, where the differences are more stressed when the search space is smaller. DDbS accuracy generally seems more stable than SRS, which decreases faster for larger models. Consequently, the larger the search space, the more sense makes DDbS. Nevertheless, SRS is superior for all tested models if runtime is not considered.

In conclusion, SAVRUS generates a correct ranking of noteworthy features and interactions 80% of the time for every incompletely measured model. This accuracy is inversely proportional to the space size and the number of samples. SRS is generally more accurate than DDbS, even with lower coverage. On the other hand, DDbS is comparatively faster, especially for larger spaces. Hence, the results are reasonably accurate without exploiting domain knowledge.

3.3.3.2.2 SAVRUS prototype scalability

To test the scalability of SAVRUS implementation, we reused the same models used in the previous section. In this case, we degraded these models with an increasing number of samples from 25 to 6400, obtaining 9 sample set sizes, where each one doubles the former one. We have followed the same procedure of 5 * 20 runs per case study (i.e., dotted marks), and the average of the results is shown in Figure 43. We have tested eight scenarios (i.e., four systems * 2 sampling strategies) for nine different sample set sizes, but two of the VMs (Dune and HSMGP) were smaller than the larger sample sizes (3200 and 6400). So, the graph shows a total of 66 cases. The X-axis is the maximum number of samples per analysis, and the Y-axis is the execution time of the analysis.

Figure 43. SAVRUS scalability graph about number of samples.

The graph shows that, while there is a minimum workload of ~ 1 minute, the runtime of a SAVRUS analysis linearly increases proportionally to the number of samples. However, the curves tend to be smooth for larger sample sets. Additionally, the separation between the curves suggests that the execution time also increases based on the complexity and space size of the model. Like the characteristics described in Table 8, the relationship appears linear again. Finally, DDbS is slightly faster than SRS. Those differences tend to increase for larger sample sets and more complex spaces.

Regarding numbers, the execution time was kept below 7 minutes for the worst-case scenario: 6400 samples of the largest and most complex system – Trimesh. However, for standard sample sets, ~ 2% of the total space, the execution time is always below 3 minutes for all cases and scenarios. For simplicity, the graph values refer to the total execution time of SAVRUS, but we have also measured its internals. We have identified that the most time-consuming components of SAVRUS are in the relevant order:

1. The database queries and related functionality include updating TL score weights or requesting k neighbors.
2. Solver-based functions.
3. Machine learning PHP8 libraries.

These experiments conclude that the SAVRUS implementation presents an initial analysis runtime of around 1 minute, taking less than 3 minutes for comprehensible cases and scenarios, and with a worst-case of around 7 minutes. We have empirically demonstrated that it has a linear relationship with the number and complexity of the samples, getting smoother based on how large the sample set is. Finally, the main bottlenecks are the database and the solver.

3.3.3.3 Summary KPIs

The KPIs provided below have been validated in D5.1, D5.2 and in this deliverable.

KPI	Results	Justification
K1	we can reduce the energy consumption of GEC up to 90%	We calculate the VNF energy saving using the GEC dataset. So, we can analyze the influence of the specific VNF on energy consumption

3.3.3.4 Requirement satisfaction

The empirical results presented in the deliverables of this WP allow us to validate the following set of requirements described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-EAWVNF-001	100%	We have empirically demonstrated that it has a linear relationship with the number and complexity of the samples, getting smoother based on how large the sample set is
NFR-EAWVNF-002	100%	According to the experiments, SAVRUS can support developers in selecting appropriate features to save up to 90% of energy consumption
NFR-EAWVNF-003	100%	The models and frameworks rely on sampling for high-speed and efficient analyses, hence theoretically requiring less energy than the optimization offered

3.3.4 Combining VNFs at the edge (A7)

In this deliverable, we feature a new version of the HADES approach that enhances the dashboard of the version presented in Section 2.1 of D4.2. In addition, we report the evaluation results of PlanetARium (presented in D5.2) in emulated scenarios, the energy overhead of Hades and its scalability.

3.3.4.1 Management and monitoring consoles

To support the interaction and visualization of the results of the iTarea module (one of the elements of Hades), we have developed several consoles and integrated this module with external open-source analytics and monitoring solutions like Grafana³, OSM⁴, and Prometheus⁵. The main console (see Figure 44) allows the launch of the assignment process of tasks to nodes considering energy consumption. In addition, it provides access to external apps through buttons (see bottom part of Figure 44).

Figure 44: The main menu of iTarea.

The button “Get From parameters” (see Figure 44) grants access to the manual configuration menu of the nodes (see Figure 45). We can include different information regarding them that will be part of our deployment. For example, the amount of RAM, the location, the number of cores, the importance of saving energy, or even whether it has sensing units or peripherals. We have a similar menu to include the configuration of the tasks, which we do not include due to space limitations. Similarly, this menu permits the inclusion of information on the task’s requirements to be deployed and its necessities regarding peripherals.

As shown in Deliverable 4.2 [21], Hades is integrated with OSM, which oversees the deployment and management of the VNFs/KNFs. We can access the OSM web interface through Hades. Figure 46 shows the deployment of the PlanetARium application in OSM.

The deployed functions are monitored through Prometheus, which can provide the data as plain text files or send them to Grafana for visualization. Figure 47 shows a screenshot of Grafana featuring information on the state of the nodes and pods of a deployment during its execution.

³ <https://grafana.com/grafana/>

⁴ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

⁵ <https://prometheus.io/>

Set the nodes

Name of node

CPU (cycles per second)

Bandwidth up (bits/s)

Power Upload (Ptx)

Maximum energy consumption (Watts)

RAM (Mb)

Importance of saving energy in nodes
(real between 0 and 1).

Power Download (Ptx)

Bandwidth Down (bits/s)

Sensing units (e.g. thermometer), " if any (bits/s)
 Thermometer

Peripherals (e.g. GPU), " if any
 Camera GPU

Type (e.g., sensing mote)

Location

Number of cores

Percentage of idle energy consumption

Submit

Nodes list:

```
[name: 'name', 'cpu': 10000000, 'bwup': 150000000, 'bwup': 0.3, 'maxenergy': 75, 'ram': 2000, 'importance': 1, 'pdown': 0.7, 'bdown': 150000000, 'sensingunits': [], 'peripherals': [camera], 'typecore': 'computing', 'location': 'dispatch 2.30', 'cores': 2, 'percnorm': 30.0] Delete
```

```
[name: 'name', 'cpu': 10000000, 'bwup': 150000000, 'bwup': 0.3, 'maxenergy': 75, 'ram': 2000, 'importance': 1, 'pdown': 0.7, 'bdown': 150000000, 'sensingunits': [], 'peripherals': [], 'typecore': 'computing', 'location': 'dispatch 2.30', 'cores': 2, 'percnorm': 30.0] Delete
```

```
[name: 'name', 'cpu': 10000000, 'bwup': 150000000, 'bwup': 0.3, 'maxenergy': 75, 'ram': 2000, 'importance': 1, 'pdown': 0.7, 'bdown': 150000000, 'sensingunits': [], 'peripherals': [], 'typecore': 'computing', 'location': 'dispatch 2.30', 'cores': 2, 'percnorm': 30.0] Delete
```

Figure 45. Menu for node configuration of iTarea.

OSM Version 12.0.4 | Projects (admin) | User (admin)

NS Instances

Name	Identifier	Nid name	Operational Status	Config Status	Detailed Status	Actions
fc	60bed405-22b1-44f8-bb6c-011895db1e01	featurecommunicatorNS	Done	Done	Done	[Action]
fs	09764646-75cf-43df-8025-21448b892764	filterselectorNS	Done	Done	Done	[Action]
gt	8b62730a-ef62-4389-b269-b574f5abed9d	galaxytrackerNS	Done	Done	Done	[Action]
pt	83115b83-8db9-45d6-9064-fc97c2d9945e	planettrackerNS	Done	Done	Done	[Action]
vc	dc16189f-1f92-45ea-812b-c1f585377228	videocaptureNS	Done	Done	Done	[Action]
vis	48a2b7fd-dc37-442b-8b1c-b27ba1d894f5	visualizerNS	Done	Done	Done	[Action]

Figure 46. Web-based admin console of OSM.

Figure 47. Nodes metrics at runtime in Grafana.

The last functionality included in this new version of Hades is the generation of reports. These reports offer a summary of the tasks assigned to nodes, which consists of the kind of multi-objective problem that has been resolved. Figure 48 shows an example of one of these files. Specifically, this file provides information on the problem that has been resolved and the optimizer used.

```

Result
-----
Restricted license - for non-production use only - expires 2024-10-28
Set parameter NonConvex to value 2
energyMain: 1 0 3 2 2 gurobi.Model Continuous instance mlp: 0 constns, 0 v
Gurobi Optimizer version 10.0.2 build v10.0.2rc0 (win64)

CPU model: AMD Ryzen 7 5800X 8-Core Processor, instruction set [SSE3]AVX[AVX2]
Thread count: 8 physical cores, 16 logical processors, using up to 16 threads

Optimize a model with 20 rows, 33 columns and 53 nonzeros
Model fingerprint: 0x80138304
Model has 20 quadratic constraints
Variable types: 14 continuous, 19 integer (9 binary)
Coefficient statistics:
  Matrix range    [1e+00, 8e+03]
  QMatrix range   [1e+00, 1e+00]
  QLMatrix range  [1e+00, 1e+00]
  Objective range [1e+00, 1e+00]
  Bounds range    [1e+00, 4e+00]
  RHS range       [1e+00, 2e+03]

-----
Multi-objectives: starting optimization with 2 objectives (1 combined) ...
-----

Multi-objectives: optimize objective 1 (weighted) ...
-----

Optimize a model with 20 rows, 33 columns and 53 nonzeros
Model fingerprint: 0xc7be7954
Model has 20 quadratic constraints
Variable types: 14 continuous, 19 integer (9 binary)
Coefficient statistics:
  Matrix range    [1e+00, 8e+03]
  QMatrix range   [1e+00, 1e+00]
  QLMatrix range  [1e+00, 1e+00]
  Objective range [1e+00, 1e+00]
  Bounds range    [1e+00, 4e+00]
  RHS range       [1e+00, 2e+03]
Presolve removed 20 rows and 31 columns
Presolve time: 0.00s
Presolved: 4 rows, 2 columns, 8 nonzeros

```

Figure 48. Result of the execution of *iTarea*.

3.3.4.2 *Prototype implementation*

The left side of Figure 50 shows the edge infrastructure used in this work to evaluate the deployment of the PlanetARium app provided by HADES. The infrastructure consists of eleven heterogeneous nodes: one operates as a manager node while the remaining nodes are distributed in three Kubernetes clusters (using Microk8s release 1.23). The manager node (labeled 1 on the left side of Figure 50) runs instances of HADES, OSM, the Virtual Network Function (VNF)/ Kubernetes-based Virtual Network Function (KNF) catalog repository, and three virtualized VIMs (that are virtualized using OSM's native emu-vim tool) in an Ubuntu VM hosted on a Windows 10 operating system using VirtualBox.

HADES allocates tasks efficiently using the nodes' idle and busy energy consumption (EC). Therefore, the EC of the nodes has been analyzed both at idle (with the Microk8s installed) and during a 1-minute CPU matrix stress test [23]. The matrix stressor is an excellent way to exercise CPU floating-point operations, as well as the memory and data cache of the processor. To measure the EC, we use Watts Up? Pro [24], a physical meter that allows real-time monitoring of the amount of energy supplied to the device connected to the power supply.

Regarding communication, the round-trip time between nodes is obtained by pinging from node a to b (considering the average of sending 1,000 small packets). The transmission rate has been analyzed using the iPerf [25] tool (considering the average transmission rate of sending packages for 100 seconds). Finally, the power transmission is given directly from the characteristics of the nodes' network cards.

3.3.4.3 *Evaluation*

In Deliverable 5.2, we show the reduction in energy consumption of the PlanetARium in physical scenarios. In this section, we report the deployment of PlanetARium in a 5G infrastructure and the energy consumption of the system in simulated environments. We compare the energy consumption obtained with our approach against the default OSM deployment and four other allocation policies. HADES energy overhead is also assessed, and the scalability is analyzed using a benchmark.

Deployment in 5G infrastructures

As a part of our experiments to validate Hades, we have deployed the PlanetARium system in the experimental 5G infrastructure of the I institute (T7 presented in D5.1, Subsection 3.1.7). In these experiments, we used iTarea to assign PlanetARium tasks to the nodes of this experimental site. Figure 49 shows the nodes considered by iTarea. There are three machines with different nodes (identified by their IP addresses in Figure 49) available: a Dell r750 (top-left of Figure 49), which is the closest to the 5G antenna of the building; a Dell r730 (bottom-left of Figure 49), which uses a 5G modem, and a Raspberry Pi (Rbpi in Figure 49), which uses a 5G modem.

Figure 49. Deployment of PlanetARium in experimental testbed.

The deployment selected by iTarea (see Table 10) allocates the most demanding tasks (Planet Tracker and Video Generator) to the most powerful node in terms of computational resources. The Filter Selector task has been assigned to the second node with more computational resources. We measured the energy consumption of these nodes when they were idle, executing the selected task and under stress benchmarks (i.e., running a stress-ng command in Linux). The main conclusion is the results are coherent with our previous experiments in non-5G infrastructures.

Table 10. Node information and energy consumption in Watts of PlanetARium.

VM	Cores	RAM	Task	Energy Consumption (Idle/Task/Stressed)
10.11.32.153	2	12GB	Filter Selector	1.5/3.5/9.5
10.11.32.154	4	16GB	Planet Tracker, Video Generator	3.5/5.5/17.5
10.11.32.155	2	4GB	Galaxy Tracker	1.5/4.5/9.75
10.11.64.155	2	4GB	Feature Generator	4.5/6.7/9.7
10.88.1.58	Raspberry PI		Visualizer	5/6/9.5

Experimentation in emulated scenarios. This subsection tries to draw further conclusions for evaluating the performance of the iTAREA module (the primary function of HADES) in terms of execution time and energy consumption reduction of the solutions by deploying applications in emulated infrastructures (benchmark). These experiments compare the EC of the deployment using the iTAREA module with (1) the obtained using the kube-scheduler (we have obtained the Kubernetes' scoring policy used to assign tasks to nodes from [26]); (2) the policy Best fit stated in [27], that selects the node with the most available resources among those capable of running the application; (3) First fit, that allocates the application to the first node it finds that meets the application requirements; (4) Random fit (also considered in other works [28]), that selects a random node that accomplishes the application's requirements; and (5) Fastest fit, which selects for the most powerful node in terms of CPU capable of running the application. The experiments consider applications of between 10 and 30 tasks and infrastructure between 20 and 30 nodes. The characteristics of the nodes (CPU, RAM, storage, free resources, eMax, a, peripherals, etc.) and application requirements (CPU, RAM, disk, data to transmit/receive, etc.) have been randomized in each experiment. Each experiment has been performed 30 times.

Figure 50. Experimentation setup for PlanetARium experiments.

Figure 51 illustrates, using a box plot, the range of EC (J) resulting from applying the different placement policies (ITarea, First-fit, Random-fit, Fastest-fit, Best-fit, default kube-scheduler). Experiment results reveal that the Fastest-fit policy (orange box) has obtained the worst energy consumption results. This is because, although not necessarily, the most computationally powerful nodes often tend to be the most energy-consuming [29]. The best energy results are obtained through our energy-aware proposal (green box), with an overall reduction in EC between 54% and 59% compared to the rest of the assignment policies.

Figure 51. Energy consumption of the deployment solutions using different placement.

Regarding the execution time of the placement, we consider the time it takes to complete one complete iteration of the application (i.e., all tasks that form the SFC). For PlanetARium, it ranges from 0.006 (in the case of Fastest-fit) to 0.029 seconds (Random-fit). The average execution time of the iTAREA module assignment solutions is 0.011 seconds.

HADES energy overhead. We have shown that HADES significantly reduces the energy consumption of running applications. However, keeping HADES instantiated and running has an associated energy consumption. Then, for HADES to be beneficial and feasible, such energy overhead must be less than the reduction in energy consumption achieved. This section evaluates this impact on the overall EC.

To conduct this experiment, we evaluate the energy consumption of Node 1 (where the HADES instance runs—see the left side of Figure 50) in three scenarios: Scenario a, idle (without OSM and HADES); Scenario b, with a clean OSM installation; and Scenario c, having OSM and HADES installed. The experiments have a duration of one minute. In the case of Scenarios 2 and 3 measurements, the experiments include the time required to deploy PlanetARium KNFs. As in the rest of the tests performed in this work, we have used the Watts Up? Pro physical energy meter.

Figure 52 shows the average energy consumption obtained during the experiments. Node 1 has an idle energy consumption (Scenario a) of 51.6 W. With OSM instantiated and running, this value increases to 53.03 W, an increase over Scenario a of 1.44 W (2.79%). With OSM and HADES running, the energy consumption of Node 1 is 53.37 W, which is an increase over Scenario a of 1.76 W (3.41%) and 0.32 W (0.6%) over Scenario 2. Based on the experiments conducted, we can derive that HADES use does not entail a significant energy consumption overhead, especially when compared to the reduction in energy consumption it can achieve.

Figure 52. Energy overhead of HADES, for node 1.

Scalability. The critical point that threatens the applicability of our proposal lies in the execution time of the iTAREA module. This time depends mainly on the nature of the problem and its size [30]. This section evaluates the execution time of the iTAREA module, which runs during the application deployment and migration process, for different problem sizes. With this purpose, we develop a Benchmark version of the iTAREA, which allows setting the number of VNFs/KNFs of the SFC, the number of nodes that form the infrastructure, and the CPU partitions. A preliminary study revealed that, for infrastructures of less than 20 nodes, the iTAREA returns the solution almost instantly. Thus, the experiments consider infrastructures of 30, 40, and 50 nodes, 5 and 10 CPU partitions per core (100 and 200 millicores allocations), and 10 to 190 VNFs/KNFs. The characteristics of the application (number of CPU cycles, memory, disk, bandwidth, peripherals, etc.) and of the nodes (CPU, cores, memory, disk, bandwidth, peripherals, etc.) are randomly set in each experiment. Since the iTAREA module can be both on a local desktop and in the cloud, we will run the tests both locally (AMD Ryzen 7 5800x, 8 cores, 16 threads at 3.8GHz, 32 Gb RAM) and on the cloud (AMD EPYC 7H12, 128 cores, 256 threads at 2.6 GHz, 64 Gb RAM), using two configurations: (1) using all its potential (128 cores, 256 threads); and (2) using 64 cores (128 threads). Each experiment is performed 30 times.

The following tables contain the mean and standard deviation of the iTAREA module execution time when executed in the three infrastructures described above (the lowest times for each Scenario–nodes and CPU partitions–are highlighted in grey). Experiments reveal that the execution time is shorter when the CPU is allocated in 100-millicore portions (10%, 10 CPU partitions) than when the portions are 200-millicore (5 CPU partitions). For highly heterogeneous infrastructures of 30 to 50 nodes and applications of 30 VNFs/KNFs or less, the iTAREA module returns the solution almost instantly (especially in the case of the desktop).

Table 11. Execution times of the iTAREA module (desktop).

KNFs/VNFs			10	30	50	70	90	110	130	150	170	190
30 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.10	0.72	2.16	4.03	10.81	21.90	136.28	342.12	1024.51	651.74
		std	0.016	0.006	0.021	0.043	0.088	0.176	0.384	1.505	17.867	1.792
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.117	0.691	1.745	3.240	5.761	10.762	13.956	21.798	46.812	72.535
		std	0.002	0.004	0.008	0.022	0.053	0.038	0.043	0.066	0.058	0.464
40 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.138	1.184	2.736	5.327	14.744	25.864	105.353	964.133	1117.22	517.11
		std	0.005	0.017	0.037	0.062	0.157	0.273	0.696	3.325	1.020	2.202
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.152	0.848	2.154	4.317	7.669	12.732	20.417	30.638	37.596	59.984
		std	0.002	0.004	0.008	0.013	0.024	0.048	0.155	0.174	0.116	0.260
50 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.154	1.340	3.254	7.400	13.514	27.561	60.598	227.98	3060.67	25779.
		std	0.006	0.024	0.071	0.103	0.186	0.158	0.575	2.108	6.276	0.022
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.187	1.044	2.845	5.453	9.276	14.073	23.211	29.247	37.163	61.656
		std	0.005	0.015	0.038	0.053	0.069	0.069	0.268	0.238	0.342	0.005

Table 12. Execution times of the iTAREA module (server 64 cores).

KNFs/VNFs			10	30	50	70	90	110	130	150	170	190
30 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.119	1.008	3.080	5.847	11.861	22.685	69.939	119.5	184.876	211.91
		std	0.001	0.058	0.459	0.489	0.441	1.159	1.215	1.734	5.044	11.033
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.143	0.980	2.473	4.455	8.388	14.216	17.991	27.261	39.958	44.883
		std	0.021	0.044	0.087	0.022	0.257	0.448	0.343	0.467	1.224	0.890
40 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.156	1.629	3.543	8.020	15.396	26.140	49.367	161.51	204.119	367.79
		std	0.002	0.108	0.311	0.172	0.603	1.096	1.534	4.775	1.757	2.518
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.204	1.166	2.991	6.312	10.893	18.072	23.606	34.947	43.877	59.635
		std	0.069	0.045	0.024	0.205	0.269	0.370	0.244	0.484	0.536	0.563
50 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.201	1.985	4.661	9.381	19.344	33.057	51.940	112.765	192.17	10587
		std	0.067	0.015	0.035	0.020	0.301	0.339	0.411	0.512	0.742	0.003
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.234	1.461	3.840	7.407	12.999	19.468	29.264	39.221	48.502	69.284
		std	0.206	0.247	0.282	0.747	1.475	0.766	1.166	6.739	12.453	0.002

Table 13. Execution times of the iTAREA module (server 128 cores).

KNFs/VNFs			10	30	50	70	90	110	130	150	170	190
30 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.118	1.104	2.992	5.665	12.106	24.325	63.766	117.687	178.807	208.28
		std	0.002	0.053	0.143	0.190	0.221	0.938	1.266	0.464	0.661	0.714
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.139	1.100	2.623	4.464	8.453	14.742	18.653	28.025	39.735	48.064
		std	0.003	0.064	0.127	0.011	0.356	0.348	0.197	0.412	0.453	0.467
40 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.158	1.791	3.901	8.239	15.510	26.788	47.800	125.015	324.772	190.96
		std	0.002	0.178	0.125	0.316	0.335	1.032	1.297	0.984	1.281	0.554
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.186	1.333	3.011	6.562	11.107	18.586	24.770	36.064	45.706	64.567
		std	0.0	0.054	0.009	0.121	0.285	0.419	0.282	0.588	0.227	0.649
50 Nodes	5 Partitions	mean (s)	0.196	2.156	4.798	9.729	19.118	31.649	46.900	98.196	209.074	397.38
		std	0.249	0.169	0.37	0.332	0.381	1.429	0.541	0.636	1.109	19.995
	10 partitions	mean (s)	0.235	1.568	3.915	7.539	13.299	19.934	30.768	40.385	49.297	75.649
		std	0.069	0.014	0.028	0.227	0.216	0.376	0.328	0.338	0.426	0.424

Figure 53 employs a logarithmic scale to depict the values from previous tables graphically. This representation simplifies the understanding of execution time trends in relation to problem size across different execution infrastructures. In the context of the three considered infrastructures, when handling up to 110 VNFs/KNFs within the iTAREA configuration of 5 CPU partitions (and in almost all scenarios involving 10 CPU partitions), it can be observed that a more extensive use of resources (in the cloud) results in a greater execution time. This occurs because, on occasion, increasing the number of cores can result in programs running slower in terms of total response time compared to less resource-intensive devices. This is because cloud servers often allocate more time to tasks like communication, control, and load balancing between threads and service requests, which can outweigh the computational benefits gained from their utilization [31]. For larger problem sizes, the problem scales well concerning the number of cores, with the cloud up to 6.5 times faster than the desktop in some cases (50 nodes, 5 CPU partitions).

Nonetheless, it is essential to mention that numerous VNFs have the potential to be utilized across multiple SFCs, only requiring a periodic increase in their instances during deployments to prevent overwhelming (auto-scaling) [32]. This fact reduces the number of VNFs/KNFs that must be deployed. Therefore, we can conclude that a commercial desktop computer is sufficient to run our proposal and has been demonstrated to be fast enough to be applicable in real-world environments.

Figure 53. Graphical representation in logarithmic scale of the average execution time of the iTAREA module for 30 (left), 40 (middle), and 50 (right) nodes.

3.3.4.4 Summary KPIs

The KPIs reported below have been validated in the different deliverables of this WP.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	Reduction between 54% and 59% compared to the other assignment policies	To compute the energy consumption, we use an energy model that we presented in D3.2 to measure the energy of different configurations of the Planetarium. We obtain energy savings by measuring the differences in energy consumption between the different configurations
K2	Idem	Our approach is focused on the edge, so the saving of computational resources of the VNF is directly related to the savings on energy consumption in the edge. So, we provide the same results as K1

3.3.4.5 Requirement satisfaction

The empirical results presented in D5.1, D5.2, and D5.3 let us validate the requirements in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-EAWVNF-001	100%	For larger problem sizes, the problem scales well concerning the number of cores, with the cloud up to 6.5 times faster than the desktop in some cases (50 nodes, 5 CPU partitions)
NFR-EAWVNF-002	100%	The placement solution reduces up to 51% of the energy consumption compared with the default deployment proposed by the existing MANO standard solution
NFR-EAWVNF-003	100%	Based on the experiments conducted, we can derive that HADES use does not entail a significant energy consumption overhead, especially when compared to the reduction in energy consumption it can achieve

3.3.5 AI-Enhanced MANO (A8)

This activity targets the development and experimental assessment of a platform for AI-supported MANO. Currently, the work has focused on the integration of the components of the platform towards deploying a comprehensive and flexible architecture that will enable structured MANO tests in the presence of NI.

3.3.5.1 Evaluation

The AI-enhanced MANO solution is deployed on a set of servers on which the OSM and OpenStack are deployed. To enable intelligence at the orchestration and management level, multiple interfaces with different components are used. Specifically, the connection with Open-Source MANO has been enabled through the OSM’s Northbound API featuring ETSI NFV SOL005. Communication with OpenStack has been done through its provided API with a RESTful web service endpoint to access, provision, allocate and automate the resources. Data and logs are retrieved directly from Elasticsearch REST API, which is also used in cases of configuration and access to other Elasticsearch features. Additionally, custom APIs have been designed and developed to enable the acquisition of information from VNFs, applications and infrastructure with the use of exporters that send specific metrics to the

Elasticsearch and Diagnostic components. Finally, the connection with Verticals has been performed with a custom API that directly connects the AI-enhanced MANO with the Verticals retrieving in this way all requirements or specific SLAs.

Figure 54. AI-enhanced MANO solution.

The architecture of the AI component is shown in Figure 54 and its connections and functions are explained below.

1. Direct Verticals info (i.e., Metrics/KPIs) of the Network Service (NS) that will be deployed acquired from AI-enhanced MANO or by utilizing the 5G EVE APIs.
2. Internally an API SERVER gets the request and triggers the AI component to evaluate the optimal deployment of the VNFs based on Vertical requirements and KPIs.
3. The API SERVER gets the VNF's info from the OSM (OSM NB API) and historical data from the db.
4. The API SERVER retrieves the metrics exported from the MEC platform and the MEC's VNF instances, to evaluate the metrics in real-time.
5. The AI component acquires all information in real-time (MEC's metrics, VNF IDs, and VNF requirements) from the API SERVER and uses old data and previous decisions. The AI finds the optimal deployments and migrations for the NSs in MECs.
6. The AI component triggers the OSM (OSM NB API), through the API SERVER, for any migration or reallocation of resources.

Additionally, Table 14 presents the enhancements that functionality allocation optimization mechanism and performance diagnosis bring to management and orchestration (MANO) operations applied to an industrial vertical. We compare the typical MANO workflow (notification, action) as baseline, with the AI-enhanced MANO workflow which uses performance diagnosis and the functionality allocation mechanism. Both workflows are used to handle two types of events/operation descriptions that can happen in the industrial context of the PoC. For each of these types, ten instances of events are triggered manually, following the typical patterns of the industrial automation service and the average of them is presented in Table 14. The two events are:

- a. The redeployment of functionalities to maximum number of resources caused by load increase.
- b. The scaling of functionalities to new resources caused by increasing load.

For each of these events we measured the following time periods:

- The notification time which is the time the monitoring system needs to check for the status of the node/component.
- The detection time which is the time the monitoring system needs to detect that there is an issue including possible timeouts, retries, etc.
- The response time which is the time the corrective actions take to be triggered on the respective component (DAEMON KPI K3).
- The operations time (provisioning time) which is the time it takes for the corrective actions to be completed, e.g., functionality reallocation, scaling by commissioning resources etc.

- The application time which is the time the service needs to be restored (mainly due to service initialization or management operations in case it became unavailable).
- The recovery time, i.e., the time of the appearance of the event until the service is available again. (DAEMON KPI K8).

The validation of the proposed algorithm illustrates a response time (K3) of the AI algorithm of about 280 – 330ms, while for the overall recovery (response) of the application we measure values around 10-14s. The actual AI suite takes about 10ms to run. Respective figures, when the algorithm is not involved, can be around 5-11s for K3 and from 21-30s for K8, depending on the case handled by MANO.

Table 14. Collected time measurements during unexpected events.

Event description		Typical MANO	AI MANO
Redeployment of functionalities to maximum number of resources, caused by load increase	Notification time	10.10s	3.90s
	Detection time	3.61s	4.80s
	Response time	10.95s	0.33s
	Operations time	3.05s	2.78s
	Application time	2.00s	2.00s
	Recovery time	29.71s	13.81s
Scaling of functionalities to new resources, caused by load increase	Notification time	9.80s	3.50s
	Detection time	1.40s	2.30s
	Response time	5.20s	0.28s
	Operations time	3.00s	2.39s
	Application time	2.00s	2.00s
	Recovery time	21.40s	10.47s

Figure 55. KPI measurements during unexpected events.

3.3.5.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allows to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K3	10 ms	The actual AI suite takes about 10ms to run, contributing to an overall Response time of the AI –MANO algorithm of about 280 – 330ms
K8	10-14s	We measure the response time of the application, which is the delay for the whole request and response process, up to service recovery

3.3.5.3 Requirement satisfaction

The results presented above allow us to validate the following requirement described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-SLMANO-001	100%	DAEMON defined metrics to check the stability of a control algorithm

3.3.6 Placement and routing for network services (A30)

In Section 6.1 of Deliverable D4.1 [33], a RL (reinforcement learning) method, referred to as SFC-E (service function chain embedding), was described to embed network services, described by SFCs (service function chains) in an infrastructure of one datacenter. In Section 5.1 of Deliverable D4.2 [21] an additional component was introduced to deal with the multi data center scenario. In particular, a DMARL (distributed multi agent RL) based and a DDQL (double deep Q learning) based method was proposed to split an SFC over various data centers was introduced. Section 4.2.6 of deliverable 5.2 [1] reported typical results obtained with that method.

3.3.6.1 Evaluation

The main conclusion of these two evaluations is that RL can be beneficially used for the embedding of SFCs (e.g., network services) into a common multi-datacenter infrastructure. Off-line training (or training on a digital twin) is required, because during training many policies (including wrong policies) need to be explored in order to come to an adequate policy, which may mess up the performance of all currently active services, which an operator will be reluctant to do on a deployed infrastructure. Once trained the policy can be rolled out yielding a substantial gain (e.g., 30%) with respect to the industry standard solution (based on static rules). During operation it needs to be checked whether or not the policy must be changed by observing the trade-off between SLA violations and request rejections. Such a decrease in performance may be due to the fact that circumstance during the live deployment might have become different from the ones during training. In case it is detected that the performance degrades, the policy needs to be retrained off-line.

3.3.6.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allows to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	30% computational saving	With respect to the current industry standard (i.e., deploying new network services in predetermined data centers based on some static rule for which often template scripts are manually adapted), the placement and routing algorithms studied in DAEMON can automatically distribute load over various data centers, thus saving 30% computing resources (for a similar blocking ratio) (see Section 4.2.6 of deliverable D5.2)
K4	30% OPEX saving	This reduction in computational resource is accompanied with a similar reduction in OPEX (see K2 above)

3.3.6.3 Requirement satisfaction

The results presented above moreover allows us next to validate the following non-functional requirements described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-SLMANO-000	100%	Latency was the high level KPI that was used
NFR-SLMANO-001	100%	DAEMON has defined two metrics that expresses the stability of a system: 1) the fraction of time that the controller takes active decision divided by the optimal number of decisions measured over some interval (for controlled loop decision); 2) the amplitude of the fluctuation in the reward (for RL approaches)

3.3.7 Energy-prudent vRAN management with loss meta-learning (A33)

In this activity we evaluate a similar use case as the one considered in Activity A4 (see Section 3.3.1 of this document and Section 4.2.1 of D5.2). We consider a virtualized RAN (vRAN) management scenario. Here, the network operator takes the decision on the functional split of the PHY/MAC function pipeline between Distributed Units (DU) and Central Units (CU).

3.3.7.1 Evaluation

The main goal of the operator is maximizing its energy efficiency to ensure RAN sustainability. The technical details of the solution for this activity have been presented in Section 3.3.1.2 of the deliverable D4.3 of this project.

Considering the traffic requirements at a specific Distributed Unit (DU), various functional divisions result in distinct computational burdens at both the DU and Central Unit (CU). This occurs as PHY/MAC functions transition from the former to the latter. The primary goal of the Management and Orchestration (MANO) system is to determine, for each DU and at each decision point, the optimal functional split. This decision aims to minimize the overall energy cost of the virtual Radio Access Network (vRAN) system. It's crucial to emphasize that, being a preemptive decision, it must rely on a forecast of the anticipated mobile data traffic that the DU is expected to encounter during the upcoming decision interval.

It is important to note that, in practice, the network operator lacks knowledge about the policy governing the activation of Physical Machines (PMs) set by the cloud provider hosting the Central Unit (CU), as well as the precise power consumption patterns of both PMs and Distributed Units (DUs) equipment. Despite this lack of information, the operator is required to make decisions regarding functional splits and allocate computing resources in the CU. Moreover, the interconnected nature of PM activation decisions, influenced by all DUs, creates a scenario where predictions are intertwined and the overarching objective remains unknown. In this scenario, we can incorporate the loss meta-learning architecture presented in Section 7.1.3 of D2.3 [4] to handle the functional split.

3.3.7.1.1 Comparative performance summary

We compare our solution with the only two other approaches that can be applied when no information about relationship between DU-CU split and the energy consumption is available. The first, *FullCU*, represents the case where all computing is done at the CU. The second, *fullDU*, represents the case where all the computing is locally done at the DUs.

We illustrate the temporal behavior of the solution in the following Figure 56. Our solution consistently maintains lower power consumption even when faced with significant fluctuations in mobile demands across consecutive days. Additionally, the stability of the performance of our solution stands out. For instance, the FullCU approach exhibits fluctuations in power consumption, where even minimal variations in traffic can lead to the (de-)activation of an additional Physical Machine (PM) for very brief periods. The bottom graph shows the resource reservation at one CU for four different DUs over time. We can observe how our solution dynamically re-distributes the resources for each DU depending on the load of each of those DUs.

Figure 56. Representation of the operation of the solution. Top, total traffic. Bottom, individual allocated resources for two slices: a value zero indicates that the slice has not been accepted for those periods.

In the following table, we present a quantitative evaluation of the solution, for different number of DUs and one single CU. The functional split is re-computed every 5 minutes, and the energy consumption of each physical machine is based on real world specifications. We show that the solution is able to improve the energy efficiency up to 30%. We note that the improvement decreases as the number of DUs per CU increases. This is not a scalability problem, but rather a natural behavior given the fact that the improvement is limited by the inverse of the number of DUs.

Table 15. Average F1-score of the 5 solutions across the 5 use cases.

DU	Our solution	fullDU		fullCU	
		Power	Increase vs solution	Power	Increase vs solution
2	138.4	180.3	30.3%	162.1	17.1%
4	339.2	365.6	7.8%	415.2	22.4%
6	496.8	542.7	9.2%	566.8	14.1%
8	624.4	663.7	6.3%	682.4	9.3%
10	824.7	861.9	4.5%	886.6	7.5%

3.3.7.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	<50% energy saving	We show that the solution can reduce the required energy to compute up to 30%
K4	60% reduction OPEX	The reduction of energy implies a consequent reduction on OPEX

3.3.7.3 Requirements satisfaction

The results of the empirical evaluations presented above also allow us to validate the following set of requirements, which were described in D2.3 [4].

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-EAWVNF-002	90%	The solution can reduce the energy consumption in the vRAN by more than 40%
NFR-EAWVNF-004	100%	The BSvBS algorithm aims at balancing network throughput and energy consumption in vRANs. As described in the solution description, the algorithm uses the power consumption profile of O-RAN base stations to make decisions on configuring the vBS
NFR-EAWVNF-006	100%	As described in the description above, the solution aims to minimize the overall energy cost of the virtual Radio Access Network (vRAN) system for a requested minimum performance

3.4 Evaluation of NI for real-time anomaly detection and automated anomaly response

In this section, we present the final evaluations related to anomaly detection, namely Evaluation E3 – which focuses on NI solutions that support anomaly detection in real-time in both controlled environments and in a production core network, and Evaluation E5 – which aims at evaluating NI solutions for anomaly response. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E3 and E5 via activities A9, A19 and A25. Table 16 below summarizes the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC execution and main findings of these activities.

Table 16. Evaluation results for E3+E5. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	Reached TRL	Testbed / Dataset	Main findings
A9	Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection	K3, K7	4	T8	NI solutions anomaly detection and response demonstrated high detection performance. Specifically, DAEMON reached 91% while the target was set at 90% precision-recall AUC with at least 85%

					scoring in both precision and recall
A19	Anomaly detection for a roaming platform	K3, K7	5	D8	Achieved device-level anomaly detection for IoT verticals using only signaling information from the roaming platform
A25	Anomaly detection in mobile service traffic at base station level	K7	3	D3	Hybrid forecast for traffic anomaly detection improves performance and provides stability under huge input ranges

3.4.1 Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection (A9)

In Section 4.4.1 of D5.1, we presented the main considerations of the solution, including the high-level architecture and the approach to be used. Here, the detailed design of the solution is presented.

The design of our solution has followed the guidelines established in D2.2 in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2. Those concern the incorporation of prior knowledge in decision-making schemes: the FL setting enables each FL client to extract knowledge from its own specific datasets (based on metrics collected locally) and exchange this knowledge with other clients via a centralized learning process, which ingests complementary knowledge from all clients; in addition, the guidelines also refer to the support for decentralized and distributed data management, for heterogeneous devices, and for different time scales: those are enabled by the independent local operation of each one of the clients. Thirdly, the guideline about the low inference time and the energy consumption is addressed via the adoption of low complexity ML models, both in the local (DBSCAN algorithm) as well as the centralized (CART algorithm) learning processes. Last but not least, the FL-powered NI functionalities guideline is addressed, via several intelligent agents deployed in the various FL setting clients acting cooperatively, via sharing their DBSCAN-based outliers and border points, as described next in detail.

The solution utilizes the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), which is a classical approach that has been applied in several outlier detection problems. DBSCAN performs unsupervised learning and classifies the analyzed data points into core points (normal behavior), border points (potentially anomalous behavior) and outliers (anomalous behavior).

The first step of the whole process is to configure the DBSCAN parameters, namely the values of ϵ (i.e., the minimum distance that shall separate the two nearest points in different clusters) and the minPts (i.e., the minimum number of points required to form a dense region). This configuration is dataset-specific and depends on the investigated feature vector size. Then, the DBSCAN is triggered for each FL client to execute locally based on the latest data received. Each client performs a distributed, "own-evaluation" of the process output, via calculating the Silhouette Coefficient Score (SCS). Then, only if the SCS indicates a satisfactory value (i.e., positive value and close to 1), then the respective client is requested to transmit the DBSCAN's output to the central FL controller, i.e., the extracted outliers, border points, SCS value and data volume. The latter is important in the centralized process, as the data volume that has been processed by each one of the FL clients, defines its respective "weight" in the federation process (algorithm pseudocode follows for more information).

Specifically, the centralized step adjusts the population of the received datasets, (i.e., the vector of the outliers, border points, SCS value, and data volume received from each FL client) by a factor. The population includes the logged/processed data volume of client k , during epoch one training period, over the sum of all FL clients' data. Then, the CART algorithm is used on the adjusted data; CART is a *Gini impurity index*-based decision-tree extraction algorithm, which extracts a number of rules that are then broadcasted to the FL clients of the system.

Figure 57. Overview of the Federated Learning-powered Anomaly Detection solution.

In this hybrid approach, the FL clients are applying rule-based anomaly detection for real-time operation, while the unsupervised DBSCAN is used at different timescales and requests for new incoming data towards enhancing the centralized CART model.

The development of the aforementioned solution is completed and lab-based validation is realized. The results demonstrate a response time of the Federated learning-powered algorithm (K3) of around 200-250 ms including all the network and protocol delays.

The evaluation of our federated learning model across five clients, as depicted in Figure 58, reveals a robust performance. It achieved high levels of precision, recall, F1-score, accuracy, and AUC scores—most of the metrics averaging above 0.8, with the AUC achieving more than 0.9. Notably, the precision score, which assesses the model's exactness, suggests an adeptness at minimizing false positives, a critical attribute for network anomaly detection. The recall scores indicate the model's strength in capturing the majority of actual positive instances. The F1-score, an aggregate measure of precision and recall, along with accuracy, reflects the model's balanced and comprehensive performance in classifying network data, confirming the effectiveness of the federated learning system. The consistently high AUC scores across all clients further underscore the model's exceptional capability to differentiate between classes, highlighting its predictive proficiency.

Figure 58. Performance of the proposed federated learning model for anomaly detection.

3.4.1.1 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allows to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Results	Justification
K3	Results demonstrate a response time of the FL-powered algorithm (K3) of around 200-250 ms.	We measure the response time of the Federated Learning (FL)-powered algorithm, which is the average latency between a request for the FL client is delivered to the FL controller and the response of the FL controller including the updated model, is delivered to the FL clients.

K7	Precision 0.842, Recall 0.862, F1-Score 0.852, Accuracy 0.816, AUC score 0.913.	We generated network impairments and calculated the precision of the proposed solution to identify the impairments. The proposed solution was evaluated for its effectiveness.
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3.4.1.2 Requirement Satisfaction

The results presented above allows us to validate the following requirement described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-AARES-000	100%	NI solutions anomaly detection and response demonstrated high detection performance. Specifically, DAEMON reached 91% while the target was set at 90% precision-recall AUC with at least 85% scoring in both precision and recall

3.4.2 Anomaly detection for a roaming platform (A19)

3.4.2.1 Evaluation

In this section, we present the final evaluation of the NI solution that we presented in deliverable D4.3,[3] in Section 5.2 (Proactive anomaly detection for IoT services in a global roaming platform), which we further call ANCHOR.

Throughout the duration of the project, we have evolved the pipeline for the ANCHOR solutions, and we have also experimented with different network data representation approaches. In Figure 59 we give an overview of the different attempts that we have had in order to solve the same problem of anomaly detection in a global platform for IoT. Branches 1 and 2 map to the information we previously presented in deliverable D4.1 [33] and D4.2 [21], while on Branch 3, we integrate the feature engineering and clustering approach that we explained in D4.3 [3].

We further present the final evaluation results for the ANCHOR Branch#3 implementation, which is the most promising. We show the results of the pilot that we have performed with TGS for this solution.

For ANCHOR Branch#3 evaluation, we first train ANCHOR for a set of ≈4M devices from over 200 different IoT clients. The data consists of signaling data from September 1st, 2022, to September 30th, 2022, and validation set consists of signaling data from October 2022. For validation, we build a ground truth with anomalies for 7 different IoT clients that we have retrieved from the ticketing systems, and which occurred throughout October 2022. Each client has operations across different economies, with varying number of devices deployed in each country. In order to validate and understand the performance of each model on each cluster, we report the percentage of anomalies that were accurately detected from the ground truth per client/country/day.

Figure 59. ANCHOR Pipeline Overview. We show here the different attempts that we had for solving the problem of device-level anomaly detection in the IoT platform. Branch#3 represents the latest version of ANCHOR with an advanced feature engineering tested on two separate providers.

3.4.2.1.1 General Clusters

For the September 2022 period, the clustering algorithm divides the devices of the multiple customers in five groups, as per Table 17. In the table, we have an overview of the five clusters we identify, and their main characteristics.

The following five patterns emerge:

Cluster 1: mostly stationary devices, 2G/3G connectivity only, very low volume of dialogues

Cluster 2: stationary devices, 4G LTE connectivity only, medium volume of dialogues

Cluster 3: mildly mobile devices, 2G/3G connectivity, high volume of dialogues

Cluster 4: highly mobile devices, mixed 2G/3G/4G LTE connectivity, very high volume of dialogues

Cluster 5: stationary devices, patchy 4G LTE connectivity (with 2G/3G), high volume of dialogues.

Table 17. Overview of mean values for the features that distinguish the clusters of IoT devices.

Device Cluster	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
Overall Statistics: Protocol Usage and Devices					
# Devices	1.7M	420k	894k	300k	621k
#Dialogues per device/day	8.7	22.4	98.4	1300	72
MAP Dialogs (2G/3G) [%]	100	0	99.99	63.4	18.1
Diameter Dialogs (LTE) [%]	0	100	0.01	36.6	81.9
Dialogue Type Volume					
#SAI (2G/3G)	4.2	0	46.4	306	2.1
#SAI (LTE)	0	15	0.01	291	43
#UL (2G/3G)	1.2	0	18.5	145.5	1.1
#UL (LTE)	0	4.4	0.001	244	12.7
#CL (2G/3G)	1.7	0	21.6	117.1	1.6
#CL (LTE)	0	1.2	0.001	102.1	6.5
Mobility Features					
LTE Operator Changes	0	0	0	25	1.6
VLR Changes	2.2	0	36.3	278	1.12
SGSN Changes	1.51	0	20.5	103.8	1

We also validated the consistency of the clustering from Table 17 between two consecutive months (September and October 2022). At inference, we use the previous day of data to assign devices to the generated clusters using the Nearest Neighbor Algorithm, which classifies new devices based on how similar devices (its neighbors) are classified. We run the clustering algorithm on the test set to identify to which cluster each device belongs, then train and apply the anomaly detection algorithm on each cluster independently.

3.4.2.1.2 Training and Inference

Table 18. Percentage of anomalous devices classified as anomalous and present in tickets (i.e., recall), reported per IoT vertical client and day of validation in October. Since the number of IoT devices with anomalies daily varies wildly, to signal the order of magnitude we use no symbols when the number of anomalies is < 10, an * denotes >10, † denotes >100 and ‡ denotes > 1000.

Model Config	IoT Vertical Client										
	Client#1						Client#2	Client#3	Client#4	Client#5	Control
	5/10*	6/10*	20/10*	26/10‡	27/10‡	28/10‡	24/10†	20/10‡	13/10	10/10‡	20/10‡
IF.05 global	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.025%	0.069%	0.0%	0.0%	13.3%	0.0%	8.51%	0.0%
IF.1 global	2.1%	6.25%	4.34%	7.85%	7.9%	6.02%	0.6%	29.79%	0.0%	64.3%	0.0%
IF.05 per cluster	6.52%	6.25%	13.04%	8.24%	6.44%	4.34%	1.54%	25.82%	0.0%	34.15%	0.0%
IF.1 per cluster	6.5%	6.25%	13.04%	18.25%	19.74%	10.85%	2.7%	31.79%	0.0%	71.22%	0.0%
IF.05 major cluster	10.86%	25%	30.43%	17.72%	9.28%	6.23%	6.79%	66.65% / 2.85%	0.0%	8.51%	0.0%
GMM global	25.08%	12.09%	26.08%	20.87%	19.83%	17.99%	0.61%	8.99%	0.0%	1.84%	0.51%
GMM per cluster	2.17%	6.25%	4.34%	1.73%	1.80%	5.18%	0.08%	19.03%	0.0%	66.07%	71.79%
GMM major cluster	2.17%	6.25%	0.0%	0.33%	0.48%	4.20%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	64.51%	65.23%
FC-VAE global	19.57%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	18.83%	18.06%	0.0%	0.32%	0.0%	64.72%	65.54%
FC-VAE per cluster	17.39%	20.83%	56.52%	9.21%	31.39%	28.09%	0.0%	1.34%	0.0%	2.77%	2.77%
FC-VAE major cluster	0.0%	0.0%	17.39%	0.1%	19.02%	13.6%	0.0%	16.77%	0.0%	0.41%	0.0%

For the training time, we observe that values vary between 50 and 400 minutes. Same as before, we leverage for this task a processing instance with 56 cores Intel Xeon E7, 504GB of RAM, and 7 GPUs NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080. The inference time has very small variability and is usually well below the upper bound of a few tens of minutes. In both inference and training time we do not consider the time it takes to create the features, since this is done automatically by a batch job, and does not represent any overhead. Nevertheless, we do consider the time to transform the metrics (for Isolation Forest and VAE, we use the *StandardScaler* transformation), as well as the time to merge the dataset output by the clustering algorithm and the features for the different ML models.

3.4.2.1.3 Model comparison

We now investigate how our models can identify the ground-truth anomalies. We consider incidents that were active during October 2022, and use for validation the first date when the anomaly was observed, as reported in the ticket. We select five different clients with reported anomalies, which correspond to devices on eight (8) countries from different continents, and we verify the ranking of devices with incidents in the output of the model. Note that the ranking reflects the deviation from the "normal" behavior, and the higher a device is in the rank, the higher is the probability of that device having anomalies (i.e., deviations from its previously learned patterns). We also use as Control a client whose devices had no anomalies. We present per-client results observed on different days, considering that a client may be situated in various countries. For example, Client#1 reported anomalies in Spain on the 5th and 6th of October, anomalies in Saudi Arabia on the 20th of October, and anomalies in India from the 26th to the 28th. This client has devices deployed in all the aforementioned countries. Furthermore, our analysis delves into the model's performance for each cluster and individual country. Specifically, we verify with the operation teams the percentage of anomalous devices that we could detect in these eight countries, given several known anomalous incidents. We report our evaluation results in Table 18. Note that results for the Tukey Fences approach, being threshold-based, are similar to the alarms systems already generate. Thus, this approach was not able to detect any of the anomalies presented in Table 18.

We devised various model versions for our study. In the case of Isolation Forest (IF), we explored different contamination levels (i.e., the percentage of devices labeled as anomalous), and present results for specific levels, namely 5% and 10%. This approach enables the detection of instances where a substantial number of devices from a given client exhibit anomalous behavior. Additionally, for all models, we sought to assess the necessity of the clustering step. Therefore, we compared performance against a global model that excludes the clustering step, creating a single model using all available data. The per cluster model utilizes the model associated with the device's mapped cluster. While the clustering step aims to optimize model selection, it may not always be accurate, and some devices might fall on the border between two clusters. To address this, we evaluated a model that employs the model of the cluster where the majority (major cluster) of devices from a given client in a specific country belong. For example, if Client#1 in Spain has 1000 devices mapped to cluster c1, 70 devices mapped to c2, and no devices mapped to any other cluster, we exclusively use the model of c1, for detecting anomalies for this particular client in that specific country. Note that in some cases the majority cluster is not obvious (difference of less than 2%), and the performance can vary (see the case of Client#3 in Table 18).

We find that the IoT devices with anomalies map to clusters c2, c4 and c5, with the vast majority (in the order of thousands of devices) falling in c2 (i.e., devices that are mostly stationary, with 4G LTE connectivity only, and medium volume of dialogues). For cluster c4, we have the lowest number of anomalous devices mapped, with as little as two IoT devices in Spain or Saudi Arabia. The distribution is similar for cluster c5, with the exception of India, where the number of IoT devices with ground-truth anomalies is roughly half of those in c2 (in the order of thousands).

Overall, the Isolation Forest model demonstrates superior performance, particularly on cluster c2, consistently triggering alarms for a significant percentage of affected IoT devices, as indicated by the ground truth dataset. In specific regions, such as the United States and Argentina, Isolation Forest successfully raises alarms for more than 70% and 30% of devices, respectively, for Client#6. This high alarm rate per IoT customer serves as a crucial signal for the operations team to verify the client's connectivity status.

Importantly, the operations team can choose how to respond to ANCHOR's results. For instance, by investigating cases where the model identifies 10% of a client's devices as behaving anomalously, the team could detect 80% of clients with incidents; with a 5% threshold, they could detect 90%, only missing the anomalies of Client#4, where less than 10 devices were behaving anomalously. Surprisingly, GMM outperforms Isolation Forest and FC-VAE for certain clients; however, this trend is more noticeable when dealing with a limited number of ground-truth anomalies (less than ten). We attribute this observation to the stochastic nature of the data. In contrast, Isolation Forest consistently produces

reliable results across different clients and dates. It excels in leveraging the clustering step, particularly in detecting anomalies when using a cluster-specific model. The reason being that in this version we emphasize more on the feature creation than on the model tuning phase to make a more explainable model. Furthermore, in the control client scenario, a client with thousands of devices reported to have no anomalies on the studied day, Isolation Forest stands out by not producing false alarms, unlike GMM and FC-VAE.

3.4.2.2 Summary KPIs

By executing the work in A9, we were able to quantify the following KPIs, which we detail next.

KPI	Results	Justification
K3	<p>For the training time, we observe that values vary between 50 and 400 minutes. For training we leverage a processing instance with 56 cores Intel Xeon E7, 504GB of RAM, and 7 GPUs NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080.</p> <p>The inference time is usually well below the upper bound of ~20 minutes for the largest cluster (1,7M devices).</p> <p>In both inference and training time we do not consider the time it takes to create the features, since this is done automatically by a batch job, and does not represent any overhead. Nevertheless, we do consider the time to transform the metrics (for Isolation Forest we use the <i>StandardScaler</i> transformation), as well as the time to merge the dataset output by the clustering algorithm and the features for the different ML models.</p> <p>For inference, ANCHOR with IF runs in under 1ms for a single device (0.7ms). However, given the particularities of the roaming platform and of the use-case, the engineering teams only verifies the results on a daily basis</p>	<p>For anomaly detection, the industry standard is currently relying on alarm systems or to react to tickets raised by the customers. Because of the complexity of the ecosystem and, consequently, of the anomalies that arise within the roaming platform, these latter come with significant delay, and are usually dealt with on a case-by-case basis. Our solution aims to reduce the reaction time of operating teams to anomalies occurring in the system by integrating NI functionalities for anomaly detection. Eventually, we aim to move towards real-time proactive approaches for anomaly detection</p>
K7	<p>ANCHOR using as a threshold a 10% of a client's devices as behaving anomalously could detect 80% of clients with incidents; with a 5% threshold, ANCHOR could detect 90% of anomalies, achieving the target KPI.</p> <p>Moreover, ANCHOR running LIVE in the roaming platform (as part of a controlled pilot) was able to identify an unknown anomaly that –left unaddressed – would have potentially impacted the roaming agreements between operators</p>	<p>The goal of our solution is to capture anomalies that the currently missed by the alarm systems in place, but otherwise dealt with (and documented) via ticketing systems. We evaluate the performance of the anomaly detection approach based on ground truth anomalies that we collect from the ticketing system of a live roaming platform for IoT managed connectivity</p>

3.4.2.3 Requirement Satisfaction

The empirical results above validate the following set of requirements that we described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-AARES-000	100%	The DEAMON-developed ANCHOR solution demonstrated high detection performance (90%) for anomaly detection for IoT devices in international roaming

3.4.3 Anomaly detection in mobile service traffic at base station level (A25)

This activity evaluates the performance of anticipatory anomaly detection for traffic load in the network. For that, we have designed an NI network function that must trigger an alert in the event of expecting an abnormal future traffic load for a particular mobile service.

The very first solution, which included hybrid approaches, was presented in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.1 [33]. Afterward, we provided the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of Deliverable 2.2 [34], as well as its mapping to major standards, in Section 4.3 of Deliverable 4.2[21]. This solution complies with the full hybrid approach proposed in Section 4.2.4 of D2.2 as a better alternative to pure deep learning AI models commonly used in the literature for network traffic forecasting.

We perform this evaluation on a virtualized network environment running an end-to-end network slicing model. In this use case, proactive load anomaly detection is crucial for the timely identification of unwanted situations and for the preemptive reaction that can be done by, e.g., new network configurations. It is important to note that the anomalous-load detection performed by the NI plane operates at the granularity of individual services. Thus, we consider in the evaluation that there are four different services concurrently being served in the network, where one slice is reserved for each of the four services.

The solution presented by the DAEMON project addressing this problem is named TES-RNN. It was introduced in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.1 [33], where we described the key characteristic of this approach: its hybrid nature, which incorporates both statistical analysis and deep learning structures. This algorithm was first evaluated for capacity forecasting in Section 4.6.1 of Deliverable 5.1 [7].

Regarding anomaly detection performance, we study it through an emulation of the network analytics function of a mobile network, which gathers data from the User Plane Function (UPF) to monitor the excessive network usage by a terminal. In our case, it must generate an alarm if such an event is expected to happen soon. As shown in D5.2, TES-RNN always achieves the best performance, while competitors offer unstable results that depend on the application considered. Finally, TES-RNN always yields the best pairing between the Recall and the false positive rate for all the considered in the range between 30% and 95%.

3.4.3.1 Evaluation

The complete empirical evaluation of this solution was presented in D5.2, Section 4.3.3.

3.4.3.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following main KPI.

KPI	Result	Justification
K7	Improvement of state of the art for any point of the ROC curve (recall vs false positive rate), for a comprehensive range of hyper-parameter values. It also outperforms all the state-of-the-art algorithms for the F-Score and the Relative MSE	We have verified the results by evaluating the algorithms on a dataset from a real nationwide dataset from a commercial network operator (D3). We consider a scenario with four different slices, each one handling a different service provider data. See D5.2 for more details

3.4.3.3 Requirements satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in Deliverable D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.1 on understanding the limits of AI and propose hybrid solutions that can overcome them. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above for this activity indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3] .

3.5 Evaluation of NI for Edge orchestration

In this section, we discuss the conclusive evaluations concerning NI for edge orchestration. Specifically, we discuss Evaluation E4, which discusses NI solutions designed for implementing and deploying the NI-assisted solutions for service orchestration and resource allocation algorithms in the Edge micro-domain. This activity encompasses A10-A17 and A26. Summaries of the tools, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), Proof of Concept (PoC) execution, and primary findings from these activities are provided in Table 19 and expanded in the following subsections.

Table 19. Evaluation results for E4. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	Reached TRL	Testbed / Dataset	Main findings
A10	Video analytics with edge computing	K2	3	D5	This proposed solution, which computes the compression and under-sampling ratio, achieved optimal performance without violating the desired constraints
A11	Multi-timescale edge orchestration	K5, K8	4	T4	The proposed solution demonstrated that the service response time could be improved up to 70% while ensuring a service reliability 99.999% , and ensuring latency below 15ms as requested by the vertical.
A12	WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management	K8	3	D6	The GNN model in our NI solution significantly enhances decision model response times, with up to a 99% improvement. This is largely due to the accelerated performance predictions enabled by data-driven models using advanced hardware, surpassing traditional tools like simulators, emulators, and limited test environments
A13	Data-driven resource orchestration	K5, K8, K9	5	D1a	This solution extracts specific end-user device requirements to enhance resource allocation, particularly for mobile scenarios. It's especially useful for vertical applications relying on global roaming, improving service response times.
A14	Multi-timescale network slice reservation	K4	2	None	This solution has proven theoretically and shown experimentally that our proposed solution reaches very close (or coincides) with the optimal performance.

A15	Testing EnergyEdgeCloudSim	K1, K2, K3	2	S5	Our auto-scaling solution for the edge reduces energy consumption between a 44% and 91%. Reductions on energy consumption directly affect OPEX.
A16	Towards autonomous VNF scaling	K4	3	S1	The resulting auto-scaler as able to save 27% OPEX compared to an oracle that performs overprovisioning. Moreover, the proposed methodology to select the auto-scaler includes both networking and learning metrics, providing a first methodology for RL-based NI autoscalers.
A17	Auto scaling Virtualized RAN caches	K3, K4	2	D9	The proposed solution solved the optimization problem for dynamic cache rental, file caching and user association for wireless edge caching networks in a fashion that maximizes aggregated delay savings and/or ensures servicing fairness across users, while respecting average budget constraint.
A26	Energy-aware VNF orchestration	K1, K2	3	None	The auto-scaling solution has a 92.5% decrease in energy consumption (a failed request rate of up to 0% and reasonable execution times of the auto-scaling process for different problem sizes). EnergyEdgeCloudSim was used to measure the energy and compute savings.

3.5.1 Data-driven resource orchestration in the MNO (A13)

3.5.1.1 Evaluation

The final results for A13 were previously reported in D5.2 (Section 3.4).

3.5.1.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allows to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K5	In Table 26 of D3.2 (Section 3.4) the same vertical (connected cars and associated vehicular services) includes 4 different clusters of requirements, from high mobility and high traffic to low mobility and low traffic.	Our solution extracts the requirements of specific clusters of end-user devices. With these, the operator can make better decisions in terms of resources allocations (e.g., under extreme mobility), thus increasing the network reliability
K8	Figure 54 of the PoC for A13 in D5.2	The clustering approach we proposed is

	shows improvement in vertical response time (e.g., PLT of web content below 10ms) when tailoring the UPF location for inbound roaming users.	specifically useful for vertical applications that might rely on roaming to connect their devices globally. By easily identifying and mapping the requirements of inbound roamers, the radio network operator can improve the vertical service response time significantly.
K9	Depending on the demand from the different clusters, the MNO can use this information to close the optimality gap in terms of the design of its mobile edge computing architecture.	With a clear mapping of end-user devices clusters and their requirements in terms of connectivity, the operator is able to perform a more optimal resources allocation.

3.5.1.3 Requirement Satisfaction

The work we have performed in this activity did not have any associated performance requirements (i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in Deliverable D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]).

This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the need of fine-granular control of the network functions associated specifically with the connected cars IoT vertical. The methodology we developed as part of this activity was integrated directly in the big data platform of an operator with the goal of providing analytics and insights.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.5.2 Energy-aware VNF orchestration (A15/A26)

3.5.2.1 Evaluation

We do not have further details to report regarding these activities. We presented their evaluation activities in Sections 4.4.6 and 4.4.9 of Deliverable 5.2. A15 was introduced in Section 3.2.4 of D5.1, while A26 was presented in Section 3.1.3 of D4.1. Here, we detail the final summary of KPIs and Requirement Satisfaction.

3.5.2.2 Summary KPIs

This activity was completed during Y2; the KPIs below have been validated in D5.2.

KPI	Result	Justification
K1	15.9% reduction in dynamic energy consumption and up to 66.2% in idle energy consumption	We use EnergyEdgeCloudSim to measure the energy and compute energy savings
K2	Same as above	The reduction in energy consumption comes directly from the savings on energy consumption

3.5.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

The empirical results presented in D5.2, Section 4.4.6, and 4.4.9 allow us to validate the requirements described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-EAWVNF-002	100%	The auto-scaling solution has a 92.5% decrease in energy consumption (a failed request rate of up to 0% and reasonable execution times of the auto-scaling process for different problem sizes)
NFR-EAWVNF-006	100%	The energy-aware orchestrator and the ENI module include the expected performance as a constraint to reduce energy consumption without compromising throughput

3.5.3 Multi-timescale network slice reservation (A14)

In this section, we present the results of the evaluation of the proposed fairness framework, described in Section 4.5 of deliverable D3.3 [5]. We target a representative resource management problem in virtualized caching systems where different caches cooperate by serving jointly the received content request. Although the static version of this problem has been studied in the literature, we investigate the more realistic version of it, where request patterns are unknown and fairness metrics are considered.

3.5.3.1 Evaluation

We consider three synthetic network topologies (Cycle, Tree, and Grid), and two real network topologies (Abilene and GEANT). A repository node permanently stores the entire catalog of files. The retrieval costs along the edges are sampled u.a.r. from $\{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$, except for edges directly connected to a repository node which are sampled u.a.r. from $\{6, 7, \dots, 10\}$. All the retrieval costs remain fixed for every $t \in T$. The capacity of each cache is sampled u.a.r. from $\{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$, but for the Cycle topology in which each cache has capacity 5. An agent $i \in I$ has a set of query nodes denoted by $Q_i \subset \Gamma_i(C)$, and a query node can generate a batch of requests from a catalog with $|F| = 20$ files. Unless otherwise said, we consider $u_{min} = 0.1$ and $u_{max} = 1$. Each query node generates requests according to the following two scenarios: (i) Stationary trace, where the requests are sampled i.i.d. from a Zipf distribution and (ii) Non-Stationary trace, where the requests are sampled i.i.d. from a catalog of F files according to a Zipf distribution, but every D requests, the popularity distribution is modified in the following fashion: file $f \in F = \{1, 2, \dots, F\}$ assumes the popularity of file $f' = (f + \frac{F}{2}) \bmod F$ (F is even). We implement (i) LRU, (ii) LFU and (iii) Online slot-fairness (OSF) as benchmarks to our algorithm OHF.

We start with a numerical investigation of the potential caching gains, and how these are affected by the fairness parameter. In Figure 59, we consider the Cycle topology and different values of $\alpha \in [0, 2]$. We show the impact on the fairness benchmark of varying the request patterns ($\sigma \in \{0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2\}$) for agent 2 under the Stationary trace in Figure 59(a), and of varying the retrieval costs between agent 1's cache and the repository ($w_{(1,3)} \in [2.5, 4]$). In Figure 59(a), we observe decreasing the skewness of the popularity distribution decreases the utility of agent 2 as reflected by the downward shift of the Pareto front. We note that, as far as the file popularity distribution at agent 2 is close to the one at agent 1 ($\sigma = 1.2$), different values of alpha still provide similar utilities. However, in highly asymmetric scenarios, different values of α lead to clearly distinct utilities for each agent. Similarly, in Figure 59(b), we observe increasing the retrieval cost for agent 1 decreases the utility achieved by the same agent, as reflected by the leftward shift of the Pareto front; moreover, increasing the retrieval costs (higher asymmetry) highlights the difference between different values of α .

Figure 60. Pareto front and fairness benchmark's utilities for different values of α under different request patterns (a) for agent 2, and different retrieval costs (b) between agent 1's cache and the repository.

In Figure 60(a)–(c), we observe for increasing the number of agents, the division of utilities differs between the fairness benchmark and utilitarian benchmark; moreover, this difference is more evident for larger values of α . Figure 60(d) provides the price of fairness, and we observe the price of fairness increases with the number of agents and α . Nonetheless, under the different settings the price of fairness remains below 4%, i.e., we experience at most a 4% drop in the social welfare to provide fair utility distribution across the different agents. Figure 61 gives the time-averaged utilities obtained by running OHF for $\alpha = 2$. We observe the utilities obtained by OHF quickly converge to the same utilities obtained by the fairness benchmark.

In Figure 62(a), we consider the network topologies Tree, Grid, Abilene, GEANT under Stationary trace ($\sigma \in \{0.6, 1.0, 1.2\}$) and $\alpha = 3$. OHF achieves the same utilities as the fairness benchmark across the different topologies. Note that for larger network topologies agents achieve a higher utility because there are more resources available. In Figure 62(b), we consider the Cycle topology and $\alpha = 3$. The query node of agent 1 generates Non-Stationary trace, while the query node of agent 2 generates a shuffled Non-Stationary trace. Therefore, on average the agents are symmetric and experience the same utilities. Also, we note that indeed this is the case for OHF policy; however, because OSF aims to insure fairness across the different timeslots the agents are not considered symmetric and the average utilities deviate from the Pareto front (not efficient).

Figure 61. Subfigures (a)–(c) provide the average utility for different agents obtained by OHF, fairness benchmark (OPT for $\alpha \neq 0$), and utilitarian benchmark (OPT for $\alpha = 0$); and Subfigure (d) provides the PoF for $\alpha \in \{0,1,2,3\}$ under an increasing number of agents in $\{2,3,4\}$ and Tree 1–3 topology.

Figure 62. Subfigures (a)–(c) provide the time-averaged utility across different agents obtained by OHF policy and OPT for $\alpha = 2$ under an increasing number of agents in $\{2,3,4\}$ and Tree 1–3 topology.

Figure 63. Subfigure (a) provides the average utility of OHF and fairness benchmark under network topologies Tree, Grid, Abilene, GEANT, and Stationary trace. Subfigure (b) provides the time-averaged utilities obtained for OHF, OSF under network topology Tree (a) and Non-stationary trace.

3.5.3.2 Summary of KPIs

The following table showcases the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K9	100%	We have proven theoretically and shown experimentally that our proposed solution reaches very close (or coincides) with the optimal performance; please refer to Section 3.5.2.1

3.5.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in Deliverable D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.2 on designing loss functions that are tailored to the networking context. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above for this activity indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions. The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.5.4 Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs (A10)

In this section, we present the results of the evaluation of the proposed algorithm, described in Section 3.5 of deliverable D3.3 [5]. We have implemented the proposed architecture in a small wireless testbed using 4 Raspberry Pis, which we also leveraged to create synthetic traces to run additional large-scale simulations. The evaluation of OnAlgo was conducted using images from two publicly available datasets of images and compared against benchmarks from previous works.

3.5.4.1 Evaluation

Testbed and Measurements. Our work focuses on image classification, and for that reason, we use two of the most well-known datasets: i) MNIST which consists of 28×28-pixel handwritten digits and includes 60K training and 10K test examples; and (ii) CIFAR-10 that consists of 50K training and 10K test examples of 32×32 color images of 10 classes. We employed two different classifiers, (i) the normalized-distance weighted k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm, and (ii) the more sophisticated Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), implemented with TensorFlow. Both of them output the probability that the object belongs to the respective class, and our goal is to discern the best. We used 4 Raspberry Pis (RPs) as end-nodes which are placed in different distances from the cloudlet. We measured energy using a Monsoon Power Monitor and used Python libraries and TensorFlow for the classifiers. Finally, we run at least 50 independent experiments for our results.

Evaluation Results. First, we present an evaluation of the different classifiers. We observe that in Figure 63(a), the accuracy of the KNN classifier improves with the size of labeled data when applied to MNIST. In Figure 63(b), it can be derived that the accuracy for CNN is improving with more hidden layers. Notice that the performance of the CNN classifier is superior to KNN, when we use fewer layers, or samples respectively. Lastly, we present the CNN performance on CIFAR, for 1, 2 and 4 hidden layers in Figure 63(c). CIFAR is more complex than MNIST due to the properties of its objects and this results in lower accuracy. Overall, we see that the classifier performance depends on the algorithm (KNN, CNN, etc.), the settings (datasets, layers, etc.), and differ also for each object class.

Figure 64. Accuracy achieved per class for KNN and CNN classifiers on MNIST and CIFAR-10, for various labeled data sizes and hidden layers.

Moreover, we evaluate our proposed algorithm, OnAlgo, for non-i.i.d. traffic load to compare its performance against Accuracy-Threshold Offloading (ATO), Resource-Consumption Offloading (RCO), and Online Code Offloading and Scheduling (OCOS) from the literature. To emulate real-world scenarios of sensor-activated cameras, the traffic load is an exponentially distributed sequence of task

bursts, with a uniform duration of 5 to 10 seconds. Therefore, we compare OnAlgo to the previous competitors using the criterion of accuracy and power consumption. We use two scenarios to demonstrate the algorithms' performance and energy costs under different datasets and resource availability states.

In Scenario 1 (low accuracy improvement; high resources), we demonstrate the average accuracy achieved by the devices and the average power consumption versus the task load in bursts per minute in Figure 64(a) and Figure 64(b) respectively. We observe that OnAlgo shows a smaller slope in the decrease of accuracy, as the load increases than all the competitors. It is interesting also to note that RCO outperforms OnAlgo by around 2% in terms of accuracy, but it uses more than twice the energy. In Scenario 2 (high accuracy improvement; low resources), we used the CIFAR dataset that demonstrates a substantial performance difference between local and cloudlet classifiers. We see from Figure 64(c) that OnAlgo outperforms ATO/RCO by up to 12% for high task load. OnAlgo consumes about half the power than OCOS since the latter always tries to offload tasks but does not leverage the cloudlet efficiently due to the lack of computing capacity. Given that the potential improvement is larger in Scenario 2, ATO slightly surpasses RCO by using up to 50% additional power compared to RCO, as illustrated in Figure 64(d); meanwhile, OnAlgo uses roughly 50% less power than OCOS, which consistently does not success in offloading tasks due to insufficient computing resources.

Figure 65. Comparison of different offloading algorithms with respect to their accuracy and energy cost, under different task load conditions

By leveraging net graphs, we show the trade-offs between number of offloadings, accuracy and resource consumption between OnAlgo and the competitor algorithms. Figure 65(a) displays the performance of OnAlgo for low medium and high task load. Observe that as the load increases, OnAlgo rapidly increases resource consumption to maintain high accuracy. In Figure 65(b), we compare the same metrics for high traffic load, and the different competitors. Note that OnAlgo attains the topmost accuracy levels, ranking as the second most efficient (just after RCO) regarding computing resources and energy usage. Furthermore, it secures this high accuracy with less frequent offloading compared to OCOS, thanks to its intelligent approach to making these choices.

Figure 66. Comparison of different key metrics (normalized): (a) On-Algo for low, medium and high traffic load. (b) Algorithm comparison for high load in scenario 2.

3.5.4.2 Summary of KPIs

The following table showcases the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	100%	Our algorithmic approach is focused on reducing the computational resources (up to 50%) required at the edge, as described in Section 3.5.4.1

3.5.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

The following table shows the set of requirements we have successfully validated with the results presented above.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-CAWRS-001	100%	The proposed algorithm was proved to respect the reconfiguration time set by the user
NFR-CAWRS-002	100%	The proposed algorithm was proved to achieve an asymptotically diminishing performance gap with the optimal radio/computing optimization decisions. Namely, the difference in utility and the norm of the constraint satisfaction vector both diminish to 0 with time. Hence, the algorithm fulfills the bounded distance from the optimal requirement

3.5.5 Towards autonomous VNF scaling (A16)

3.5.5.1 Evaluation

In Section 6.2 of D4.2 [21] and [35], we proposed two Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) models for providing auto-scaling capabilities to any network whose architecture is service-based, e.g., Network Function Virtualization (NFV) networks and Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN). Assuming the availability of multiple Reinforcement Learning (RL) models for deployment, trained with different Reward Functions (RFNs), we incorporate best practices for algorithm comparison and selection. Typically, the lifecycle management of the Machine Learning (ML) models is handled through a Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) framework. However, most of the MLOps implementations predominantly focus on Supervised Learning (SL), often neglecting comprehensive support for RL algorithms [36].

Consequently, we propose a methodology for designing, training, validating, and selecting RL-based algorithms for autoscaling. We enhance the MLOps methodology by incorporating practices for algorithm selection and comparison. In contrast to prior methodologies such as MLOps[37], RLOps [36], Q-Model [38] and O-RAN workflows [39], our approach considers multiple RL models tailored to a specific problem. Furthermore, these diverse RL models are configured with different RFNs introducing an additional challenge as we aim to optimize the lifecycle management for not just one but multiple algorithms. In the following, we detail the changes that our methodology proposes for the training, validation, and selection stages of the MLOps workflow.

3.5.5.1.1 Training

Once the appropriate RL algorithms and RFNs tailored to the problem have been selected, the next step in their lifecycle is to develop the autonomous agent. This is commonly known as training. Following the recommendations from the O-RAN alliance, RL algorithms should be trained offline [39]. Offline training in networking can be performed in a Network Digital Twin (NDT)[40], where the outcomes of the untrained agents can be safely injected without compromising the stability of the production network [41]. The environment proposed in Section 6.2.1.3 of D4.3 [3] can serve as a NDT for the proposed use case.

A major challenge in the RL community is that minor implementation details can considerably impact performance, sometimes surpassing the disparity between various algorithms [42]. Ensuring the reliability of implementations employed as experimental baselines is paramount. Otherwise, comparing novel algorithms to unreliable baselines may result in inflated estimates of performance enhancements. Thus, standard, open-source frameworks that provide reliable implementations of RL algorithms are recommended [43],[44].

To compare the performance of the different RL algorithms, we follow the guidelines suggested by Colas et al.[45], [46]. In their paper, the authors suggest (i) obtaining the measure of performance of every agent to plot the learning curves of the algorithms, (ii) performing statistical difference testing, (iii) comparing the full learning curves not only comparing the final performances of the two algorithms after t steps in the environment.

Taking those recommendations into account, we extend the current methodological proposals for lifecycle management of RL applications in software-based architectures to support algorithmic comparison and selection. We summarize this extension into the methodology shown in Figure 66.

At least five different agents should be implemented initially. Each agent is trained using episodes, where an episode is defined as the number of steps until the simulation must be restarted or a maximum number of steps is reached. Accordingly, we determined two situations where an episode is terminated: when the agent creates more replicas than needed or lets the latency go above an

inadmissible threshold. These two situations represent an undesired agent behavior and must be penalized. In such situations, the episode ends, the agent receives -100 of reward, and the simulation is restarted. After the simulation is restarted, the initial scenario is again deployed.

If what happens in an actual second in every step is simulated, we chose one-hour episodes. Thus, the maximum number of steps is 3600. Notice that the episode length may vary during training since, at the beginning of the training, the agent is expected to take random actions, which can easily lead to episode termination due to undesired behavior. After the agent is trained during N episodes, we freeze its policy and evaluate it during V episodes. Following the logic of Supervised Learning (SL) approaches, we split the workload trace into two, one for training and another for evaluation, aiming to test the generalization capabilities of the algorithms to unseen data. The training trace uses the workload's first $432 \cdot 10^3$ values, while the evaluation trace uses the last $172.8 \cdot 10^3$ values. Training and evaluating the agent is considered an epoch; we repeat the process during E epochs.

Generally, the values of N , V , and E should be selected by trading off training time and the agent's performance. The agent's performance should be evaluated as soon as possible, which implies selecting a lower training time, i.e., lower N , but ensuring enough training is reflected in improving the agent's behavior. Moreover, a larger V gives a better estimation of the true agent's performance but, at the same time, slows down the training. Following this trade-off, we selected the values for N , V , and E for all RFns and RL algorithm combinations. The values are shown in Table 20.

Table 20. Parameters used in the experimental evaluation.

Parameter	Value
Steps per episode	3600
Episodes in training mode, N	24
Episodes in evaluation mode V	12
Epochs E	10
d_{tgt}	20 ms
c_{tgt}	75%
ϵ	20%

At the end of an evaluation episode, we record the accumulated reward of the episode. Then, the performance per epoch is the average earned reward over the V episodes. To provide a fair comparison of the performance of the algorithms among the different RFns, all the RFns must be in the same range. Min-Max normalization can be applied to normalize the range of different RFns.

Once each agent's and run's performance were calculated, we performed statistical difference testing as a main way to compare their performance. In particular, we completed the Welch t-test on the data since it was more robust than other tests to the violation of their assumptions [46].

3.5.5.1.2 Validation

Once trained and evaluated, the performance of all the scalars is assessed. This performance can be evaluated from two perspectives: how well the agent learns and how well the agent performs the task at hand. For this purpose, we tested the learned policy in deterministic mode after the E epochs of training by letting the agent run a validation episode of $172.8 \cdot 10^3$ steps. We gathered the accumulated reward the agents received at the end of the validation episode and the main statistical figures of the number of created replicas and the latency. Depending on the obtained values, we score all the agents using the Equations below.

$$score\ learning = \frac{normalized\ accumulated\ reward}{normalized\ episode\ length}$$

$$score\ networking = w_v \cdot V' + w_d \cdot D'$$

$$V' = 1 - \frac{\bar{v} - min}{max - min}$$

$$D' = \frac{\bar{d}}{max}$$

Figure 67. Proposed methodology, extending the current MLOps frameworks to support RL algorithms, in order to increase reliability of RL implementations.

The first equation scores the agents regarding the learning perspective. The episode termination cases should be avoided if the agent is well-trained. If these cases do not occur, the agent maintains the simulation running, and the episode length is the largest it could be, i.e., $172.8 \cdot 10^3$ steps. Then, using a min-max scaler, the normalized length of a testing episode should be 1, and the score should be approximately the same as the normalized reward achieved during training. Suppose the agent falls into the episode termination cases. In that case, the validation episode is finalized before time, where the normalized episode length is lower than one, forcing the score to be higher than one. In this case, the agent can be discarded since it is unacceptable.

The second equation scores the agents regarding the networking perspective in terms of the number of created replicas and the fulfillment of the Service Level Agreement (SLA) expressed in terms of the processing latency. The goal of a scaler is to fulfill the SLA with the minimum number of replicas needed. Then, to compare how an agent performs over the remaining agents, we need to also apply normalization. For the number of replicas, we use min-max normalization as expressed in the second equation, where \bar{v} is the average number of replicas created during the validation episode, min , and max , are the minimum and maximum values of all the created agents. We used inverse normalization since the min-max normalization would return values close to zero when \bar{v} approaches the minimum.

Similarly, the fourth equation normalizes the latency. By using only the maximum latency value, this equation is able to identify how far this maximum is from its mean value. The closer to one, the distribution is more centered around the mean, while the closer to zero, the distribution presents a right-hand side tail. This type of normalization is handy for detecting extreme peak values in the latency

distribution [47] which should be avoided in mission-critical applications, for instance. Notice that, while the min , max , in the previous equation should select the minimum (or maximum) between all the created agents, the max , in the fourth equation corresponds to the maximum latency value of each agent during the validation episode. This value is associated with the latency distribution of the agent itself, and therefore it is irrelevant to compare it against other agents.

Being V' the normalized value of the replicas created by a given agent and D' the normalized latency of a given agent, the score networking equation tries to find a balance between the two main objectives of the scaler. w_v and w_d are weights used to tune which of the two criteria is more important to the Network Service Provider (NSP). Moreover, the equations are chosen depending on the service type that the Network Function (NF) is providing. For instance, if the application allows the users to experiment some extreme latency issues, then the normalized latency could be replaced by another equation, e.g., \bar{d}/d_{tgt} measures how far are the mean latency values from the target. After all the agents have been scored, model selection can start.

3.5.5.1.3 Selection

Model selection is a filtering process in which all the agents that were not able to perform in a plausible way during the previous two stages are ruled out. The first step in this process is to discard all the agents whose learning score is not similar to the measure of performance obtained during the training. As explained above, a well-trained agent is able to maintain the running of the validation episode; if this is not the case, the learning score will be higher than the measure of performance, indicating a possible outlier. Such agents should undergo model refinement, by, e.g., changing the seed. We filter first by the learning score since an ill-trained agent is most likely to have a poor performance in the scaling task.

Then, by using the networking score, we select the best scoring agent per reward function. Ultimately, the agent's true performance is given in terms of the networking Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and not the reward the agent achieves during training. The chosen agent must satisfy two criteria: firstly, its learning score should rank among the highest within its respective RFn; secondly, if there exists statistical evidence demonstrating higher performance of one algorithm over another, the highest-performing agent should be trained using the algorithm proven to be more effective. If at least one of the criteria is met, the agent with the highest learning score should be deployed. In case none of the criteria is met, the agents should undergo model refinement, by either increasing the number of agent-environment interactions or by redesigning RFn.

3.5.5.1.4 Experimental evaluation of the methodology

Using the procedure described in previous subsections, we trained and validated the algorithms of Section 6.2.1.1 of D4.3 [3] using the RFn described in Section 6.2.1.2 of the same deliverable. The scores of each run for each algorithm and RFn are shown in Table 21 and Table 22. Regarding the learning score, we observe in Table 21, the cases where this score is above 1, highlighted in red. Such cases are immediately discarded and are not scored using the networking score equation. According to the methodology introduced in the previous subsections (see Figure 66), such agents can be replaced by others by changing the seed, for instance. Besides that fact, for most cases, the learning score corresponds to the stabilizing value of the normalized reward in their learning curves. In general, the learning score of the agents per RFn and algorithm is similar, which leads us to think that the algorithms can find an akin policy independently of their weight initialization.

Table 21. Learning score of all the individual runs. In red are highlighted the cases where the agents terminated the validation episode before time.

	DQN					PPO				
	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5
RFn 1	0.9971	0.9999	0.998	0.9999	0.9999	0.7462	0.7427	0.6765	0.6976	0.7529
RFn 2	0.5662	0.5565	0.5521	0.5629	0.5598	0.3777	0.3784	0.3781	0.3784	0.3852
RFn 3_1	0.6666	0.6666	0.6666	0.6666	0.6666	246.7	0.6581	1.522	0.6567	0.6588
RFn 3_2	0.4975	22.28	0.4975	0.4975	0.4975	1.181	768.0	340.3	594.4	22.18
RFn 3_3	43.92	0.9901	0.9901	0.9901	0.9901	0.9901	0.9901	0.984	0.9894	0.989

Regarding the networking performance, as depicted in Table 22, agents that were eliminated in the previous stage are denoted with a red dash, while those with the highest scores per RFn are highlighted in green. Similar to Table 20, scoring is consistent among agents trained with the same RFn. However, our two-step approach, as outlined in our methodology, enables the identification of the most suitable model for deployment.

Table 22. Networking score of all the individual runs. The red dash identifies the agents disregarded in the previous stage, while in green are shown the best-performing agents per RFn.

	DQN					PPO				
	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5
RFn 1	0.4142	0.4467	0.4166	0.4591	0.4567	0.4525	0.4519	0.4496	0.4444	0.4513
RFn 2	0.5219	0.5225	0.5265	0.4472	0.4455	0.4867	0.4968	0.4883	0.5005	0.4931
RFn 3_1	0.4499	0.5062	0.4999	0.4774	0.4736	-	0.3886	-	0.4193	0.3894
RFn 3_2	0.8695	-	0.7842	0.8863	0.8873	-	-	-	-	-
RFn 3_3	-	0.3026	0.2577	0.3462	0.3977	0.4416	0.4630	0.4190	0.4289	0.3844

For instance, suppose we adhere to the conventional method of selecting the agent with the highest accumulated reward. In that scenario, agents 2, 4, and 5 of the DQN utilizing RFn1 could all be considered viable options. Nevertheless, upon closer examination of their scores, it becomes apparent that agent 2 slightly underperforms compared to the others. Furthermore, as illustrated in Table 22, PPO agents demonstrate better-than-anticipated performance, contrary to expectations based solely on their learning scores.

Combining both tables reveals that, in certain instances, assumptions based on learning scores align with evidence from networking scores. For example, agents trained with RFn1 consistently outperform PPO agents in both learning and networking. Similar trends are observed in RFn2. In the case of RFn3_1, although both algorithms exhibit similar learning performance, DQN demonstrates clear superiority over PPO in networking. Conversely, in RFn3_3, while all agents exhibit similar learning scores, networking scores indicate better performance by PPO agents for this specific function.

In the final selection phase, we identify the top-performing agents as follows: (i) DQN Run 4 for RFn1, (ii) DQN Run 3 for RFn2, (iii) DQN Run 2 for RFn 3_1, (iv) DQN Run 5 for RFn 3_2, and (v) PPO Run 2 for RFn3_3. As suggested by our methodology, the next step is to we check if all the agents meet the criteria for deployment.

Firstly, the learning score criterion ensures that the chosen agents rank among the highest within their respective RFns. From Table 21 and Table 22 only DQN Run 4 with RFn1 and PPO Run 2 with RFn3_3 achieve high scores in both learning and networking. Furthermore, during the training phase, the DQN agents trained with RFn1 consistently demonstrated superior performance compared to PPO agents, validating the selection of DQN Run 4 for deployment. Table 23 summarizes the behavior of this agent in terms of replicas and latency control.

Table 23. Main Statistical values of Run 4 of the DQN using RFn1.

	Replicas	Latency (s)
mean	5.0771	0.0089
std	1.1276	0.0004
min	2.0000	0.0058
25%	5.0000	0.0087
50%	5.0000	0.0089
75%	6.0000	0.0090
max	9.0000	0.0612

3.5.5.2 Summary KPIs

The following table shows the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results presented above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K4	The resulting agent is able to save 27% OPEX compared to an oracle that performs overprovisioning	The methodology proposed in this section allows the comparison and selection of scaling algorithms considering two perspectives, learning and networking. Regarding the networking perspective, the score focuses on the algorithms that minimize the extreme latency values, which should be avoided in mission-critical applications. After proper formulation as an MDP, the selected algorithm minimizes the number of SLA violations while keeping the number of replicas

		<p>under control, which saves OPEX compared to a traditional solution (overprovisioning).</p> <p>Assuming an oracle scaling agent that has perfect information of the incoming workload, this agent creates maximum 7 replicas.</p> <p>Additionally, assuming that as scaling strategy, there is overprovisioning (to avoid risks), the selected agent is able to reduce the OPEX by 27%. This also assuming a unitary cost for each replica created during the lifespan of the experiment</p>
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3.5.5.3 Requirements satisfaction

The following table shows the set of requirements that are successfully validated with the results above.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-MTERM-001	100%	The algorithms proposed for intelligent scaling belong to the operation and orchestration procedures. Moreover, the methodology allows the autonomic algorithm selection which is one fundamental operation in the lifecycle management of the NI
NFR-SLMANO-001	100%	The methodology takes into account not only the performance of the algorithm at the scaling task but also looks at their learning process, including also practices recommended by the RL community which ensures the reproducibility of RL algorithms
NFR-NIP-009	100%	The methodology proposed in this section allows the implementation of a procedure for algorithm selection, an important step in the lifecycle management of the NI

3.5.6 WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management (A12)

3.5.6.1 Evaluation

The complete empirical evaluation of this solution was presented in D5.1, Section 4.3.

3.5.6.2 Summary KPIs

The following table shows the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results presented in D5.1, Section 4.3 and D5.2, Section 4.4.3.

KPI	Result	Justification
K8	The GNN model allows to improve in 99% the response time of a decision model	See D5.2, Section 4.4.3
K5	The KPI was not experimentally validated	See D5.2, Section 4.4.3

3.5.6.3 Requirements satisfaction

The following table shows the set of requirements that are successfully validated with the results presented in D5.1, Section 4.3 and D5.2, Section 4.4.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-MTERM-003	100%	The created NIF uses standard frameworks for development and implementation. Moreover, the GNN model can be easily extrapolated to other technologies besides Wi-Fi
NFR-MTERM-002	100%	As shown in D3.2, section 3.2.5, the GNN model can be easily mapped to reference architectural frameworks, e.g., ITU architectural framework for machine learning in future network systems, including IMT-2020 [48]

3.5.7 Multi-timescale edge orchestration (A11)

3.5.7.1 Evaluation

The complete evaluation of this solution is presented in D5.2, Section 4.4.2. The evaluation summarizes the performance of two algorithms that trigger edge service relocation. The first algorithm is a simple rule-based algorithm that makes a decision to relocate service based on the current CPU load on the source edge computing node. The second one is more sophisticated, as it proactively selects a new target node to which the observed edge service should be relocated in order to maintain/achieve the required service response time (end-to-end latency).

3.5.7.2 Summary KPIs

Three KPIs were evaluated in the context of multi-timescale edge orchestration solution, and as such they are summarized in the table below.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	CPU values mapped to vertical service response time, ranging from 2% to 70%	The CPU load of the edge computing node where the edge service is running. The experiment increased the awareness of CPU load and how such a load impacts the vertical response time (K8). The detailed results presented in Deliverable D5.2, Section 4.4.2
K5	99.999%	Service reliability in the context of multi-timescale edge orchestration is defined as a ratio of served and received requests at the edge service. The detailed results presented in Deliverable 5.2, Section 4.4.2
K8	Values maintained below 15ms due to the optimized orchestration decisions	Vertical response is the average response time of the edge service that is serving the user, i.e., the end-to-end latency capturing the communication between user and edge server, including the processing time on the edge. The detailed results presented in Deliverable 5.2, Section 4.4.2

3.5.7.3 Requirements satisfaction

The following table shows the requirements that we successfully validated with the proposed solution.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-MTERM-001	100%	The solution in Section 3.1 of D3.2, our solution uses OSM on top of Kubernetes, which covers the most basic orchestration operations
NFR-MTERM-002	100%	Our solution uses OSM, which is an implementation of the standardize framework for ETSI MEC and ETSI NFV MANO
NFR-MTERM-003	100%	Our solutions is composed of functionalities developed as containers following a cloud-based approach, facilitating modularity and reusability

3.5.8 Auto scaling Virtualised RAN caches (A17)

3.5.8.1 Evaluation

In Section 4.4.8 of Deliverable 5.2 [1], we presented the evaluation of our proposed elastic femtocaching algorithm, devised for maximizing the performance of vRANs, while respecting the monetary budget spent when leasing cache capacity. No updates are reported in this Deliverable.

3.5.8.2 Summary KPIs

The following table showcases the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K3	100%	We formulated an optimization problem for dynamic cache rental, file caching and user association for wireless edge caching networks in a fashion that maximizes aggregated delay savings and/or ensures servicing fairness across users, while respecting average budget constraint (please see Section 4.4.8 of Deliverable 5.2 [1])
K4	100%	Follows from the explanation of K3 above.

3.5.8.3 Requirement satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in deliverable D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.1 on understanding the limits of AI. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Still, the evaluation presented above for this activity indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.6 Evaluation of NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning

Evaluation E6 focuses on the evaluation of NI solutions for long-timescale operations, i.e., MANO, VNF placement and the associated resource allocation. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E6 via activities A20, A21, A22, A27, A31 and A32. Table 24 summarizes the tools, KPIs, TRL, main innovations of such activities.

Table 24. Evaluation results for E6. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project. New activities are indicated as such.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	Reached TRL	Testbed / Dataset	Main findings
A20	Anticipatory capacity allocation	K2, K4	3	D3	Anticipatory provisioning of network resources to individual network slice to avoid underprovisioning while minimizing the unnecessary allocation of resources
A21	Virtual Machine reservation	K2, K9	3	D3	Prediction of the number of VMs that need to be allocated in advance to each NSSI, so as to run the VNFs required to serve the demand generated by the corresponding mobile service
A22	Minimisation of video streaming slice OPEX	K4, K9	3	D3	Minimisation of the monetary OPERating EXPenses (OPEX) associated to running the video streaming slices at the network Edge
A27	Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing	K9	3	D9	Online learning-based network management using forecasting models (or predictions)
A31 (new)	Anticipatory admission control and resource allocation for network slicing with overbooking	K2, K4	3	D3	Admission control of network slices based on predictive analysis of future traffic demands and anticipatory provisioning of network resources to network slices to avoid underprovisioning while minimizing the unnecessary allocation of resources
A32 (new)	Anticipatory meta-learned capacity allocation with	K2, K4	3	D3	Reduction of the cost of anticipatory admission control and resource allocation of network slices

	overbooked admission control for network slicing without a priori knowledge				by up to 40%. Reduction of SLA violations below 0.5% of time, simultaneously decreasing the computational cost and increasing the profit
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Overall, the results of these activities have proven the potential of anticipatory resource allocation and self-configuration based on anticipatory learning.

3.6.1 Anticipatory capacity allocation (A20)

This activity focuses on a capacity forecasting scenario, where the anticipatory NI function is responsible of allocating network resources (e.g., compute, transport, or memory resources) to each one of the network slices present in the corresponding section of the network. The critical trade-off to be considered here is that of ensuring no underestimation of required resources, which would cause a disruption of the end user service and a possible violation of Service Level Agreements with service providers and slice requesters, while minimizing any overprovisioning that would freeze unnecessary resources, preventing those resources to be used for other slices or elements of the network.

The solution presented by the DAEMON project addressing this problem is named TES-RNN. It was introduced in Section 4.1 of D4.1 [33], where its full hybrid approach incorporating both statistical analysis and deep learning structures was described. The outcome of the application of TES-RNN in the proposed scenario was described in Section 4.6.1 of D5.1 [7], where it was shown that it can outperform the capacity forecasting performance of state-of-the-art solutions, providing also an in-depth analysis of a prediction instance and proving that TES-RNN is flexible and allows us to control the SLA violations and the operation point in the trade-off between SLA violations and overprovisioning. We also provided in Section 3.1 of D4.2 [21] the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of D2.2 [34], as well as its mapping to major standards. Indeed, TES-RNN complies with the full hybrid approach proposed in Section 4.2.4 of D2.2 as a better alternative to pure deep learning AI models commonly used in the literature for network traffic forecasting. We refer to the previous deliverables mentioned for a more detailed description of the methods and results. In the analysis presented in Section 4.6.1 of D5.1 we showed that TES-RNN provided gains up to 25% over state-of-the-art forecasting methods particularly designed for the target problem in practical application use cases characterized by real-world traffic volumes and dynamics. These foundations motivated further research on hybrid approaches to NI design, and, in fact, led to the development of Activity A25, which was presented in Section 4.3.3 of D5.2 [1].

3.6.1.1 Evaluation

The complete empirical evaluation of this solution was presented in D5.1, Section 4.6.1, and D5.2, Section 4.3.3, and contextualized in Section 4.5.1 of D5.2.

3.6.1.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented in D5.1 and D5.2 allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	29-50% savings per server	We have verified through a data-driven evaluation with a real nationwide dataset from a commercial network operator. We corroborated that the proposed solution requires less resources to be computed with respect to previous state-of-the-art solutions. We showed in D5.2 that the required complexity (mean training time) is reduced by 50% for two different use cases. See D5.2 for more details
K4	29-50% savings per server	The solution proposed by the consortium is able to reduce the Mean Square Error (MSE) of the traffic forecast by at least 30%, peaking at 50% for some services. See D5.1 for more details

3.6.1.3 Requirements satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.1 on *understanding the limits of AI*. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Yet, the evaluation presented above in Section 3.6.1.2 indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.6.2 Virtual Machine Reservation (A21)

This activity targets a capacity forecasting use case intended for a core network datacenter. In the situation in which different video streaming services (or, more generally, any service provider) are assigned individual and dedicated Network Slice Subnet Instances (NSSI), the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) that is responsible of the datacenter resources control must predict the number of Virtual Machines (VMs) required for each NSSI in advance, such that all the required VNFs can be deployed to serve the demand generated by the corresponding service. Naturally, it is desirable that only the strictly necessary set of VMs is reserved for each NSSI to reduce unnecessary costs. In this scenario, we develop a suitable NI to manage VM reservations to accommodate future demands for each NSSI/service.

The solution presented by the DAEMON project addressing this problem is coined LossLeaP, for Loss Learning Predictor. It was introduced in Section 4.2 of D4.1 where we show how LossLeaP is able to learn the implicit (and partially unknown to the operator) operating costs of the datacenter and the local VM management strategies. The outcome of the application of LossLeaP in the proposed scenario was described in Section 4.6.2 of D5.1 where it was shown that LossLeaP is substantially more efficient and precise than even a fine-tuned decision-making policy based on a legacy prediction. We also provided in Section 3.2 of D4.2 the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of D2.2, as well as its mapping to major standards. Indeed, LossLeaP comply with the guidelines from Section 4.1 of D2.2 in terms of adaptation of legacy AI models to the specificities of real-world NI problems, and the proposed solution overcomes the common loss-metric mismatch in a fully automated way, in alignment with the strategy outlined in Section 4.1.3 of D2.2. The experiments were performed with traffic demands for each video streaming service from Dataset D3 described in Section 3.3 of this document and in Section 3.3.3 of D5.1. We refer to the mentioned deliverables for a more detailed description of the methods and results.

The significant gains provided by this solution (achieving with a 4x – 20x reduction of SLA violations), motivates us to extend the refinement of the design of loss-learning architectures for NI to use them to other different NI use cases, and these new results are planned to appear in the next project deliverables.

3.6.2.1 Evaluation

The complete empirical evaluation of this solution was presented in Section 4.6.2 of D5.1 and contextualized in Section 4.5.2 of D5.2.

3.6.2.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	29-50% savings per server	We evaluated the KPIs through data-driven evaluation in a simulated environment. The data is obtained from a nationwide operator. The proposed solution reduces the cost of anticipatory reservation of VM by 40% (cf. Section 4.6.2 of D5.1 [7]). Consequently, the solution reduces the computational resources required at the edge
K9	0.5% (<1%)	The solution proposed by the consortium is able to reduce the SLA violations below 0.5% of the time, while also reducing the computational cost

3.6.2.3 Requirements satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in DD2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.2, which aimed at designing *loss functions that are tailored to the networking context*. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above in Section 3.6.2.2 indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.6.3 Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX (A22)

This activity casts the capacity forecasting problem in a mobile Edge environment where computational facilities serve a large number of individual radio access base stations located in their proximity, with the aim of reducing latency in service provisioning. This activity is another use case of the self-learning solution LossLeaP mentioned in the case of A21 presented in Section 4.6.2, and it also shares with that activity the use of the realistic traffic demands for different services from Dataset D3 described in Section 3.3 of this document and in Section 3.3.3 of D5.1. In this case, our management goal is the minimization of the economic Operating Expenses (OPEX) incurred by running the video streaming slices at the network Edge. Therefore, the tasks is to recurrently readapting and rescaling the computation resources associated to each NSSI.

This activity serves as an example of the flexibility of the LossLeaP solution mentioned in Section 4.6.2. The outcome of the application of LossLeaP in the proposed scenario was described in Section 4.6.3 of D5.1 where it was shown that loss-learning models can effectively support NI also in the case of resource allocations that target the reduction of OPEX. We also provided in Section 3.3 of D4.2 the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of D2.2 as well as its mapping to major standards. As mentioned for the previous activity, LossLeaP comply with the guidelines from Section 4.1 of D2.2 in alignment with the strategy outlined in Section 4.1.3 of D2.2. We refer to the mentioned previous deliverables for a more detailed description of the methods and results.

Experiments with real-world measurement data prove the significant advantage that a loss-learning approach yields over a state-of-the-art capacity predictor. These findings foster further research on these applications, and current non-finished advances on OPEX reduction jointly (and automatically) handled with admission control through NI solutions will be presented in incoming deliverables.

3.6.3.1 Evaluation

The complete empirical evaluation of this solution was presented in D5.1, Section 4.6.3 and contextualized in Section 4.5.6 of D5.2.

3.6.3.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K4	29-60% savings per server	We collected the KPIs through a simulation and data-driven evaluation making use of a real nationwide dataset from a commercial operator. The solution proposed by the consortium provides OPEX savings of around 30% with respect to state-of-the-art (SotA) solutions. Importantly, the SotA solution requires perfect knowledge of the OPEX derived from the network operation, while the proposed approach is generic and is able to learn an unknown function characterizing the OPEX. The gain with respect to standard approaches is above 60%
K9	0.5% (<1%)	The solution proposed by the consortium achieves OPEX savings that are only 10% higher than the ideal optimal solution. Here we should note that the optimal solution is an unattainable approach in which the system knows the future traffic with perfect accuracy, while the solution does not have such knowledge

3.6.3.3 Requirements satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.2, which aimed at designing *loss functions that are tailored to the networking context*. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above in Section 3.6.3.2 indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.6.4 Learning with predictions for edge caching and computing (A27)

In this subsection, we evaluate the solution presented in D4.3, Sec 4.4. Recall that we focused on the discrete caching (prefetching) challenge, which involves selecting files for replication in a local cache with the aim of maximizing the likelihood that a new file request will be fulfilled locally. We proposed two algorithms (OFIPL-Cache) and (OFTRL).

3.6.4.1 Evaluation

Our *metric* that we use to measure and evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm is the regret, which we restate below for clarity.

$$R_T(\{x\})_T = \sup_{\{f_t\}_{t=1}^T} \left\{ \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x^*) - \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_t) \right\}$$

Experimental Setup. We compare the performance of our algorithms with carefully selected competitors: the FTRL policy which generalizes the OGD from [49], and the FTPL method from [50]. We note that these competitors already showed superior performance to the classical methods of LRU and LFU in their experiments. The request traces are created using the MovieLens dataset [51] which contains time-stamped movie ratings. We assume a request is initiated to a CDN in the same chronological order as their ratings' timestamps. We consider movies with at least 8 ratings, leading to a library of $N = 10379$ and we set capacity $C = 150$. Each prediction is assumed correct with probability ρ . Specifically, we generate a one-hot predictions that has 1 at the file to be requested with probability ρ , or at any other random file with probability $1-\rho$. We also experiment with probabilistic predictions where the vector components represent the probabilities of files being requested. For the experiments with unequal-sized files, we generate the sizes uniformly $s_t \sim U[1, 10]$ and set $C = 500$. For the bipartite network, we use the 100k variation of the MovieLens dataset and consider files with at least 10 ratings, leading to $N = 1152$. The network consists of 3 caches ($C = 150$) and 4 user locations, the first two connected to caches 1 & 2, and the rest to caches 2 & 3.

Equal Size. Figure 67 shows the average regret (hit-rate gap to the optimal) growth with time for FTPL, FTRL, and their proposed optimistic counterparts. We experiment with $\rho = 0$, and $\rho = 0.75$. If, e.g., the request predictions were based on recommendations, these reflect the cases where the users do not follow the recommendations ($\rho = 0$), or actually request the recommended movie/file with probability 75%, ($\rho = 0.75$). In addition, we experiment with a sinusoidal ρ , which varies between $\rho = 0.5$ and $\rho = 0.9$, with a period of 103 slots. We observe that optimism accelerates and improves learning the best files to cache, reaching an average improvement of 104% (for OFTRL) and 37.1% (for OFTPL) when $\rho = 0.75$, compared to their "vanilla" counterparts (no predictions). Moreover, the performance degradation due to inaccurate predictions is almost negligible: $\leq 8.3\%$ for OFTRL and $\leq 6.6\%$ for OFTPL.

Figure 68. Comparison of $\frac{R_T}{T}$ for equal-sized files in a single cache and different policies: (a) OFTRL-Cache vs. FTRL/OGD; (b) OFTPL-Cache vs. FTPL; (c) OFTRL-Cache vs. OFTPL-Cache for good predictions and in (d) for worst-case predictions. In (c), (d) we plot the 0.95-confidence interval (8 runs)

Unequal Sizes. Recall that here we used the α -regret for the case if unequal sized files. In Figure 68 we evaluate the algorithms for the unequal sizes case and plot the $1/2$ -regret. We observe the same pattern of negligible performance degradation when $\rho = 0$, while $\rho = 0.75$ enables an improvement of 35% (for OFTRL) and 18.8% (for OFTPL). We kindly refer the reader to the appendix for additional experiments for the experts-caching algorithm, the bipartite caching problem, and with probabilistic predictions of varying qualities.

Figure 69. Comparing $\frac{R_T^{(1/2)}}{T}$ for unequal-sized files, single cache. (a) OFTRL-Uneq Cache vs. FTRL/OGD; (b) OFTPL-UneqCache vs. FTPL; (c)-(d) OFTRL-UneqCache vs. OFTPL-UneqCache for good/bad predictions.

3.6.4.2 Summary of KPIs

The following table showcases the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K9	100%	Similar to the previous iteration of this solution, we propose online learning-based caching policies that utilize predictions (of unknown quality) to boost performance, if those predictions are accurate, while still maintaining robust performance bounds otherwise. The difference is that this time we target <i>discrete caching</i> , dropping the continuous caching assumption. In general, our proposed system provably (theoretically and experimentally) reaches very close (or coincides) with the optimal performance; please refer to Section 3.6.4.1 for more details

3.6.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.2, which aimed at *designing loss functions that are tailored to the networking context*, and objective 3.3, which intended to *develop AI models for adaptable NI*. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above in Section 3.6.4.2 indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.6.5 Anticipatory capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing with a priori system knowledge (A31)

3.6.5.1 Evaluation

This activity casts an admission control and resource allocation problem in a mobile network environment where network slicing is applied. We consider a scenario where a set of content/service providers (e.g., Instagram, YouTube, Twitch, Google Maps, or Twitter) request distinct network slices to transmit their respective traffic. The network operator must decide which slices it accepts and how many resources it allocates to each one of the accepted slices. We consider that the operator's goal is to maximize the profit obtained from the deploying network-slicing-as-a-service (NSaaS). For that, we consider a) the revenue obtained from the service providers that pay for ensuring a Quality of Service (QoS) for their traffic, b) the cost of violating the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) that define the conditions for which the service providers are paying the operator, and c) the cost of allocating a certain amount of resources for these slices.

The activity evaluates the performance of the algorithm presented in Section 4.1.1.1 of the D4.3 of the project [3]. A key contribution of this activity is to evaluate for the first time the performance of *overbooking* on NSaaS with real traffic traces obtained from a nationwide commercial operator. IN this case, *overbooking* refers to the fact that the operator can actually allocate less resources than the amount agreed with the service provider, so as to be able to accept more slices without any traffic loss and thus increasing its profit. This *overbooking* of resources is possible due to the inherent dynamic nature of the cellular traffic: Since the service provider wants to ensure that its content is seamlessly transmitted, it will generally request a network capacity that is over-dimensioned or at least based on the value of a high percentile of the expected throughput distribution. Yet, the traffic volume variability is known to be huge, both in the long term (hours) but also in the short term (seconds-minutes, since the traffic presents a bursty behavior), and this aspect can be exploited by the network operator to boost its profits.

As for the case of A22 presented in Section 3.6.3, we assume that each of the services has a dedicated NSSI at the Edge facilities, and we derive realistic traffic demands for such services from Dataset D3 described in Section 3.3 of D5.2 of the DAEMON project [1]. Since the dataset D3 cannot be made publicly available, we also generate a synthetic dataset that mimics the main properties of the real-world service-level demands, and which leads to comparable results in our evaluations.

We compare the proposed kaNSaaS solution against several benchmarks: 1) Legacy NSaaS, which does not consider overbooking and allocates the exact number of resources agreed with the service provider, 2) CoNEXT, the state-of-the-art solution for overbooking for network slicing [52], and 3) Oracle, the ideal (and impossible) solution in which the resources allocated exactly match the minimum needed to serve all the traffic --- this solution would require a perfect knowledge of the future traffic.

Figure 70. Revenue, profit, OPEX, and SLA violation costs of all considered NSaaS solutions under (a) measurement and (b) synthetic demands, and with default system settings.

We wanted to understand the reasons behind the apparent better performance of kaNSaaS against the other benchmarks. For that, we have a deeper look at how the profit is obtained for each one of the proposed solutions, and we do so by splitting the revenue and the different costs incurred by each NSaaS scheme. Figure 69 represents the disentangled costs and revenue for all the accepted slices. We show the net profit (green), the operative expenses (OPEX) from allocating the network resources (dark orange), and the economic penalties derived from SLA violations (light orange).

The legacy NSaaS model does not suffer any cost from SLA violations. This is due to the highly conservative behavior of this approach, which abides to the overconservative estimation of the service providers. Yet, this approach results in a higher resource-allocation cost and the minimum profit among the tested approaches due to the aforementioned conservative approach. Conversely, the state-of-the-art model “CoNEXT” admits the highest amount of slices, increasing the revenue, yet at the cost of substantial SLA violations penalties.

The proposed solution kaNSaaS is the one that gets the closest to the ideal oracle approach. It strikes the balance between reducing the allocated resources, augmenting the number of accepted slices, while not increasing the SLA violations. Note that the total revenues are lower than the revenues of CoNEXT, but kaNSaaS achieves a considerably higher total profit.

Figure 71. Performance evaluation as function of different scenario parameters.

We have also evaluated the performance of the proposed approach when different parameters of the scenario vary. Specifically, we have studied the impact of the interval of time during which the resource allocated remain constant (Figure 70a), the impact of the total available network capacity (Figure 70b) and the impact of the cost of allocating resources with respect to the revenue brought by the traffic passing through those resources (Figure 70c). In Figure 70 we show the results from the real-world private dataset. The y-axis corresponds to the performance of the approaches with respect to the ideal Oracle. We demonstrate that kaNSaaS improves operator’s profit by more than 20% over previous state of the art for any network configuration.

3.6.5.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	29-50% savings per server	We evaluated the KPIs through data-driven evaluation in a simulated environment. The data is obtained from a nationwide operator. The proposed solution reduces the cost of anticipatory admission control and resource allocation of network slices by more than 30% over a huge range of operation points and hyperparameter values

K4	40% OPEX savings, 0.5% (<1%) SLA violations	The OPEX costs are reduced by more than 40% thanks to the important reduction on SLA violations, which account for most of the cost of operation of the operator
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3.6.5.3 Requirements satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.1, which aimed at *understanding the limits of AI*, and Objective 3.2, which aimed at *designing loss functions that are tailored to the networking context*. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above in Section 3.6.5.2 indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.6.6 Anticipatory meta-learned capacity allocation with overbooked admission control for network slicing without a priori knowledge (A32)

3.6.6.1 Evaluation

This activity evaluates a similar scenario as the previous activity A31 of admission control and resource allocation in a mobile network environment where network slicing is applied. As for the previous activity, we consider that a set of content/service providers (e.g., Instagram, YouTube, Twitch, Google Maps, or Twitter) request their own network slices, while the network operator aims at maximizing its profit from NSaaS. Again, we take into account a) the revenue obtained from the service providers that pay for ensuring a Quality of Service (QoS) for their traffic, b) the cost of violating the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) that define the conditions for which the service providers are paying the operator, and c) the cost of allocating a certain amount of resources for these slices. The technical details of the solution for this activity have been presented in Section 4.1.1.2 of the deliverable D4.3 of this project.

The main key difference with respect to Activity A31 is that, in this case, we do not assume any knowledge about the relationship between the final end-user QoE and the network decision. This assumption is a real practical limitation in modern communication networks due to their complexity and heterogeneity, as well as due to the highly dynamic nature of the network. The said relationship is often a complex function that depends on information that the operator cannot get access to.

In this scenario, we can incorporate the loss meta-learning architecture presented in Section 7.1.3 of D2.3 [4] to handle the task of deciding (i) which slices to accept and (ii) how many resources to reserve to accepted services. The network setup simulation is similar to that of Activity A31. We evaluate the solution with the traffic demand data obtained for the different services from Dataset D3 described in Section 3.3 of D5.2 of the DAEMON project [1]. As explained in Section 4.1.1.2 of the D4.3 of the project [3] the meta-learning task is far from trivial and represents a complex problem that cannot be solved with traditional techniques.

For fairness, any other solution that is compared against our solution may also consider that the relationship between the network decision and the target performance is unknown. The only existing solution for loss meta-learning in network regression tasks is LossLeap, from [53], although this algorithm is not designed to work with intertwined decisions such as the admission control. For that, we consider that the admission control is handled separately while the resource allocation is computed through LossLeaP.

We run experiments with real-world mobile traffic of up to 12 different service providers. The data from D3 includes over 400 base stations in a production infrastructure. The joint AC-RR task is computed at each Edge datacenter, where one edge datacenter serves up to 30 base stations.

In Figure 71 we represent an illustration of the performance of our solution. On top, we represent the total (sum) capacity allocated and the traffic demand of all the slices. We can observe how the solution is able to automatically limit the total allocated capacity below the maximum available capacity. This is done by (a) varying the resources allocated to each slice, and (b) rejecting/accepting more or less slices. At the bottom, we focus on only two slices (gray and red) to show their requested capacity (solid) and the allocated resources by our solution (dotted). When the available capacity is not enough to serve both, the gray slice is usually rejected, and the red slice is allocated less resources than the actual traffic. This reduction of traffic, which may look as a bad performance, is actually the optimal solution based on the defined loss function and profit function. Indeed, the operator obtains more profit by losing a bit of money from the red slice's service provider to free up space for other slices.

Figure 72. Left: illustration of the learned loss function (relationship) for one single slice, in order to stay within three dimensions. Right: representation of the operation of the solution, with (top) total traffic, and (bottom) individual allocated resources for two slices, where a value zero means that the slice has not been accepted in the period.

Table 25. Average F1-score of the 5 solutions across the 5 use cases.

Slices	Our solution			Benchmark	
	Normalized profit	Improvement over benchmark	Mean admitted slices	Normalized profit	Mean admitted slices
2	0.0549	24.67%	1.00	0.043	1.00
4	0.1816	12.09%	3.18	0.162	2.60
6	0.3363	26.38%	5.71	0.266	4.36
8	0.3725	6.55%	6.41	0.350	4.83
12	0.4621	36.96%	10.99	0.337	8.94

In Table 25, we present a quantitative evaluation of the solution, for different number of service providers concurrently applying for slices. We can observe how we can increase the profit of the operator up to 36% when all 12 slices are present, admitting an average of two slices more than the benchmark. We recall that it does so without any prior knowledge of the system or of the objective, which shows its meta-learning capabilities, and the practical advantages entailed by that in solving the MANO task.

3.6.6.2 Summary KPIs

The results presented above allow us to validate the following set of KPIs.

KPI	Result	Justification
K2	29-50% savings per server	We evaluated the KPIs through data-driven evaluation in a simulated environment. The data is obtained from a nationwide operator. The proposed solution reduces the cost of anticipatory admission control and resource allocation of network slices by up to 40%
K4	0.5% (<1%)	The proposed solution by the consortium is able to reduce the SLA violations below 0.5% of the time, while also reducing the computational cost and increasing the monetary profit

3.6.6.3 Requirements satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is due to the fact that this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project’s objective 3.2, which aimed at *designing loss functions that are tailored to the networking context*. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements.

Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above in Section 3.6.6.2 indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.7 Evaluation of NI to configure a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (A23)

All the effort of DAEMON on Reconfigurable Intelligent surfaces has been concentrated into a single activity, as it involved the actual building of hardware, which required a substantial amount of resources.

Table 26. Evaluation results for E7. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	Reached TRL	Testbed / Dataset	Main findings
A23	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	K6	4	T9	RIS can more than double the wireless capacity per square meter in many scenarios

The prototype design of a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) was described in D5.2, Section 4.6.

During Y3, we manufactured 10 boards of 10x10 unit cells each. The unit cells were deployed in a PCB layout such that the same inter-cell distance can be maintained across co-located boards. The remaining elements (flip-flops, resistors, etc.), are standard components assembled on the PCB. The final printout is shown in Figure 72(a).

(a) RIS Board.

(b) Testbed.

Figure 73. (a) 10×10 RIS PCB realization. (b) Testbed in an anechoic chamber with rotating structure.

3.7.1 Evaluation

We characterized one of our 10x10 RIS boards in an 8m×5m anechoic chamber. Figure 72(b) and Figure 73 illustrate our testbed. We mounted the board on a turntable controlled remotely from a master PC, which is also used to configure the beamforming parameters of the RIS. We use two software-defined radio devices attached to horn antennas with gain $G = 13.5$ dBi to generate ("TX") and receive ("RX") a continuous stream of OFDM QPSK-modulated symbols with 5 MHz of bandwidth and numerology that meets 3GPP LTE requirements. The transmission power of TX is -30 dBm per subcarrier, and we sample the reference signal received power (RSRP) at RX.

Figure 74. Map of the testbed.

The distances RIS-TX and RIS-RX are $d_{\text{RIS-TX}} = 1.1$ m and $d_{\text{RIS-RX}} = 6.3$ m, respectively. Considering the size of the RIS and its operating frequency, it is hard to guarantee that $d_{\text{RIS-TX}}$ is larger than the far-field threshold, which is $2 \frac{D^2}{\lambda} = 6.5$ m, where $D = 0.43$ m is the diagonal of the array. Nevertheless, our choice of $d_{\text{RIS-TX}}$ is larger than the reactive near-field threshold, which is $0.62 \sqrt{\frac{D^3}{\lambda}} = 0.73$ m, and sufficient for our purposes. As shown in Figure 73, the rotation of the table determines the azimuth angle θ_r , and the location of TX determines θ_t . Conversely, the elevation angles of RIS-TX and RIS-RX are fixed to $\phi_t = 33^\circ$ and $\phi_r = -3^\circ$, respectively.

3.7.1.1 Codebook characterization

We begin our experimental campaign by characterizing the codebook generated in D3.3, Section 5. To this end, we test out all the configurations $\mathcal{V} = \{\mathbf{v}_n\}_{n=1}^{N_B=1891}$ for a wide range of $\theta_r = [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and for $\theta_t = \{20^\circ, 90^\circ\}$.

For our empirical results, the first observation is that the direction (θ_n, ϕ_n) of the main lobe points towards $(\theta_r - \theta_t, \phi_r - \phi_t)$, as intended, for all configurations $\mathbf{v}_n \in \mathcal{V}$. These results, hence, validate our prototype for practically all configurations in \mathcal{V} . Figure 74 and Figure 75 depict some representative configurations $\mathbf{v}_n \in \mathcal{V}$ for both θ_t settings, respectively. These figures show that the main beam points towards the intended directions. We note, however, that the gain of the main lobe is penalized when we use large steering angles (see, e.g., $\theta = 60^\circ$ in both figures), which is expected. Overall, the power received in the intended direction ranges between -74 dBm (for large steering angles) and -64 dBm (for smaller angles), which give us remarkable beamforming gains between ~ 17 dB and ~ 27 dB over the noise floor.

Figure 75. Examples of beam patterns for $\theta_t = 90^\circ$.

Figure 76. Examples of beam patterns for $\theta_t = 20^\circ$.

Using the radar range equation introduced in D5.2, Section 4.6, the peak RCS can be calculated as $64\pi^3 \frac{P_{\text{RX}}}{P_{\text{TX}}} \cdot \left(\frac{d_{\text{RIS-TX}} \cdot d_{\text{RIS-RX}}}{\lambda \cdot G}\right)^2 = 11.2 \text{ dBm}^2$. Moreover, the HPBW is in average around 10° for all beam patterns. Both results are in line with our simulations in D5.2.

3.7.1.2 Scalability Analysis

To assess scalability, we analyze the beamforming gain of our RIS for a variable number of unit cells. To this goal, we take advantage of the absorption state available in our design for each cell, and produce virtual RISs with different sizes by setting the activation patterns shown in Figure 76 (a) to Figure 76 (d). For every virtual RIS, we re-optimized its codebook \mathcal{V}_N to account for its effective size and inter-cell spacing.

Figure 77. Different unit cell activation patterns in a 10x10 RIS board. Colored squares represent deactivated (in black) and activated (in white) cells.

To ease the analysis, we now fix $\theta_r = \theta_t = 0^\circ$ and measure the power received for every configuration $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}_N$. The results are shown in Figure 77, which represent the measured power with a color range for every combination of θ (x-axis) and ϕ (y-axis) from \mathcal{V}_N , and for $N = \{4, 8, 64, 100\}$. From these plots, we can observe how the main beam becomes sharper and carries more power as we increase N . With $N = 4$ (top left plot), no configuration produces a distinguishable beam, which renders a 2x2 RIS ineffective. For the rest, we note a growing amount of power in the intended direction, respectively, equal to -81.8 dBm ($N = 16$), -71.5 dBm ($N = 64$), and -66.5 dBm (all cells are activated).

Figure 78. Received power over the respective optimal codebook \mathcal{V}_N for virtual RISs with different sizes (activation patterns of Figure 76(a) to Figure 76(d), respectively). $\theta_r = \theta_t = 0^\circ$.

This behavior is expected: Figure 78 depicts in red the power observed at RX with the optimal configuration \mathbf{v} as a function of N , and compares that with a mathematical model, represented in blue. Both results are remarkably close to each other, which validates the ability of our approach to effectively create virtual surfaces with different shapes.

Figure 79. Beamforming gains as a function of the total number of antennas N .

3.7.1.3 *Other activation patterns*

To conclude our characterization, we study the performance of our RIS prototype when the inter-cell distance differs from $d_{max} = \lambda/2$ (shown in Figure 77 for $N = 100$). Like before, we calculated new optimized codebooks $\mathcal{V}_{d_{max}}$ for $d_{max} = \{\lambda, 1.5\lambda\}$, and plot in Figure 79 the power received at RX for each configuration $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{V}_{d_{max}}$. We do this for both activation patterns depicted in Figure 76(e) ("off2") and Figure 76(f) ("off3"), for $d_{max} = \lambda$ and $d_{max} = 1.5\lambda$, respectively.

Figure 80. Received power over the respective optimal codebook $\mathcal{V}_{d_{max}}$ for virtual RISs generating grating lobes (activation patterns of Figure 76(e) and Figure 76(f), respectively). Red dots indicate the expected location of the lobes based on theory. $\theta_r = \theta_t = 0^\circ$.

By changing d_{max} , we also change the density of active cells per board, $N = 25$ for $d_{max} = \lambda$ (Figure 79(a)) and $N = 16$ for $d_{max} = 1.5\lambda$ (Figure 79(b)). As shown earlier, this has a cost in terms of beamforming gains that is evidenced also in Figure 79: the maximum power is -80.4 dBm and -84.2 dBm for the two cases, respectively. Both plots reveal the presence of grating lobes, which are symmetrical beams that are denser for larger d_{max} values. These effects are well understood in the literature of antenna design and their distance can be estimated using a theoretical model. The figure depicts with red circles the expected location of these lobes, which match our measurements remarkably well. This further validates our design to effectively modify the shape of the RIS to the requirements of any given use case.

In conclusion, in the scope of this activity, we designed, prototyped and characterized an RF switch-based RIS that met our defined requirements in terms of RF steering, reconfigurability, energy efficiency, and cost.

3.7.2 *Summary KPIs*

The results presented above allows to validate the following KPI.

KPI	Result	Justification
K6	>100% capacity gain	The empirical evaluation performed over a 10x10 RIS board operating at sub-6GHz indicates gains between 17 and 27 dBs over the noise floor. Such remarkable gains in SNR translate into more than doubling the wireless capacity per square meter in many scenarios

3.7.3 *Requirement satisfaction*

The empirical results presented above moreover allows us next to validate the following set of requirements described in D2.3.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-RIS-000	100%	The empirical evaluation performed over a 10x10 RIS board operating at sub-6GHz indicates gains between 17 and 27 dBs over the noise floor. Such remarkable gains in SNR translate into more than doubling the wireless capacity per square meter in many scenarios
NFR-RIS-001	100%	As shown in D5.2, Section 4.6.1.5, re-configuration time takes less than 35 ms
NFR-RIS-002	100%	As shown in D5.2, Section 4.6.1.5, power consumption is lower than 65 mW
NFR-RIS-003	100%	As shown in D5.2, Section 4.6 and D5.3 above, our RIS design and its prototype can achieve up to 27 dBm gains passively, without active RF chains

3.8 Evaluation of NI for In-backhaul learning

Evaluation 8 encompasses the activities associated with NI solutions for in-backhaul learning. Table 27 summarizes these activities, the testbeds/datasets used to evaluate them, the KPIs captured, and the TRL achieved.

Table 27. Evaluation results for E8. The testbed and datasets indicated in the fifth column of the table are described in Section 3 of D5.2 [1] of the DAEMON project.

Activity	Topic	KPIs	Reached TRL	Testbed / Dataset	Main findings
A18	Random Forest models in programmable switches	K3	2	T12, D11	Inference fully performed in the user plane, at line rate, via programmable switches
A28	Efficient backhaul circuit switching	K3	3	None	Backhaul circuit switching with the aim of increasing the speed and efficiency

3.8.1 Efficient Backhaul Circuit Switching (A28)

3.8.1.1 Evaluation

In Section 4.7.2 of D5.2 [1], we presented the numerical evaluation of Birkhoff+, a robust, fast and efficient algorithm to address the problem of backhaul circuit switching. In this Deliverable, no additional work/results are presented.

3.8.1.2 Summary KPIs

The following table showcases the KPIs we have successfully achieved with the results presented above.

KPI	Result	Justification
K3	100%	We demonstrate how different traffic matrices affect the performance of a circuit switch in terms of throughput, configurations computation time, and number of configurations (please refer to 4.7.2 of D5.2 [1])

3.8.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

This activity did not have any associated performance requirements, i.e., any associated Non-Functional Requirement among the requirements defined in D2.3 of the DAEMON project [4]. This is because this activity is a proof of concept for the methodology developed within the project to address the main project's objective 3.1 on understanding the limits of AI. Thus, this is a generic use case not associated to non-functional requirements. Nevertheless, the evaluation presented above for this activity indicates that the proposed methodology clearly outperforms existing solutions.

The Functional Requirements (i.e., those which do not set hard constraints on performance) related to this activity are provided in D4.3 [3].

3.8.2 Random Forest models in programmable switches (A18)

In this section, we evaluate the performance of three in-switch inference solutions, described in section 6.1 of D3.3 [5] i) Henna [54] for hierarchical packet-level (PL) classification, ii) the extension of Flowrest [55] for flow-level (FL) classification and ii) Jewel [56], for joint packet- and flow-level classification.

Table 28 summarizes the results of evaluating the response time of the three different solutions and the baseline, where no inference is performed.

Table 28. Latency comparison between the no inference baseline, the PL, the FL and the joint PL-FL classification solutions.

Scenario	Measured latency [nanoseconds]
No Inference	284
Henna	318
Flowrest	392
Jewel	397

3.8.2.1 *Henna evaluation*

We implement Henna in an Intel Tofino switch, using testbed T12, and we evaluate its classification performance in a device classification task, exploiting dataset D11.

We organize the 21 classes of the dataset in 5 groups: Switches and Plugs (Belkin Wemo switch, iHome, TP-Link Smart plug, and Light Bulbs LiFX Smart Bulb); Sensors (Withings Aura smart sleep sensor, Belkin wemo motion sensor, and NEST Protect smoke alarm); Video Devices (Withings Smart Baby Monitor, Insteon Camera, TP-Link Day Night Cloud camera, Samsung SmartCam, Dropcam, and Netatmo Welcome); Appliances (PIX-STAR Photo-frame, Amazon Echo, Tribby Speaker, Netatmo weather station, Withings Smart scale, and Smart Things); and, Computers (Laptop, and MacBook).

We design Henna as a two-stage model with a first stage RF classifier identifying the group and five Decision Trees (DTs) in the second stage, aiming at identifying the class inside the group. We select the hyperparameters of the models by performing a grid search. We finally use a first stage RF with 3 trees and depth 10, and DTs with a depth in the range from 4 to 10 (depending on the group) in the second stage.

We compare Henna against a state-of-the-art single-stage model encoded using our implementation of Planter [57], configured with 3 trees and depth 10. The results, summarized in Table 29, show a superior performance Henna in all the 3 metrics considered.

Table 29. Performance comparison between Henna and a monolithic classifier.

Metric	1-Stage classifier	Henna	Relative gain
Precision	84.50%	89.07%	5.41%
Recall	77.25%	83.91%	8.62%
F1-score	78.95%	85.52%	8.32%

3.8.2.2 *Flowrest extension evaluation*

The extension of Flowrest focused on optimizing the operation logic of the solution both in the user plane, by enabling better resource usage, and in the control plane, where we introduced a simulator of the switch operation. We leverage the simulator to select a model that guarantees the scalability of the switch flow management system with no accuracy performance degradation. In particular, the simulator attains to i) minimize the dimension of the switch registers allocated for tracking the flows and their features, ii) dimension the timeout mechanism designed to remove expired flows from the memory. Figure 80 shows the simulator results in the CICIDS use case, with the best parameters we picked highlighted in red.

Figure 81. Simulator results in terms of collision rate, classification rate, macro and weighted F1 scores.

We evaluated the improved capabilities of Flowrest in five use cases: UNSW (D11), UNIBS (D12), ToN-IoT (D14) and IoT23. We compared the performance of Flowrest with five state-of-the-art solutions. Three of the benchmarks are for PL inference, i.e., Soter [58], Planter and Mousika [59], and two are for FL inference, i.e., pForest [60] and NetBeacon [61]. Figure 81 shows that Flowrest outperforms all the competitors in all the use cases, with gains that range from 11% to 39%.

Figure 82. Gain of Flowrest over the benchmarks in terms of average F1-score over all use cases.

3.8.2.3 *Jewel evaluation*

We implement Jewel in an Intel Tofino switch and we evaluate it in testbed T12 in four different use cases, leveraging datasets UNSW (D11), UNIBS (D12), ToN-IoT (D14) and IoT23 dataset. We compare Jewel against four state-of-the-art solutions that represent the most advanced works leveraging tree-based ML models for in-switch inference, namely, Planter, Mousika, Flowrest, and NetBeacon. While Planter is one the earliest works tackling PL classification at line-rate, Mousika leverages the knowledge distillation paradigm to provide an innovative methodology for the training of Binary Decision Trees (BDTs) for packet classification. We chose Flowrest, described in D3.2 [8], as the benchmark for flow-level (FL) classification. Finally, NetBeacon is the most recent solution and the first one to propose joint packet- and flow-level classification by employing: one DT for the prediction of short or long flows; one DT for the classification of early packets with PL features only; multiple DTs to perform FL classification at different flow lengths.

Jewel stands up among these state-of-the-art solutions as the most recent and the only one employing truly joint PL-FL classification, as it leverages just one single Random Forest (RF) model able to classify both early packets and flows. Table 30 summarizes the performance of Jewel and the four benchmarks in terms of F1 score (averaged among micro, macro and weighted F1-scores), with the best score highlighted in bold.

Table 30. Average F1-score of the 5 solutions across the 5 use cases.

	Mousika	Planter	Flowrest	NetBeacon	Jewel
UNIBS	90.351%	91.560%	96.398%	94.570%	98.354%
UNSW	82.003%	79.853%	80.691%	78.594%	87.317%
ToN-IoT	27.554%	70.496%	73.461%	70.063%	75.703%
IoT23	85.054%	88.147%	82.857%	86.076%	91.314%

Figure 83. Score (a) and resource consumption (b) comparison of the solutions. For each solution, the distance to the best-performing solution is shown across the 4 use cases.

In Figure 82 (a), we provide a performance comparison between Jewel and all the benchmarks in terms of Micro, Macro and Weighted F1-score. As the bars shows the distance from the best score, Jewel exhibits the best score in all the use cases and with all the metrics. A similar representation is shown in plot (b) for resource consumption, with TCAM and average resources available are highlighted. Jewel appears to be the best among the FL solution, which are naturally more resource-hungry, while the PL solutions consumes less resources.

3.8.2.4 *Summary KPIs*

The results show that it is possible to perform PL, FL and join PL-FL classification in programmable switches with random forest models with a response time below the microsecond.

KPI	Result	Justification
K3	< 1 microsecond	As shown in Table 28, the response time of the solutions is always below the microsecond

3.8.2.5 Requirements satisfaction

All the solutions of random forest models in programmable switches meet the requirements.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
NFR-IBSSI-000	100%	All the models evaluated are tailored to the switch architecture, taking into account the operation of the match and action units and of their specific components, such as memory registers, SRAM and TCAM tables
NFR-IBSSI-001	100%	All the models evaluated are resource-prudent, as they are designed with original software meant to optimize the utilization of the switch hardware components, especially of the critical ones like TCAM tables and memory registers

4 Open-source datasets and software

All datasets and tools developed and utilized throughout the DAEMON project, including those employed in various activities, have been open-sourced and are publicly available on the DAEMON GitHub page. D6.4, Section 2.3.2 provides a comprehensive overview for Y3 of the project. For completeness, in the following we list all the assets produced by the end of the project, separating tools and datasets into two distinct groups. We associate each asset with its relevant activity and corresponding section within this deliverable to enhance clarity and since that was not available in previous deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 for assets produced in Y1 and Y2 of the project execution.

Table 31. Open-source tools developed by DAEMON.

Name	Activities	Section	Link	Brief description
srsLTE	A29	3.2.5	https://github.com/h2020daemon/srsLTE	These repositories have been used to evaluate A29, for the RAN and Core, respectively. They have been described in D5.2 Section 3.1.1 and in [62]
Open5GS with K8s	A29	3.2.5	https://github.com/h2020daemon/k8s-open5gs	
Flowrest	A18	3.8.2	https://github.com/h2020daemon/Flowrest	Python and P4 code implementing the Flowrest framework, plus information on how to reproduce the results reported in the original paper [55]
LossLeaP	A21, A22	3.6.2 3.6.3	https://github.com/h2020daemon/LossLeaP	Python code implementing the LossLeaP model for GPU execution
TES-RNN	A20, A25	3.6.1 3.4.3	https://github.com/h2020daemon/wowmo_m22_tes-rnn	Python code implementing the TES-RNN model for GPU execution
Henna	A18	3.8.2	https://github.com/h2020daemon/Henna	Python and P4 code implementing the Henna framework, plus information on how to reproduce the results reported in the original paper [54]
NEMO	A6	3.3.3	https://github.com/h2020daemon/Nemo_tool	Nemo is a boolean and numerical constraint language and tool with first-class support for feature modeling used in SAVRUS (A6), a proof of concept that analyses extensive IoT/Edge/Cloud systems
NEMO2	A6	3.3.3	https://github.com/h2020daemon/Nemo2_tool	A flavor of NEMO, also used in SAVRUS (A6), which extends classic variability models with numerical features and arithmetic in the formats DIMACS and Universal Variability Language (UVL)
Energy-driven vRAN orchestration	A4	3.3.1	https://github.com/h2020daemon/contextual_bayesian_optimization	A library that implements a novel Bayesian online learning approach to solve contextual bandit problems, created to address A4
Energy-driven joint vRAN & Edge orchestration	A5	3.3.2	https://github.com/h2020daemon/constrained_bayes_opt	An extended Bayesian online learning approach to solve contextual bandit problems, created to address A5
AutoManager	A32, A33	3.6.6 3.3.7	https://github.com/h2020daemon/AutoManager	Python code implementing the Automanager model for GPU execution
kaNSaaS	A31	3.6.5	https://github.com/h2020daemon/kansaas	Python code implementing the kaNSaaS model for GPU execution, plus synthetic data to reproduce the results in the original paper [63]

Latency and energy consumption models of a CPU and a GPU LDPC decoder	A2	3.2.2	https://github.com/h2020daemon/CloudRIC	Neural network-based models of two different processors for 5G LDPC decoding: A CPU-based processor based on Intel FlexRAN, and a GPU processor based on NVIDIA Aerial. These models were created to develop A2
Code of Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Network Contextual Bandits	A2	3.2.2	https://github.com/h2020daemon/risk_aware_contextual_bandit	A novel library to solve contextual bandit problems, which supports hard constraints with controllable risk. This library was generated to develop A2

Table 32. Datasets collected for and/or employed in the evaluations of DAEMON.

Name	Activities	Sections	Link	Brief description
Quality-aware Analysis and Optimization of Virtual Network Functions	A6	3.3.3	https://github.com/h2020daemon/SPLC22	This repository contains the models, operations and results empirically used in Quality-aware Analysis and Optimization of Virtual Network Functions used to develop A6
Energy-driven joint vRAN & edge service orchestration	A4	3.3.1	https://github.com/h2020daemon/energy_edge_AI_dataset	This repository contains a dataset with empirical data from a joint vRAN/edge video delivery service, used in A4
Traffic Classification at the spectrum level dataset and code	None. This is related to research outcomes from WP2 T2.3 (Limits of AI and Hybrid Approaches)	7.2.1 in D2.3	https://github.com/h2020daemon/tc_spectrum	This repository has the code and the link to the zenodo repository with the dataset generated to perform traffic classification using spectrum data (L1 PHY packets) with Deep Learning approaches
Latency and energy consumption characterization of a CPU and a GPU LDPC decoder	A2	3.2.2	https://github.com/h2020daemon/CloudRic-Artifacts	This repository contains a dataset with empirical metrics from two different LDPC processors: a CPU-based processor based on Intel FlexRAN, and a GPU-based processor based on NVIDIA aerial
Experimental characterization of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	A23	3.7	https://github.com/h2020daemon/RIS-Power-Measurements-Dataset	This repository contains a dataset with the empirical characterization of the Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface developed in A23

5 Demonstrators, pilots, and proof-of-concepts

DAEMON aims at significantly advancing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of NI technologies within our identified NI functionality areas. Table 33 provides an overview of all empirical and data-driven evaluations conducted since the project's inception, including relevant evaluations, activities, KPIs, TRL achieved, and highlighting those specifically executed during Year 3.

More specifically, in Year 3, DAEMON successfully performed **four additional demonstrations (TRL<5)** of NI functionalities, and **one new pilot (TRL 5)** involving real customers, in addition to the completion of the first pilot started in Y2. We also performed **3 further Proofs-of-Concept (PoCs) and data-driven evaluations**. Notably, these activities not only fulfill DAEMON's Objective 4 (six empirical and data-driven evaluations in the context of NI for sustainable virtualized RANs, NI for VNF placement control, NI for real-time anomaly detection, NI for edge orchestration, NI for automated anomaly response, and NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning), but also demonstrate our commitment by exceeding this goal with two additional evaluations focusing on Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (E7) and in-backhaul learning (E7). Furthermore, DAEMON has conducted **an additional demonstration** of an NI Plane implementation, which is reported in Section 2 and demonstrated in Section 5.1.1.

Table 33. DAEMON demonstrations, pilots, and proof-of-concepts.

Evaluation	Short description of the evaluation	PoC/Pilot Means (Tools used)	PoC, Pilot or Demo executed	Max TRL reached
E1	NI for sustainable virtualized Radio Access Network (RAN)	Experimental (T1, S2)	Demos: A1, A2 (Y3)	4
E2	NI for VNF placement and control	Experimental and data-driven (T5, T8, D10)	Demos: A4, A7 (Y3)	3
E3+E5	NI for real-time anomaly detection	Experimental and data-driven (T8, D3, D8)	Demo: A9 Pilot: A19 (Y3) PoC: A25	5
E4	NI for Edge orchestration	Experimental and data-driven (D1, D5, D6, D9, T4, S4, S1)	Demo: A11, A15/A26 (Y3) Pilot: A13	5
E6	NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning	Data-driven (D3, D9)	PoCs: A20, A21, A22, A27, A31 (Y3), A32 (Y3)	3
E7	NI to configure a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	Experimental (T9)	PoC: A23 (Y3)	4
E8	NI for in-backhaul learning	Experimental and data-driven (D7, D11, D12, T12)	Demo: A18 (Y3)	3

For many of these evaluations, DAEMON has executed specific demonstrations or pilots during Y3 (in addition to the ones reported in D5.2), which are summarized in Table 34.

In addition to these, DAEMON has also developed a demonstrator of DAEMON's NI Plane. The goal of this demonstration activity is to showcase how the NI functionalities proposed by the project would integrate natively within the next-generation mobile network architecture.

Table 34. List of Y3 demo and pilot activities.

Evaluation with Y3 PoC/Pilot Demo	Description	Tools/Means
E1	The PoC of activity A2 has been performed using an O-RAN compliant cloud platform. The solution, discussed in WP3 optimizes cost and energy efficiency with heterogeneous hardware accelerators shared by multiple 5G Distributed Units (DUs)	A2 PoC discussed in Section 5.3
E2	We demonstrated the HADES approach (activity A7) work using a case scenario on augmented reality. Specifically, we use the Planetarium System presented in Section 3.3.4. Videos of the demos can be found in the DAEMON website	PoC
E3	We executed a pilot of activity A19 . This showcased the anomaly detection pipeline we designed and tested in collaboration with Telefonica's IoT Managed Connectivity Platform. Our evaluation relies on a large-scale dataset that we collect from the IoT platform, comprising of a sample per-device of mobility signaling traffic. The NI functionality we developed within A19 has a TRL 5 based on the pilot we carried out with Telefonica's IoT Platform	Data-driven (D8)
E4	We demonstrated the work of EnergyEdgeCloudSim (activity A15/A26) using the Shanghai data set. EnergyEdgeCloud is an extension of EdgeCloudSim, an open-source tool that provides a simulation environment specific to Edge Computing. Concretely, we have modified this simulator to consider the energy consumption during the simulation and to return the energy consumed by each edge device at the end of the simulation using the energy consumption	Data-Driven
E8	We demonstrated In-backhaul learning (activity A18) with an experimental PoC that exploits testbed T12. The demonstration aims at: i) showing that our solution Flowrest outperforms a packet-level benchmark in terms of classification score (i.e, F1-score, Precision, Recall); ii) the inference is performed at line-rate. To achieve this, we evaluate our solution with a multi-class traffic classification use case and run three experiments: i) we perform normal forwarding to measure the in-switch latency of a legacy switch; ii) we perform packet-level classification by running a benchmark solution to measure both the classification performance and the in-switch latency; iii) we apply our solution Flowrest and measure both the classification performance and the in-switch latency. We summarize and show in a dashboard the results of the experiments	Experimental Demo on testbed T12.
NI Plane	In testbeds T4 and T8 the NIP architecture (described in WP2) was deployed, and a set of solutions (two solutions as a first step) was realised following the NIP approach. In order to showcase the NIP approach and the solutions we demonstrate a Smart-Highway scenario in which anomalies (QoS degradations in vehicular services) are detected in a real time manner and actions in edge orchestrators are triggered as a response to them. A first version of the NIP demo is already deployed, and it is described in detail in the next section 5.1	Experimental Demo on Testbed (T4, T8)

In the following, we provide additional details on each of the **demonstrators and pilots** executed by DAEMON during Year 3 and one pilot that was executed during Y2.

5.1 Demonstrations

5.1.1 NI Plane integrated demo

This section describes a demonstrator of an implementation of WP2's NIP Architecture, reported in D2.3 [4]. As described in Section 2.2 we create and deploy two example NIFs (NIF1 and NIF2) to demonstrate the conflict resolution capabilities of the NI Plane. These 2 NIFs were demonstrated during Y2's review.

The first NIF (NIF1) utilizes a federated learning-powered anomaly detection algorithm, extended with a basic service resource management capability (e.g., scale in/out on resource under/ overutilization). This NIF corresponds to A9 whose design is reported in D4.3 [3], Section 5.1 (WP4), and whose evaluation is reported in Section 3.5.3 of this document (WP5). NIF1 (i.e., FL Controller) is composed of two NIF-C components, a "Analyze" component that learns from a global model built from the input of different FL clients, and a "Knowledge" component that represents the federated learning-powered anomaly detection capabilities and may scale in/out services according to such detected anomalies. While the annotation and creation procedures for NIF1 is described as Kubernetes manifest files, as presented in Section 2.2 (see Figure 5), for the representation of the intra-NIF topology we use Kubeflow Pipelines manifests which map the outputs of each component to the inputs of the components which require from different inputs. An example of such a file is provided in Figure 83, where two components of type "Analyze" (template 'analyze-component'), and "Knowledge" (template 'knowledge-component') are linked together. This link is represented by redirecting output of the "Analyze" component (i.e., analyzeAnomaly-output) to the input to the "Knowledge component".

```
spec:
  entrypoint: kubeflow-pipeline
  templates:
    - name: kubeflow-pipeline
      steps:
        - name: analyzeAnomaly
          template: analyze-component
          arguments:
            parameters:
              - name: sourceX-output
                value: data/sourceX.csv
        - name: knowledgeFL
          template: knowledge-component
          arguments:
            parameters:
              - name: analyzeAnomaly-output
                value: "{{steps.analyzeAnomaly.outputs.parameters.analyze-output}}"
        - name: analyzeAnomaly
          inputs:
            parameters:
              - name: sourceX-output
          outputs:
            parameters:
              - name: analyzeAnomaly-output
                valueFrom:
                  path: /tmp/analyzeAnomaly-output
            container:
              image: analyzeAnomaly-image:latest
              command:
                - python
                - /src/analyze.py
              args:
                - --input
                - "{{inputs.parameters.sourceX-output}}"
                - --output
                - /tmp/analyzeAnomaly-output
        - name: knowledgeFL
          inputs:
            parameters:
              - name: analyzeAnomaly-output
          outputs:
            parameters:
              - name: knowledgeFL-output
                valueFrom:
                  path: /tmp/knowledgeFL-output
            container:
              image: knowledgeFL-image:latest
              command:
                - python
                - /src/inference.py
              args:
                - --input
                - "{{inputs.parameters.analyzeAnomaly-output}}"
                - --output
                - /tmp/knowledgeFL-output
```

Figure 84. Example of Kubeflow Pipeline used to represent the intra NIF topology of NIF1

The second NIF (NIF2) employs a service relocation algorithm that collects real-time monitoring information from the edge [29], such as CPU load, memory load, used storage, and end-to-end latency measured at the client side. This NIF (i.e., RSU Orchestrator) corresponds to A11 whose design is reported in D3.3 [5], Section 4.1 (WP3), and whose evaluation is reported in D5.2 [1], Section 4.4.2 (WP5).

Even though NIF2 has only one NIF-C of type "Plan", it does require a Kubeflow Pipeline manifest file since it may be connected to other external NIFs. In this case, it is connected to NIF2 via the output of the "Knowledge" component of NIF1 (i.e., shown as knowledgeFL-output in Figure 84).

```
spec:
  entrypoint: kubeflow-pipeline
  templates:
  - name: kubeflow-pipeline
    steps:
    - name: plan_orch
      template: plan-component
      arguments:
      parameters:
      - name: knowledgeFL-output
        value: "{{steps.knowledgeFL.outputs.parameters.analyze-output}}"
        type: external
    - name: plan_orch
      type: external
      extID: rsu_orch
      inputs:
      parameters:
      - name: knowledgeFL-output
      outputs:
      parameters:
      - name: plan_orch-output
        valueFrom:
        path: /tmp/plan_orch-output
      container:
      image: plan_orch-image:latest
      command:
      - python
      - /src/orch.py
      args:
      - --input
      - "{{inputs.parameters.knowledgeFL-output}}"
      - --output
      - /tmp/plan_orch-output
```

Figure 85. Example of Kubeflow Pipeline used to represent the intra NIF topology of NIF2.

In order to onboard both NIFs into the NIS CSOI, the corresponding NIF Descriptors (NIFD) have to be added from a local/external repository. In the demo, this is done by dragging the files to the 'dropzone area' of the NIS CSOI GUI. Once added, the NIS CSOI parses and assesses each NIF, and stores and displays their attributes and annotations. Figure 85 shows the GUI of the CSOI after onboarding NIF1 and NIF2. We manually mark NIF1 in blue as "FL Controller" and NIF2 in green as "RSU Orch".

The NIF CSOI only starts the conflict resolution procedure whenever NIFs need to be deployed. Upon selection of the NIFs that want to be deployed, the NIS CSOI begins to deploy sequentially each of the marked NIFs. However, before deploying them, it checks with the PolicyC if there is any conflict with this NIF, as illustrated in Figure 6. The PolicyC will forward the NIF descriptor to the Conflict Resolution component, which will analyze if such conflict exists. If it does, it will select the right solver to resolve the conflict and will generate the corresponding rules to mitigate it.

DAEMON
DAEMON NIS CSOI

Select	Name	Number of NIF-Cs	CPU Requested	CPU Limit	Memory Requested	Memory Limit	NodeSelector	State
<input type="checkbox"/>	flcontroller	2	1	4	268435456	1073741824	false	Ready
<input type="checkbox"/>	rsu_orch	1	0	0	0	0	true	Ready

Figure 86. Example of the NIS CSOI displaying NIF1 and NIF2 as onboarded.

Figure 86 shows an example of when both NIF1 and NIF2 need to be instantiated. Due to NIF1 (FL Controller) having annotations on limits and requests in CPU and memory (see again Figure 7) that are not compatible with the nodeSelector annotation of NIF2 (RSU Orch) manifest file (see again Figure 8), a conflict will happen. The NIF CSOI will try to deploy both NIF1 and NIF2. Given that the nodeSelector annotation is specifying the particular Kubernetes worker where NIF2 should be instantiated, and NIF1 annotation on memory and CPU impose certain rules that such Kubernetes worker may not own, such attributes generate a conflict when both NIFs are connected and deployed together. Because both NIFs are incompatible, the Conflict Resolution component will trigger a message warning about the conflict. Additionally, it will generate rules for the NIF CSOI to let it know how to proceed. In this case, we define a toy example stating that when conflict of this type (e.g., resourceRequestConflict) exists, NIF1 should be undeployed (if already deployed) and NIF2 should be deployed, since it is assigned a higher priority.

Figure 87. Example of the NIS CSOI displaying the conflict between NIF1 and NIF2 and performing the corresponding actions (i.e., undeploying NIF1 and deploying NIF2).

In order to organize how conflicts resolution functions are performed, and which solvers need to be used to retrieve the actions to be applied to mitigate the conflict, we define an additional ConflictResolution configuration YAML file (`conflict_resolution.yaml`) which can be loaded to the ConflictResolution of the NIO. Figure 87 illustrates the content of the file used for the above-described conflict between NIF1 and NIF2.

```

metadata:
  name: nif-conflict-resolution-policy
  namespace: vnf-management
  conflictResolutionPolicy:
    type: PriorityBased
    defaultAction: ChooseHighestPriority
nifDefinitions:
  - nif: rsu_orch
    annotations:
      - daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector
    priority: 1
  - nif: fcontroller
    annotations:
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.memory
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.memory
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.cpu
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.cpu
    priority: 5
annotationConflictMatrix:
  daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector:
    conflictsWith:
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.memory
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.memory
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.cpu
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.cpu
  daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.memory:
    conflictsWith:
      - daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector
  daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.memory:
    conflictsWith:
      - daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector
  daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.cpu:
    conflictsWith:
      - daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector
  daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.cpu:
    conflictsWith:
      - daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector
nifConflictDefinitions:
  - conflictType: resourceRequestConflict
    annotations:
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.memory
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.memory
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.requests.cpu
      - daemon.nmapek.analyze.target.spec.containers.resources.limits.cpu
      - daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector
nifResolutionStrategies:
  - conflictType: resourceRequestConflict
    solvers:
      - name: prioritySolver1
        steps:
          - undeploy: lowest_prio_nif
          - deploy: highest_prio_nif
    resolution:
      action: prioritySolver1
      fallback: consultAdmin
  
```

Figure 88. Example ConflictResolution configuration YAML file used to identify conflicts and provide mitigation actions.

It consists of different elements that allow define the NIFs that may conflict (i.e., `nifDefinitions`), the conflict resolution matrix that determine which annotations have potential conflicts (i.e., `annotationConflictMatrix`), the types of expected conflicts (i.e., `resourceRequestConflict` in our case) and the list of resolution strategies for each of the conflict types (`nifResolutionStrategies`). Examples of other types of conflicts may be related to learning methods (`learningMethodConflict`), data incompatibility (`datasetIncompatibilityConflict`), format errors (`badFormattingConflict`), etc. When the ConflictResolution module applies the above illustrated “`conflict_resolution.yaml`” file, the result is that NIF1 is undeployed since it has lower priority, and NIF2 remains deployed as it has higher priority (see again Figure 87).

In order to show an example of a conflict-free connection between NIF1 and NIF2, we temporarily set the annotation “`daemon.nmapek.plan.target.spec.containers.nodeSelector:`” to “`false`” in the NIFD manifest file from the NIF2. By doing this, the two NIFs can be jointly deployed, being

the output of the “Knowledge” component of NIF1 (FL Controller) attached to the input of the “Plan” component of NIF2 (RSU Orch) by a new dashed line as shown in Figure 88.

Figure 89. Example of the NIS CSOI displaying NIF1 and NIF2 as deployed without conflicts.

Finally, we show in Figure 89 how other more complex NIF (e.g., Nuberu and Athena as in Figure 9 of D2.3 [4]) can be onboarded in the NIS CSOI, jointly deployed, and conflicts can be assessed and resolved accordingly (although no conflicts are shown in this case).

Figure 90. Example of the NIS CSOI displaying Nuberu and Athena as deployed without conflicts.

5.1.2 Evaluation E1: CloudRIC demo

Using the prototype described in Section 3.2.2, we have created a dashboard and a testing O-Cloud environment to replicate the results of Figure 16 in a real-time demonstrator of Activity 2 (A2), which corresponds to Evaluation E1.

More specifically, we allow the instantiation of a variable number of virtualized Distributed Units (vDUs) as shown in Figure 91. Each vDU can generate one type of workload, saturated (5x 5G UEs per DU, as explained in D5.2, Section 4.12) or not saturated (5x 5Gx64 UEs per DU). By varying the number of vDUs in the system, we can test different workloads in the O-Cloud platform, as in Figure 16.

Once a scenario is selected (number of vDUs and saturation level), a NI solution for the O-Cloud platform can be selected: Industry-std, O-Greedy, O-MWT, C-MWT, C-DA or, finally, CloudRIC. These solutions are explained in detail in Section 3.2.2.

After submitting the parameters of the demonstrator, real-time measurements of reliability, throughput and energy consumption, as those of Figure 16 are presented, demonstrating the ability of CloudRIC to guarantee reliability in all the scenarios (like Industry-standard) while consuming substantially less energy than Industry-std.

Figure 91. CloudRIC demonstrator dashboard.

5.1.3 Evaluation E2: PlanetARium demo

PlanetARium (corresponding to [Evaluation E2](#)) is an augmented reality application used as a case study for activity A7 in the DAEMON project. This demo illustrates the work of iArea, the component of the Hades approach (presented in Section 2.1 of D4.2) for the optimal deployment of VNF in a collection of nodes. PlanetARium was introduced in Section 4.2.4 of D5.2, comprising six scalable virtual network services. In the demo, these services communicate using Zenoh Flow, and it is possible to see how planets are rendered using ARUco markers.

The demo illustrates the monitoring of the application pods at runtime using Prometheus and Grafana. The information Prometheus provides is used by iArea to select the optimal deployment at runtime. So, as a part of the demo, we demonstrate the work of the different iArea consoles to configure nodes and tasks and generate optimal deployment.

Figure 92. Rendering of planets in PlanetARium demo.

5.1.4 Evaluation E4: EnergyEdgeCloudSim Demo

In this section, we present a demonstration within [Evaluation E4](#), which demonstrates the use of EnergyEdgeCloudSim. This demo is part of activities A15 and A26, which seek to validate the mentioned tool. EnergyEdgeCloudSim was introduced in 3.2.4 of D5.1, and a demo is available on the DAEMON website.

EnergyEdgeCloudSim is an extension of the tool EdgeCloudSim⁶ that adds functionality for energy consumption measurements. The original tool, EdgeCloudSim, is a simulation environment specific to Edge Computing scenarios where conducting experiments considering computational and networking resources is possible. It is deployed in a computer as a simulation tool, and different modules are used to simulate different kinds of WLAN or WANs.

The E4 demonstration introduces the tool and overviews its main components and consoles. The usage is illustrated using the Shanghai Telecom dataset⁷. This dataset contains six months of mobile phone records accessing the Internet via base stations distributed over Shanghai. In addition, it has more than 7.2 million records from 9481 mobile devices and 3233 base stations. Figure 92 shows part of the output of this experiment (results were reported in D5.2) where the energy consumption of nodes is reported.

Figure 94. Main GUI of EnergyEdgeCloudSim.

⁶ <https://github.com/CagataySonmez/EdgeCloudSim>

⁷ <http://squangwang.com/TelecomDataset.html>

5.1.5 Evaluation E8: Flowrest demo

The demo of Flowrest, stems from activity A18 and is part of [Evaluation E8](#). The demonstration has the goal of i) showing that Flowrest outperforms a solution based on PL inference, namely, Planter [57], and ii) proving that RF inference can be performed in programmable switches at line-rate, with a response time below the microsecond. We implemented our demonstration in testbed T12 and evaluated Flowrest and the benchmark with dataset UNIBS (D12) with 8 different applications.

In the demonstration we run three consecutive experiments. In the first experiment, we test a baseline program with no inference to evaluate the latency of the switch in normal conditions. In the second and third experiments, we test respectively the PL and FL solutions, both in terms of classification accuracy and response time.

Figure 93 shows the dashboard where accuracy and latency are depicted. On the left part of the screen, live results are shown as the experiments progress. The accuracy is expressed in terms of F1-score, Precision and Recall, with the thin lines representing the instantaneous accuracy and the thick lines representing the moving average. In the case of the Latency, just the instantaneous one is shown and represented as a solid line. It is worth noticing that the latency is very stable during the experiment, showing that the switch pipeline can guarantee a virtually constant response time, almost without fluctuations. On the right side of the screen the overall results are shown. Flowrest improves the classification accuracy of the benchmark by 10%, while spending roughly 100 and 70 nanoseconds more than the baseline and the PL benchmark. We want to stress that the difference in terms of latency with respect to both baseline and benchmark can be safely ignored, as it does not cause any packet drop.

It is worth noting that this demonstrator was displayed at the Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2023 and won the Best Demo Award at the international scientific conference IEEE NetSoft 2023.

Figure 95. Dashboard of the DAEMON Flowrest demo.

5.2 Pilots

5.2.1 Evaluation E4: Data-Driven Orchestration Pilot

In this section, we summarize the pilot that we performed corresponding to Activity A13 ([Evaluation E4](#)), which we previously presented in D3.2 (Section 3.4) and briefly reported in D5.2 (Section 4.4.4). We note that this pilot was generated during Y2 but was not detailed in D5.2.

Figure 96. Big data platform.

For this pilot, we worked directly with Virgin Media O2 (VMO2) in the UK, using their big data platform. This infrastructure includes more than 250 nodes, 3PB of storage, 60TB of RAM, and more than 5,000 CPUs. The data ingestion service runs 24/7 and receives more than 10TB/day. Figure 94 captures the specifics of the software stack running in the UK cluster. For our work, we relied on various datasets that the operator collects from their infrastructure (see Figure 95) and stores in their big data platform.

Figure 97. High-level architecture of the measurement infrastructure integrated in the cellular network.

With this, we created an analytics pipeline that runs within the platform, and that captures general statistics about the activity of a sample of 1 million IoT devices connecting to the cellular infrastructure. We give in Figure 96 an overview of the data processing logic we have in place, as we integrated it in the big data cluster together with the operator.

With this, we then analyze three representative groups of devices: connected cars as a use case of URLLC, smart meters as a representative of mMTC, and smartphones for eMBB.

Figure 98. Airflow DAG for the data processing pipeline that generates the per-device features that we collect and further use for device classification.

Our analysis reveals that specific metrics capture distinct behaviors among these three groups of devices corresponding to the main 5G use-cases. This validates the 5G design's accurate prediction of their importance. However, when constructing device samples, we noticed that the global

deployment model preferred by IoT verticals is rapidly becoming the norm. Less than 2% of connected cars in our sample are native to the operator we analyze, reducing visibility into end-user requirements. Despite this, we observe network behavior similarities across different device categories (e.g., smartphones and connected cars). Within each group, unique traffic patterns emerge, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches by network operators. Fine-grained understanding and intelligent analytics are essential to match devices with their predicted requirements profiles. As part of the pilot, we explore emerging patterns within these three major 5G device categories, considering both category similarity and heterogeneity within standalone use cases.

To further justify the need for a data-driven orchestration approach, we use Representational Similarity Matrices (RSMs) and examine the cosine similarity between the representations of each pair of users in the same category (Figure 97.a) and in the same cluster (Figure 97.b) for a random sample of 1,000 users. Square sections in Figure 97 - left indicate the similarity between connected cars and smartphones. The square sections of the RSM lying along the blue diagonal in Figure 97.b correspond to the similarities between users in the same cluster, implying that the clustering approach can capture the similarities among users with the same behaviour.

Figure 99. RSMs between pairs of users in a random sample of 1000 end-users.

5.2.2 Evaluation E3: ANCHOR Pilot

In this section, we summarize the pilot we performed of the ANCHOR activity (A19), which is part of Evaluation E3. This effort demonstrates the anomaly detection pipeline we designed and tested in collaboration with Telefonica Global Solutions (TGS) IoT Managed Connectivity Platform.

Our evaluation relies on a large-scale dataset (D8) that we collect from the IoT platform, comprising of a sample per-device of mobility signaling traffic. The NI functionality we developed within A19 has a TRL 5 based on the pilot we carried out with Telefonica's IoT Platform operated by TGS. We show in Figure 98 below the global footprint of the IoT managed connectivity service operated by TGS.

Figure 100. Global Footprint of the TGS IoT managed connectivity commercial platform.

For the ANCHOR prototype, we have built together with the engineering team a separate data ingestion pipeline to samples the live feeds that the operator usually collects from the commercial platform in their four points of international signaling (namely, Miami, Frankfurt, Madrid and Puerto Rico). We show in Figure 99 a schematic representation of the centralized data collection solution. Specifically, we collect a sample of the data in a dedicated big data platform (approximately 300TB of SSD storage, 500CPUs, 15GPUs, and 1TB of RAM) that we operate on-premises within TID data centers. On here, we store two large datasets that we collected from the commercial platform in December 2019 – January 2020, and September 2022 – March 2023.

Figure 101. Data collection approach from the commercial IoT platform.

For the ANCHOR Demo, we mainly focus on the **inference process**, which is what the engineering team mostly leverages. We show in Figure 100 the process of inference as the engineering team would use it. The pipeline runs according to a schedule that we have designed together with the engineering team:

- Training is performed monthly, at the end of the month, to capture the entire billing cycle of the IoT devices
- The data transformation and feature engineering jobs run every day, using the data collected during the previous day;
- Every IoT devices gets classified to a specific cluster using at least 7 days of data. If the device is a new device and there are not the 7 days available, then we discard this device from inference
- We run the anomaly detection per device using the ANCHOR model corresponding to the cluster that we previously identified.

Figure 102. ANCHOR Inference Pipeline.

Using the prototype that we described in Section 3.4.2, we created a dashboard where we inspect the anomaly scores for the IoT clients of the global roaming platform. With this, the engineering team can inspect the devices that show the highest probability of anomaly.

Figure 103. ANCHOR anomalies visualization.

6 Conclusions

In this document, we presented an update on the results of the work carried out in WP5 on the evaluation of the performance, sustainability and reliability of the 34 NI-solutions we developed across WP3 and WP4 of the DAEMON project. We validated such solutions against the 9 target KPIs of the project, which have been measured and assessed by a comprehensive set of 8 evaluations involving technical tools such as experimental testbeds, simulators or emulators, and datasets. These evaluations validate all the NI functionalities we defined in WP2.

Overall, each of the 34 NI-solutions integrate proof-of-concept activities that enabled us to collect the corresponding KPIs per activity. All evaluation activities are completed and targeted KPIs collected and analyzed. Furthermore, for two NI-solutions we evolved these PoCs into pilots with commercial units (TRL5). Last but not least, a DAEMON-wide NIP Architecture demo was performed showcasing the manner in which the NI functionalities we propose would integrate natively within the next-generation mobile network architecture.

7 References

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